

SOME INVESTIGATION ON DIELECTRIC RESONATOR ANTENNA SYSTEM

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By

Sumer Singh Singhal

(Enrolment No. 150001002071)

Under the Supervision of

Prof. Binod Kumar Kanaujia
Jawaharlal Nehru University, Delhi

Prof. Ajit Singh
B.T.K.I.T. Dwarahat, Almora

to the

Faculty of Electronics & Communication Engineering

UTTARAKHAND TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

(A State Government University)

DEHRADUN

August, 2020

Sumer Singh
Singhwal

CERTIFICATE

Certified that **Sumer Singh Singhwal** (Enrolment No. 150001002071) has carried out the research work presented in this thesis entitled " **Some Investigation on Dielectric Resonator Antenna System**" for the award of **Doctor of Philosophy in Electronics & Communication Engineering** department at **Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun, India**, under our supervision from **29-01-2015** to 31/8/2020 (**Duration of time: 5 Years & 7 Months**). The thesis embodies results of original work and studies have been carried out by the student himself and the contents of the thesis do not form the basis for the award of any other degree to the candidate or to anybody else from this or any other University/Institution.

Prof. Binod Kumar Kanaujia
School of Computational and Integrative Sciences
Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India

Prof. Ajit Singh
B.T.K.I.T. Dwarahat, Almora
Uttarakhand, India

 Dr. BINOD KUMAR KANAUJIA
Professor
School of Computational and Integrative Sciences
Jawaharlal Nehru University
New Delhi-110067

Date: 31/08/2020

The Viva Voce Examination was successfully held at
Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun on 31/08/2020

Vice Chancellor
/ Chairman
RDC Committee

External Examiner

Internal Examiner (1)

Internal Examiner (2)

Vice Chancellor
Uttarakhand Technical University
Dehradun

SOME INVESTIGATION ON DIELECTRIC RESONATOR ANTENNA SYSTEM

Sumer Singh Singhwai

ABSTRACT

Dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) is new area of research because of its inherent advantages over traditional microstrip patch antennas. Some of the advantages of DRA are low ohmic losses due to dielectric material body, more degree of freedom due to three-dimensional structure, high radiation efficiency, large bandwidth and easily excited by number of methods. Polarization of field wave also matter when diverse field is to be received by antenna. A circularly polarized antenna can receive field wave with almost any orientation whether it horizontally polarized, vertically polarized or circularly polarized. Our contribution in this field of research is presenting some novel and compact structures of DRA for different wireless applications. Mushroom shaped DRA, V-Shaped DRA, Kite shaped DRA are some of the novel structures which are presented for various wireless applications. These antennas are circularly polarized having operating bandwidth as per different applications.

In wireless communication, high speed data transmission needs are also exponentially increasing resulting WLAN, WiMAX, 4G and 5G standards. High speed data transfer become reality due to advent of multiple input multiple output (MIMO) technology. New age antennas are also required to fulfill MIMO requirements. In this catena of research, our contribution is presenting different configurations of MIMO antenna using DRA such as, dual-port dual-band circularly polarized MIMO DRA, dual-port circularly polarized agile MIMO DRA for WiMAX applications and novel, compact dual-port single element Kite shaped MIMO DRA. One of the main areas which are to be evolved with time are dual-port dual-band dual-circularly polarized MIMO DRA. Our contribution towards this newest area of research is presenting a dual-band dual-circularly polarized MIMO DRA. Frequency re-configurability is discussed in literature in details but new concept of circular polarization agility is discussed in one of paper presented by us. This field is in nurturing phase and lot of research in wireless data transmission using MIMO DRA is still to come in future.

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Sumer Singh Singhal

Sumner Singh
Singhwal

**DEDICATED TO
MY MASTER**

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LIST OF SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND NOMENCLATURE

3D- Three Dimension

4G-Fourth Generation

5G- Fifth Generation

AR- Axial Ratio

ARBW- Axial Ratio Band Width

ADRA- Annular Dielectric Resonator Antenna

BW- Band Width

CP- Circular Polarization

CDRA- Cylindrical Dielectric Resonator Antenna

DRA- Dielectric Resonator Antenna

DR- Dielectric Resonator

DG- Directive Gain

ECC- Envelope Correlation Coefficient

EF-Electric Field

GBW- Gain Band Width

IEEE- Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers

IBW- Impedance Band Width

LHCP-Left Hand Circular Polarization

MIMO- Multiple Input Multiple Output

MEG- Mean Effective Gain

MF-Magnetic Field

MPA-Microstrip Patch Antenna

PBW- Percentage Band Width

RHCP- Right Hand Circular Polarization

RADAR- Radio Detection and Ranging

RDRA- Rectangular Dielectric Resonator Antenna

RF- Radio Frequency

RL- Return Loss

SONAR-Sound Navigation and Ranging

SNR- Signal to Noise Ratio

TARC- Total Active Reflection Coefficient

VSWR-Voltage Standing Wave Ratio

VDRA- V-shaped Dielectric Resonator Antenna

WiMAX- Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access

Wi Fi- Wireless Fidelity

WLAN- Wireless Local Area Network

GHz- Giga Hertz

MHz- Mega Hertz

ϵ_r -Relative Dielectric Constant

ϵ_0 -Dielectric Constant of Vacuum

θ -Theta (Elevation Angle)

φ -Phi (Azimuth Angle)

π - Pi (Ratio of Circumference to Diameter of a Circle)

μ - Permeability

λ - Wavelength

$\tan \delta$ - Loss Tangent

η -Efficiency

f - Frequency

C - Velocity of Light in Vacuum

mm – millimeter

dB- Decibel

dBm- Decibel mW

mW- milli Watts

dBi- Decibel isotropic

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DRA in Wireless Communication

Human nature is to run before speed whether it is high speed car racing or high data rate communication system. The advent of modern communication has now become essence of human communication system. There are various means of wireless communications such as 4G/5G cellular networks, Wi-Fi, WLAN, WiMAX, satellite communication, RADAR, SONAR, DTH broadcast etc. In every wireless communication system, a device which makes it wireless known as “Antenna” is used. The Oxford dictionary says “Antenna or aerial is a piece of equipment made of wire or long straight pieces of metal for receiving or sending radio and television signals”. According to Balanis2005 [1], “the antenna is the transitional structure between free-space and a guiding device. The guiding device or transmission line may take the form of a coaxial line or a hollow pipe (waveguide), and it is used to transport electromagnetic energy from the transmitting source to the antenna, or from the antenna to the receiver”. DRA can be described as a transitional structure made up of dielectric material and excited by various means to, work as efficient radiators for different applications. The two books on DRA Luk (2003) [2] and Petosa (2007) [3] describes details of DRA in full length. Harrington [4] discussed time harmonic fields and its behavior in detail. In 1960s, Okaya, Karp and Iveland [5-7] discussed working of dielectric microwave resonator for different applications. In 1980s, Long, McAllister, Shen and Kaifez [8-13] have undergone a systematic and purposeful study of DRs. Later, major work on DRAs have been

contributed by three groups which are mentioned here, first is Kishk, Gilsson and Junker [14-26], second is Ittipiboon and Mongia [27-42], third is Luk and Leung [43-53]. In [54-55], DRA technology is reviewed in respect of historical and recent developments.

In 1990s, Foschini [56-57] presented concept of multi-antennas which later revolutionized as MIMO antenna system. In 1999, Telatar [58] found that there is increase in channel capacity of isotropic MIMO channel with the increase in number of radiators, so the channel capacity is directly proportional to number of radiators used to transmit. This study boosted emergence to MIMO communication system which later on practically tested by Bell laboratory. Today, MIMO system is inevitably important in implementation of 4G and 5G communication networks.

1.2 Scope of DRAs

According to Collins dictionary dielectric means “a substance or medium that can sustain a static electric field within it or a substance in which an electric field gives rise to no net flow of electric charge but only to a displacement of charge”. Dielectric materials are insulating materials with characteristics of electric polarization. It means positive and negative charges displace themselves in accordance to EF applied. Dipole moment of material is also disturbed due to applied EF. These dielectric materials can be distinguished on the basis of their ‘dielectric constant’ or ‘relative permittivity’ expressed as Eq. (1.1)

$$\epsilon_r = \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_0} \quad (1.1)$$

where

ϵ_0 -permittivity of free space

ϵ -permittivity of the medium

The dielectric constant of any material helps in evaluating its ability to carry ac current in respect to that of free space or vacuum. Whenever a potential is applied to material, dielectric constant also relates with how much amount of energy is stored by the material in respect of vacuum. It is the reason why dielectric material used previously in condensers to up their storage capacity, in microwave filters, resonators etc. In last few decades, dielectric

materials are also preferred in antennas because of several disadvantages of metallic antennas and advantages of dielectric as radiators which includes low metallic losses, high radiation efficiency, more dimensional freedom etc. Some of the characteristics of DRA are discussed here.

1. Design and Dimensional Flexibility

Unlimited shape and dimensional flexibility available while designing a DRA. In literature several shapes were already discussed and more shapes are yet to be discussed. Some of the shapes of DRA are shown in Fig. 1.1

Fig. 1.1 Dielectric resonator antennas (DRAs) structures. [54]

2. High Temperature Tolerance

At high temperatures, high metallic losses can perturb the antenna performances which is not possible in DRAs, so these are more suitable for adverse circumstances which includes warfare, fire etc.

3. Wide Impedance Bandwidth

In comparison to microstrip patch antennas, DRAs yield wider impedance bandwidth. Figure 1.2 demonstrates comparison between patch antennas and DRAs in terms of impedance bandwidth. It shows DRA's impedance bandwidth is 15.6 %

in comparison to microstrip patch antenna's bandwidth which is 2.6 % at resonance frequency of 35 GHz [63].

Fig. 1.2 DRA and microstrip antenna (MSA)- IBW comparison [3]

4. Integration with other antennas is easier

One important advantage of DRA is its ease and simplicity of joining or combining with other structures. It can easily be loaded upon other radiators which is shown in Fig. 1.3. It can be observed that IBW increases from 2% to 10% after loading of DRA on microstrip patch antenna [3].

Fig. 1.3 DRA loaded upon square and circular microstrip patches [3].

5. Minimal metallic losses

DRAs are nothing but a model of dielectric material which are non-conducting unlike metals. So, while working as radiators, there is less conductor losses in DRAs as compared to other metallic antennas such as patch antennas. This characteristics of DRAs yields appreciable radiation efficiency at higher frequency in comparison to their counterparts. Figure 1.4 shows comparison of radiation efficiencies of DRA and patch antenna. Figure 1.4 shows that radiation efficiency of DRA approaches 95 % while that of patch antenna has radiation efficiency of 86% [63]. In [3], it was demonstrated that at 24. GHz, DRA array achieved peak gain of 20 dBi whereas microstrip patch array antenna has maximum gain of 19 dBi at 24.5 GHz.

Fig. 1.4 Comparison of radiation efficiencies of a) DRA and b) microstrip patch antenna [63]

Fig. 1.5 Basic feed mechanism in DRA a) Probe Feed b) Microstrip line feed c) Aperture couple feed

6. Flexibility in excitation of DRA

There are various methodologies discussed in the literature to excite different modes in the DRA. Basic feed mechanism are probe feed, microstrip line feed and aperture coupled feed as shown in Fig. 1.5. There are some other feed mechanism apart from basic mechanism such as conformal feed and coplanar feeds discussed in [2, 3].

1.3 Objective of Thesis

Thesis are to be made to address some specific research problem. The purpose of this thesis is to address following research problem statements.

- 1) Design and investigation of DRA for wireless applications
- 2) Design and investigation of MIMO DRA for wireless applications.

Distinguished applications of DRAs has already been discussed in literature, such as in satellite communication, WLAN, WiMAX, 5G network etc. Figures 1.6 -1.9 shows satellite communication, WLAN, WiMAX and 5G communication network examples. Objective of this thesis also covers designing and study of DRA and MIMO DRA for these applications.

Fig. 1.6 Concept of satellite communication [59]

Fig. 1.7 An example of Wi-Fi network [60]

Fig. 1.8 An example of WiMAX network [61]

Fig. 1.9 Futuristic 5G communication network [62]

In continuation to current research, in first objective statement, designing and investigating DRAs for different applications has been involved. To achieve this objective, three novel DRAs has been designed for different applications. First, a circularly polarized DRA with high gain of 8.6 dBi has been designed and investigated for microwave image sensing and wearable sensor applications. Major advantages of discussed antenna are wide bandwidth, high gain all across mm wave band. This DR is excited using microstrip line feed network. This feed network consists of circular loop type network which maintain phase

difference of 90° to produce circular polarization. The gain of antenna is approximately 8.6 dBi on 25-26 GHz band and 3 dB axial ratio bandwidth is almost 1 GHz from 25.2-26.2 GHz. 10 dB impedance bandwidth is 24-27 GHz. Second, a probe fed circularly polarized V-shaped DRA has been designed and studied for X-band applications. Measured impedance bandwidth and measured axial ratio bandwidth (ARBW) of the proposed antenna are 25% (7.85-10.1 GHz) and 4% (8.35-8.7 GHz), respectively. This antenna can also be used in the MIMO antenna system and smart antenna array because of its directional circular polarization property. Proposed antenna operates in X band which has a plethora of applications as discussed in [211, 212] such as Radar and satellite communication. Smart beam steering antenna array is also one of the emerging applications in X band. Third, a novel mushroom shaped low dielectric material DRA has been analyzed and scripted for 5G communication applications. This antenna operates at 3-5 GHz frequency range. Impedance bandwidth of antenna is 34.5% having range 3.5-5.1 GHz. Axial ratio bandwidth is 33% from 3.55-5 GHz. Peak gain at broadside direction is 6.5 dBi and average gain throughout operating band is 5.5 dBi. Latest International Telecommunication Union documentation [216] suggests lower 5G bands for 5G communication are 3.5-5 GHz.

Presently MIMO technology is growing rapidly due to its various advantages such as high data rate and low coupling loss. This advancement in MIMO DRA motivated us to enter into this field. In second objective statement, designing and investigating MIMO DRAs for different wireless application has been carried out. Under this objective three MIMO DRAs have been studied. First, a dual port kite-shaped MIMO DRA with high gain of 7.4 dBi has been studied and analyzed for WLAN applications. The measured impedance bandwidth of dual feed MIMO DRA is 4.7-6.2 GHz (27.5%) and maximum gain has been measured 7.4 dBi. Port isolation bandwidth for MIMO DRA has been measured 5-6 GHz which is under impedance bandwidth and covers 5 GHz IEEE (802.11a/h/j/n/ac/ax) band for WLAN. Second, a circular polarization controllable dual port MIMO DRA has been discussed for Sub-6 GHz and WiMAX applications. Measured impedance bandwidth measured axial ratio bandwidth (ARBW) of the discussed radiator is 22.2% (3.12-3.9 GHz) and 4.25% (3.45-3.6 GHz) in broadside direction ($\theta = 0$; $\varphi = 0$), respectively. Isolation

between ports is better than 20 dB over the entire impedance bandwidth and maximum gain of the antenna is 7.2 dBi. Third, a dual band circularly polarized MIMO DRA has been designed and studied for WLAN/WiMAX/Sub-6 GHz applications. Demand of circular polarization antennas has increased because of their various advantages such as high efficiency, low polarization losses and many others discussed in detail in chapter no. 2. To meet this demand we have primarily focused on circularly polarized DRAs and MIMO DRAs.

1.4 Thesis Organization

In chapter 1, brief historical aspect and scope of DRAs has been discussed which is followed by objectives of thesis. Different wireless applications has also been discussed in this chapter.

In chapter 2, a detailed review of literature concerning with DRAs has been discussed. Overall chapter is broadly divided in two parts which are DRAs and MIMO DRAs. Further, DRAs are discussed and compared in details on the basis of structure of DRAs such as conventional and non-conventional. Conventional DRAs covers rectangular and cylindrical DRA whereas non-conventional DRAs covers various other shapes other than conventional, such as triangular, hexagon, alphabet-shaped etc. Performances of DRAs have been compared on the basis of conventional shape of DRA which are as follows.

a) Rectangular DRAs

b) Cylindrical DRAs

MIMO DRAs are discussed and compared in detail in three categories which are as follows.

a) Wideband MIMO DRAs

b) Dual band MIMO DRAs

c) Dual band circularly polarized MIMO DRAs

In chapter 3, a rectangular DRA has been discussed for 28 GHz band sensor applications. This DRA is fed by loop like microstrip feed to achieve circular polarization. This antenna exhibits wide bandwidth and good performance over mm wave band. This DRA is made of low dielectric constant material to widen the impedance bandwidth range of antenna.

In chapter 4, a non-conventional shaped DRA inspired by alphabet V has been discussed. DRA is made of Eccostock Hik material having relative dielectric constant of 10. Here, probe feed method is used to excite DRA and internal circular patch which resulted in circular polarized radiation. Due to its V shape, it behaves symmetrically in both linear directions.

In chapter 5, another non-conventional shaped DRA inspired by Mushroom has been discussed for wireless applications. This DRA exhibits wideband operation with circular polarization. This DRA is also made of low dielectric constant material to widen impedance bandwidth of antenna. Due to optimized dimensions of the antenna dielectric losses are minimized while maintaining good circular polarization bandwidth.

In chapter 6, a single feed DRA is proposed followed by dual feed MIMO DRA. Aperture coupled feed is used to achieve wide bandwidth. Advantages of proposed antennas are wide bandwidth, high gain and compact substrate size of area 32.8 cm^2 . Single element MIMO DRA are always difficult to construct because of difficulty in mode excitation and input isolation. This single element MIMO DRA overcomes both the difficulty with improved gain.

In chapter 7, a novel concept of CP agility is presented with two antennas configurations. Two dual-port multiple input multiple output DRAs are proposed. Proposed antennas evinced the CP agility by mechanical insertion and extraction of concentric cylindrical shells of different radii using robotic tool changer or robotic quick-change system.

In chapter 8, a dual-band MIMO ring DRA with appreciated CP performance has been proposed. It demonstrates circular polarization in both the operating frequency bands and size of antenna is also small which makes it good choice for WiMAX dual band applications and sub-6 GHz band applications such as 5G communications.

In chapter 9, conclusion of the work explained in the thesis is discussed and future possibilities of the work and field is presented which is followed by references mentioned throughout this thesis. Objective of the thesis is achieved chapter wise by studying DRAs in chapters 2, 3, 4 and 5 and then followed by MIMO DRAs in chapters 6, 7 and 8.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Almighty has given humans different sensors and antennas such as nose, ears etc. for their transmission and reception of physical signals. It created curiosity in humans to design antennas for transmitting and receiving wireless signals. After first practical monopole antenna in 1895, researchers have travelled a long distance to reach modern patch antennas. Microstrip patch antennas have come into practical implementation in 1970s. But the hunt for better antennas yielded new types of antennas made up of dielectric materials in 1980s. Thereafter, a vast literature was published in reputed journals discussing various aspects, design and techniques in DRA [2-55]. In 1990s, the concept of MIMO antennas was presented which was further explored by using DRA in 2008 by Ishimiya et. al. [65,66]. Circular polarization is very much desirable property of antenna for better reception and low polarization losses. Current research is in progress in the field of efficient DRA, MIMO DRAs and CP MIMO DRAs. This thesis is also one step towards this domain of research.

2.2 Circular Polarization

Polarization may be defined as the bent or orientation of E.F. vector in space [1]. The electromagnetic wave varies with time and space and E.F. is perpendicular to M.F. counterpart all the time. So, in literature, it is suggested to analyze orientation and motion of E.F. vector which is termed as polarization of the wave. Polarization may be divided into different types depending upon variation of E.F. vector, for example, Linear, Circular and Elliptical. Linear polarization means E.F. vector moves in linear fashion which can be horizontally or vertically. Elliptical polarization means E.F. vector along orthogonal direction having unequal magnitude resulting elliptical path of motion of E.F. vector. Let us consider a plane wave travelling in +z direction, there will be two E.F. components in x and

y directions, respectively. At the start of travelling plane wave when $z=0$, the time domain E.F. may be defined as Eq. (2.1).

$$E = \hat{x}E_x \cos(\omega t + \phi_x) + \hat{y}E_y \cos(\omega t + \phi_y) \quad (2.1)$$

Where, E_x and E_y are E.F. components in x and y directions, respectively.

ϕ_x and ϕ_y are phase of E_x and E_y , respectively.

For $\phi_x = \phi_y = \phi$, magnitude of E.F. given by Eq. (2.2) and phase of E.F. is given by Eq. (2.3)

$$|E| = \sqrt{(E_x^2 + E_y^2)} \cos(\omega t + \phi) \quad (2.2)$$

$$\psi = \arctan \left(\frac{E_x}{E_y} \right) \quad (2.3)$$

Where, ψ is an angular orientation with respect to the y-axis.

If $E_x = E_y = E_0$ and phase $\phi_x - \phi_y = \pm\pi/2$ then magnitude and phase of E.F. is given by Eq. (2.4) and Eq. (2.5), respectively.

$$|E| = \sqrt{2}E_0 \quad (2.4)$$

$$\psi = \phi_y \pm \omega t \quad (2.5)$$

In circular polarization two orthogonal linear components of E.F. vector must satisfy two conditions [1]:

- a) both the components must have equal magnitude
- b) time phase difference of odd multiples of 90° must be present in two field components.

Figure 2.1 demonstrates both the conditions of circular polarization. AR is one of the parameters to judge amount of circular polarization of the wave. It is defined as ratio of field magnitudes in orthogonal directions of the time-varying electromagnetic wave as mentioned in Eq. (2.6).

$$AR \text{ (in dB)} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{E_1}{E_2} \right) \quad (2.6)$$

For elliptical polarization, where circularity of field is distorted, AR can also be defined as ratio of major to minor axis of the ellipse. When $AR=0$ it is perfect case of circular polarization whereas when AR increases, the distortion in circular polarization increases, resulting elliptical polarization. However, in practical cases $AR < 3$ dB is also acceptable as circular polarized wave.

Fig. 2.1 Circular Polarization

Advantage of CP wave antenna is that it can receive any linear polarized wave without any orientation problem. So, a CP wave antenna can easily receive horizontally, vertically and circularly polarized wave without much loss. Depending upon clockwise or anticlockwise movement of field vector, a CP wave can be further categorized as LHCP and RHCP. An antenna with CP capability is always preferable over its linear polarized counterparts but it is a tedious task to maintain CP bandwidth over impedance bandwidth of an antenna. There are various techniques to generate circular polarization in DRAs which have been already implemented in literature such as using single microstrip feed technique, using different geometrical DRA shape, using different slot excitation techniques, parasitic strip and parasitic patch excitation technique, multiple points feed DRA technique and sequential rotation technique. Advantage of circularly polarized antennas has been discussed in [67-69] in more detail. For MIMO antenna system CP antennas are preferred to increase its diversity performance. Presently CP MIMO antennas using microstrip patch and DRA are preferred in mobile communication, satellite communication and similar wireless applications.

2.3 DRAs

In 1980s Long and McAllister [11-13] presented the concept of hemispherical, cylindrical and rectangular DRAs. In 1960s, low loss ceramics have been used as high-Q DRs in microwave applications. DRs have been used as replacement of cavity resonators because of more adaptability to printed circuits. To prevent radiation and obtaining high-Q, DRs are enclosed inside metal cavities which is also important for filter design. DRs are generally made up of material with $\epsilon_r \geq 35$. DRs can become efficient radiators over a broad range of frequencies when metal shielding is removed and dielectric constant of DRs is reduced [39].

Main features of DRAs can be summarized [39, 40]

- a) In traditional antennas size of metallic radiators is approximately proportional to λ_0 whereas in DRAs length of the structure is approximately proportional to $\lambda_0/\sqrt{\epsilon_r}$ where $\lambda_0 = c/f_0$ being the free-space wavelength at the resonant frequency f_0 and ϵ_r is the relative permittivity of the DR material. DRAs with high ϵ_r also has a smaller form factor.
- b) As dielectric material is used in the construction of DRA, so no metallic losses present here which results in high radiation efficiency when lower ϵ_r material is used. So, DRAs are preferable at higher frequencies where metallic losses become very high.
- c) DRAs have shown large IBW as compared to patch antennas.
- d) There are various techniques to excite different modes in DRAs as per the requirement of applications. DRA arrays are also becoming popular due to ease of excitation techniques. Gain, polarization and bandwidth like characteristics can also be easily varied by using different design techniques.

One more important advantage of DRAs are its three dimensionalities. There are infinite shapes in which DRAs can be moulded. Some common shapes are rectangular, cylindrical, hemispherical and triangular which are depicted in Fig. 2.2.

Fig.2.2 DRAs of various geometry [2]

Fig. 2.3 Sectored and elliptical shaped DRAs [3]

Fig. 2.4 Conical and cross-shaped DRAs [3]

Some more uncommon shapes such as sectored cylindrical, sectored ring, elliptical, conical, cross, triangle and truncated pyramid, stepped rectangular, stepped cylindrical and hemispherical DRAs are shown in Fig. 2.3 - 2.6. In the next section, two

conventional shapes of DRA which are rectangular and cylindrical have been discussed in detail. Although, there are other non-conventional shapes of DRAs such as triangular, bowtie, trapezoidal, pyramid and many more, but major research has been done on studying the conventional shapes and applying similar theories on non-conventional shapes of DRA.

Fig. 2.5 Triangle and truncated pyramid-shaped DRAs [3]

Fig.2.6 Stepped rectangular, stepped cylindrical and hemisphere shaped DRAs [3]

2.3.1 Rectangular Dielectric Resonator Antenna (RDRA)

From the beginning of research in the field of DRA, humans are more interested in two shapes which are easy to construct. These are cuboid and circular shaped DRA. Cuboid shaped DRA are generally termed as RDRA which has length, breadth and height in three cartesian coordinate directions as shown in Fig 2.7. First RDRA was proposed by McAllister et al. [12] in 1983. Similar to waveguide theory, various field modes propagate in DRA which directly yield radiation. According to Okaya and Barash [5], there are two types of modes

which exist in RDRA which are TE(H) and TM(E). But still, practical observation of TM(H) mode is under investigation whereas TE (H) is well observed in [6-7]. Due to three independent dimensions of RDRA, it has three lowest order modes in directions x, y, z correspondingly. These modes are TE_{111}^x , TE_{111}^y and TE_{111}^z as explained in [39]. Due to a similar analysis of all three modes, design steps for TE_{111}^z are discussed here only. For TE_{111}^z mode field inside RDRA is derived from magnetic potential directed in z-direction [4]. Field components are given here in Eq. (2.7-2.13).

Fig. 2.7 Basic model of RDRA [39]

$$H_z = \frac{(K_x^2 + K_y^2)}{j\omega\mu_0} A \cos(K_x x) \cos(K_y y) \cos(K_z z) \quad (2.7)$$

$$H_x = \frac{K_x K_z}{j\omega\mu_0} A \sin(K_x x) \cos(K_y y) \sin(K_z z) \quad (2.8)$$

$$H_y = \frac{K_y K_z}{j\omega\mu_0} A \cos(K_x x) \sin(K_y y) \sin(K_z z) \quad (2.9)$$

$$E_x = AK_y \cos(K_x x) \sin(K_y y) \cos(K_z z) \quad (2.10)$$

$$E_y = -AK_x \sin(K_x x) \cos(K_y y) \cos(K_z z) \quad (2.11)$$

$$E_y = 0 \quad (2.12)$$

$$K_0 = \frac{2\pi f_0}{c} \quad (2.13)$$

Where

A – constant

K_x, K_y, K_z – wavenumbers along the x, y and z directions respectively -

f_0 – resonant frequency

K_0 – free space wavenumber corresponding to f_0

c – velocity of light in vacuum

At the resonator surface if magnetic wall boundary condition is applied then the following design equations are obtained. [39]

$$K_x = \frac{\pi}{a} \quad (2.14)$$

$$K_y = \frac{\pi}{b} \quad (2.15)$$

$$K_z \tan\left(K_z \cdot \frac{d}{2}\right) = \sqrt{(\epsilon_r - 1)K_0^2 - K_z^2} \quad (2.16)$$

$$K_x^2 + K_y^2 + K_z^2 = \epsilon_r K_0^2 \quad (2.17)$$

Where ϵ_r – relative dielectric constant of DR material

Fig. 2.8 Normalized frequency of RDRA [2]

To design a RDRA of a particular material having dielectric constant ϵ_r . Eq. (2.14-2.17) must satisfy for a resonant frequency of interest and physical dimensions of DR. An approximate relation between dimension and the resonant frequency is shown using normalized frequency (F) of RDRA in Fig. 2.8. It can be observed from Fig. 2.8 that normalized frequency increase with increase of length (a) with respect to height (b). It is

also dependent on ratio of width (d) to height (b) of DRA. Expression of normalized frequency is shown by Eq. (2.18).

$$F = \frac{2\pi a f_0 \sqrt{\epsilon_r}}{c} \quad (2.18)$$

There are various techniques to feed or excite the RDRA for example probe feed, slot feed, line feed etc. Some of the excitation methods are shown in Fig. 2.9 - 2.11.

Fig. 2.9 RDRA excited in TE_{111}^z the mode by using probe feed method [39]

Fig. 2.10 RDRA excited in TE_{111}^z using the slot feed method [39]

Fig. 2.11 RDRA excited using a simple microstrip line feed method [39]

In 1983, McAllister, Long and Conway [12] proposed first RDRA with dimensions 3 cm x 1.5 cm x 1.5 cm and relative permittivity of DR was 8.9. Figure 2.12 shows antenna geometry and measured impedance bandwidth of proposed antenna. DR excited by monopole probe feed which yield radiation from DR in normal direction from ground.

Fig. 2.12 Antenna geometry and measured impedance bandwidth [12]

Fig. 2.13 Geometry of aperture coupled CP RDRA [94]

In 1995, Oliver et.al. [94] proposed first circularly polarized RDRA. This RDRA built with material of relative permittivity 40 and demonstrated ARBW of 1.8 % by applying slot coupled feed. Figure 2.13 shows the geometry of first CP RDRA. It is pertinent to note that first circularly polarized DRA has been made, nearly after one decade of first RDRA which was proposed by McAllister et al. [12].

RDRAs have always been a popular choice among researchers because of inherent advantages such as ease of design, various degree of freedom and ease of feed. In [70-71] design and development of recent circularly polarized DRAs have been reviewed. From [72-103], various RDRAs has been proposed by researchers having various capabilities and applicability. In Table 2.1, a comparison is made between different RDRAs on the basis of resonant frequency, the material used for DRA, gain and bandwidth of DRA. It can be observed that relative dielectric constant of DRAs varies from 9.8 – 80 shown in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Comparison of RDRA Designs

S.No.	f_r (GHz)	ϵ_r	Excitation	Max. Gain (dBi)	BW (GHz)	BW (%)	Ref.
1	94	11.7	Slot	10.5	91-97	6.3	72
2	2.09	79	Coplanar	5.42	2.06-2.11	2.4	73
3	5.25	12.6	Slot	-	4.95-5.6	12	74
4	3	48	Microstrip	9	2.49-3.125	22	75
5	3.8	10.2	Annular	3.97	3.35-4.25	23	76
6	5.6	10.2	Annular	5	4.92-6.21	23	77
7	5.5	10.2	CPW	3.8	4.71-6.30	29	78
8	4.5	9.8	Probe	4.8	3.4-5.3	42	79

Table 2.1 (Continued)

9	11.9	10.8	Slot	-	10.1-13.7	28	41
10	4.53	9.8	Probe	6	3.28-5.77	55	80
11	12.4	10.2	Slot	-	9.0-16.4	59	81
12	12.5	10.2	Probe	7	8.6-16.4	65	82
13	11.85	9.2	Probe	8.6	7.2-16.5	78	83
14	5.94	10.2	Microstrip	-	3.46-8.42	84	84
15	5.83	9.2	Patch	6.1	5.14-6.51	24	85
16	60	12.9	CPW	3.6	54-71.5	29.2	86
17	59.56	48	CPW	3.2	58.655- 60.55	3.1	87
18	2.16, 2.41	10	Coupling Slot & Microstrip	3.2	1.85-2.52	30.9	88
19	4.21	15	Bevel Shaped Patch	~4	2.13-6.08	96	89
20	3.7	10	CPW	~6.2	3.6-3.86 & 3.54- 3.98	7 & 11.6	90
21	3.1	6.6	Probe	~5	3.1-10.6	110 VSWR	91
22	2.45	80	Microstrip	-	2.17-2.77	25	92
23	2.6	12	Slot	4.6	2.15-2.77	25	93

Table 2.1 (Continued)

24	5.4	40	Slot	-	5.23-5.65	1.8 (3 dB AR)	94
25	14.75	10.8	Slot	-	14.35- 14.80 AR	3.0 (3 dB AR)	95
26	5.4	10.8	Slot	-	5.2-5.6	6.6 (3 dB AR)	96
27	2.45/5.8AR	9.7	CPW	3/4	2.36-2.55 / 5.67- 6.05AR	7.4/6.6 (3 dB AR)	97
28	2.2	12	Archimedean spiral slot	4.95	-	25.5/36.36(3 dB AR)	98
29	3.10/3.52/4. 28	10	Slot	2/3.5	-	19.8/6.2 24.3/6.2 AR	99
30	1.48/1.71/2. 31/2.75	9.8	Aperture coupling	6/8.5	-	6.3/3.68 25.3/35.3 AR	100
31	23.86	10	Aperture coupling	5.8	23.30- 24.59		101
32	3.14	9.8	Q mark line feed	1.51	2.8-3.6	2.8-3.7	102
33	2.4/3.3	9.8	Cross shape coupled		2.38- 2.68/3.25- 3.56	2.38-2.48	103

2.3.2 Cylindrical Dielectric Resonator Antenna (CDRA)

Earlier RDRA was formed by following the cartesian coordinate system, similarly, CDRA can be formed by following cylindrical coordinate system having radius, height and azimuth angle. A basic CDRA is displayed in Fig. 2.12. An isolated CDRA is placed in vacuum can be considered double in height when placed on ground plane, due to image theory [2]. A CDRA can be excited using different feeding methods similar to RDRA as discussed in previous section.

Fig. 2.12 Cylindrical DRA placed on the ground plane [3]

Similar to RDRA there are various modes that an isolated CDRA can exhibit as shown in Table 2.2. The resonant frequency of isolated CDRA for various modes can be computed for a given aspect ratio (h/a) of the resonator. If the $\epsilon_r \geq 100$, then value of normalized wavenumber ($K_0 a$) is given by Eq (2.18) for a particular aspect ratio of CDRA. [40]

$$(K_0 a) \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (2.18)$$

Where K_0 expressed in Eq (2.8)

For CDRA with $\epsilon_r \leq 50$, Eq (2.14) get modify to become Eq (2.19)

$$(K_0 a) \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r + X}} \quad (2.19)$$

In mode nomenclature shown in Table 2.2, δ is a half-wave variation of field in z direction. Eq. (2.19) can be seen as an approximation of Eq. (2.18) for lower dielectric

Table 2.2 Different modes of an isolated CDRA [40]

Mode	Plane of Symmetry (z=0)	Nomenclature Ref [62-64]	Far Fields	Orientation of Far Fields Multipole	
$TE_{01\delta}$	Magnetic Wall	$TE_{01\delta}$	Magnetic Dipole	Axial (Vertical)	
$TE_{011+\delta}$	Electric Wall	$TE_{011+\delta}$	Magnetic Quadrupole	Axial (Vertical)	
$TM_{01\delta}$	Electric Wall	$TM_{01\delta}$	Electric Dipole	Axial (Vertical)	
$TM_{011+\delta}$	Magnetic Wall	$TM_{011+\delta}$	Electric Quadrupole	Axial (Vertical)	
$HE_{11\delta}$	Electric Wall	$HEM_{11\delta}$	Magnetic Dipole	Transverse (Horizontal)	
$HE_{21\delta}$	Electric Wall	$HEM_{21\delta}$	Magnetic Quadrupole	Transverse (Horizontal)	
$EH_{11\delta}$	Magnetic Wall	$HEM_{12\delta}$	Electric Dipole	Transverse (Horizontal)	
$EH_{21\delta}$	Magnetic Wall	$HEM_{22\delta}$	Electric Quadrupole	Transverse (Horizontal)	

constants. X is to be found empirically by comparing results and methods as mentioned in [40]. Mongia et al. proposed general formula for resonant frequencies of various modes in CDRA [40] given in Eq. (2.20-2.23).

$HE_{11\delta}$ Mode:

$$K_0 a = \frac{2\pi f_0}{c} = \frac{6.324}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r + 2}} \left[0.27 + 0.36 \frac{a}{2h} + 0.02 \left(\frac{a}{2h} \right)^2 \right] \quad (2.20)$$

Eq. (2.20) is valid for $0.4 \leq a/h \leq 6$

$TE_{01\delta}$ Mode:

$$K_0 a = \frac{2\pi f_0}{c} = \frac{2.327}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r + 1}} \left[1.0 + 0.2123 \frac{a}{h} - 0.00898 \left(\frac{a}{2h} \right)^2 \right] \quad (2.21)$$

Eq. (2.21) is valid for $0.33 \leq a/h \leq 5$ and $\epsilon_r \leq 25$

$TE_{011+\delta}$ Mode:

$$K_0 a = \frac{2\pi f_0}{c} = \frac{2.208}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r + 1}} \left[1.0 + 0.7013 \frac{a}{h} - 0.002713 \left(\frac{a}{2h} \right)^2 \right] \quad (2.22)$$

Eq. (2.22) is valid for $0.33 \leq a/h \leq 5$

$TM_{01\delta}$ Mode:

$$K_0 a = \frac{2\pi f_0}{c} = \frac{\sqrt{3.83^2 + \left(\frac{\pi a}{2h} \right)^2}}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r + 2}} \quad (2.23)$$

Eq. (2.23) is valid for $0.33 \leq a/h \leq 5$

Fig. 2.13 Antenna geometry and feed configurations[11]

In 1983, first cylindrical DRA was proposed by Long et al. [11]. Results have been measured for various configurations of CDRA with radius to height ratio of cylinder chosen 0.15, 0.3, 0.5, 1.67 and relative permittivity of DRA was 8.9. Direction of radiation was found normal to the ground with the use of probe feed method. Figure 2.13 shows antenna geometry and feed configuration of the first CDRA.

In 2000, Leung et al. [119] proposed a circularly polarized CDRA. Here CP fields are generated with the help of two unequal conformal strips which are exciting two degenerate orthogonal modes. To produce CP fields, the ratio of lengths of two conformal probes act as tuning parameter which decides variation in CP field. If $L_1 > L_2$ then DRA worked in LHCP operation and for $L_2 > L_1$ DRA worked in RHCP operation. A 3dB AR bandwidth reported was 3.5%.

Following the footsteps of Long et al. various researchers proposed different versions of CDRA with different excitation methods [104-127]. There are various feed method adopted to achieve circular polarization in DRA. These methods includes (i) using cross slot aperture of unequal length, (ii) using C-shaped slot (iii) using U-shaped slot (iv) using shorted annular slot, (v) using parasitic slot, (vi) using reversed T-shaped slot, (vii) using monofilar-spiral slot, (viii) using inclined slot, (ix) slot with parasitic strip excitation, (x) power divider network feed, (xi) dual conformal strips of unequal length, (xii) parasitic strip with hybrid coupler, (xiii) sequential rotation technique and many more. These feeds are discussed in literature in detail [1, 2, 70, 71]. Development of circularly polarized DRA has been ascended due to various advantages of CP antennas such as they are less sensitive to the transceiver orientation and less sensitive to propagation effects. In contrast, a linearly polarized antenna cannot transmit or receive the signal orthogonal to the transmitted and received field. A comparison has been made between recently proposed CDRA's on the basis of parameters like gain, impedance bandwidth, excitation technique etc. This comparison is depicted in Table 2.3. There are a lot of non-conventional shapes of DRA such as triangular, hexagonal, trapezoidal, alphabet shaped, cross-shaped, stair shaped etc. [128-150]. There can be infinitely different shapes other than conventional rectangular and cylindrical shapes and different feeding methods also studied vastly in literature. But the advantages of conventional shaped DRAs lies in its ease of fabrication.

Table 2.3 Comparison of CDRA Designs

S.No.	f_r (GHz)	ϵ_r	Excitation	Max. Gain (dBi)	BW (GHz)	BW (%)	Ref.
1	4.18	82	Strip	5	4.12-4.25	3.6	104
2	0.82	12	Probe	4	0.80-0.85	1.7	105
3	2.89	20	Probe	4.8	-	2.5	106
4	1.90/2.45	35.5	Microstrip	6.5/5.5	1.87- 1.92/2.43- 2.48	5.3/2.1	107
5	2.7	48	Microstrip	9.2	2.48-3.08	26	108
6	3.5	12	Probe	6.5	3.04-3.98	27	109
7	5.75	10.2	Slot	5	5.1-6.7	27	110
8	3	20.8	Microstrip	3.35	2.43-3.47	35	111
9	6.5	10	Aperture	4	5.3-7.75	28	112
10	59.96	48	CPW	3.2	59.02-60.74	28.6	113
11	3.38	10	Probe	4	3-4	29	114
12	3.5/5.8	15	Probe	1.3/3.3	3.4-3.6/3.4- 3.6/-5.99	5.71/7.99	115
13	2.45	9.4	Probe	2.26	2.182.63	18.75	116
14	7.49	10	Probe	9.5	-	-	117
15	3.9/7.4	10	Probe	5.8/6	-	7.03/8.6	118

Table 2.3 (Continued)

16	5.36/5.47 (AR)	9.5	Two-strip feed	-	5.05-5.8/5.1- 6.2(AR)	13.7/20 (3dB AR)	119
17	1.9	9.5	Four-Probe	4.9	1.65-2.14 AR	25.9 (3dB AR)	120
18	3.2	9.4	Probe	8.88	3.05-3.91	24.7 (3dB AR)	121
19	3.3	11.5	Probe	~7	3.3-3.62 AR	6.4 (3dB AR)	122
20	2.45	79	Aperture coupled	2.7	2.359-2.51 AR	5.6/3.46 (3dB AR)	123
21	6.7	10.2	Probe	6.8	5.7-13.2	79	124
22	2.4	6.85	Aperture coupled	9.6	1.7-1.88/2.4- 2.48	10/3.2	125
23	5.8	10	Quadrature feed	5.8	4.6-7.25 AR	43/42(3dB AR)	126
19	3.3	11.5	Probe	~7	3.3-3.62 AR	6.4 (3dB AR)	122
20	2.45	79	Aperture coupled	2.7	2.359-2.51 AR	5.6/3.46 (3dB AR)	123
21	6.7	10.2	Probe	6.8	5.7-13.2	79	124
22	2.4	6.85	Aperture coupled	9.6	1.7-1.88/2.4- 2.48	10/3.2	125
23	5.8	10	Quadrature feed	5.8	4.6-7.25 AR	43/42(3dB AR)	126
24	4.4, 6.1	9.8	Aperture coupled	4.9, 5.6	600 MHz , 500 MHz	-	127

2.4 MIMO DRA

In the present decade, increased growth of wireless communication system resulted in the development of the MIMO antenna. These antenna system with the ability to suppress fading, increased coverage & connectivity, high throughput and low latency, play crucial role in the development of various RF and microwave communication system. The 4th generation and upcoming 5th generation wireless broadband standards depend heavily on MIMO technology. This technology used multiple antennas at both transmit and receive ends to increase data rates, channel capacity and link reliability with the limited power levels and bandwidth. To exploit the benefits of MIMO antenna systems, the multiple antennas at the transmitter and receiver have been designed for low coupling, even when closely spaced [151, 152] to maintain MIMO channel characteristics. In the literature, various MIMO antenna systems are designed and discussed for different wireless applications. During the last decade, different aspects of MIMO antenna system such as pattern diversity, polarization diversity, bidirectional pattern diversity, dual-band, wideband and dual-polarized have been investigated. A large number of researches were focused on the analysis and design of microstrip based MIMO antenna system. But at high-frequency antenna efficiency deteriorate significantly due to conductor losses. In order to overcome this difficulty dielectric resonator is used as an antenna. Dielectric resonator antennas (DRA) have several attractive characteristics such as no surface wave losses, low radiation losses, compact size, nearly constant gain, high impedance bandwidth and ease of excitation. DRA can also offer various design degrees of freedom due to different shapes, and ease of feeding mechanism makes a good choice in wireless communication system [2-3]. Ishimiya et. al. [65-66] presented concept of MIMO DRA initially. DRA has also been operating in multimode and radiate power effectively in one direction. Also, Circular polarization can be realized in DRA by using orthogonal mode. Exciting multimode or orthogonal modes in the DRA can be utilized to create multiple decoupled antenna ports, which can be considered as a basic building block of the MIMO system [153, 154]. Still, DRAs have not received much attention in MIMO system, especially for wireless communication system. However, MIMO antenna system using dielectric resonator has one of the most important evolving research areas.

2.4.1 Wideband and ultra-wideband DRA Based MIMO Antenna

Wideband and ultra-wideband antennas are the promising wireless technologies used to achieve high data rates. In this section, investigation of MIMO antenna System designed by using DRA. Das et al [155] have designed a wideband MIMO antenna using multipoint feeding of ring DRA, as shown in the Fig. 2.14. This antenna configuration design and fabricate on FR4 substrate; on the top layer of the substrate consist of two ring dielectric resonators (RDR) excited with a 50Ω microstrip lines. The RDR resonates at two different frequencies having $HE_{11\delta}$ and $TE_{01\delta}$ modes. Similarly, in the bottom layer of the substrate consist of a metallic ground plane with two stepped slots excited by 50Ω microstrip lines, this configuration also resonates at two different frequencies.

Fig. 2.14 Fabricated structure of the ring base MIMO antenna [155]

This MIMO antenna configuration achieved a wideband frequency response due to the combined effect of dual-band characteristics shown by individual radiator configuration. Impedance bandwidth of this wideband MIMO Antenna is 85.21% (3.3-8.2 GHz). Similarly, isolation between the radiators is ≥ 20 dB in the operating frequency band due to generation of opposite direction current in the ground plane. The average gain and radiation efficiency of the wideband MIMO antenna is 3dB and 88% respectively. Various diversity performance of the wideband MIMO antenna system such as diversity gain (DG), envelope correlation coefficient (ECC), total active reflection coefficient (TARC) and mean effective gain (MEG), are found to be in acceptable limit.

Sharma et al [156], described a wideband MIMO dielectric resonator antenna using two resonators arranged orthogonally which offers polarization diversity as shown in the Fig. 2.15. Each resonator is a mushroom-shaped dielectric resonator excited by a conformal trapezoidal patch antenna. To realize wideband MIMO antenna, first, a mushroom-shaped DR is build using RT/Duriod of relative permittivity 10.2, which is placed on the low permittivity substrate with relative permittivity 2.2. Copper tape can be used to build trapezoidal patch feed. Each mushroom-shaped DR can resonate at three different frequencies 5.37, 6.95, and 9.58 GHz respectively. This resonator is now used to realize wideband MIMO DRA. The simulated and measured bandwidth is 63%. Similarly, isolation between the two orthogonal radiators is better than 20 dB and radiator exhibits broadside radiation pattern with cross-polarization below 15 dB. MIMO diversity performance such as ECC and Capacity loss are under acceptable limit. This MIMO antenna system can be used in WLAN and upper ultra-wideband frequency application.

Fig. 2.15 Response of the mushroom-shaped MIMO antenna [156]

Abedian et. al. [157] proposed a new approach to the design of an ultra-wideband (UWB) MIMO dielectric resonator antenna with WLAN band rejection between 4.98 and 6.08 GHz, as shown in Fig. 2.16. In this design author's simultaneously achieved bandwidth enhancement and mutual coupling between resonators by connecting a stub in top edge of the partial ground plane. Similarly, two L- shape strip utilised to achieve WLAN band rejection. In this, MIMO DRA antenna consists of two rectangular dielectric resonators (ECCOSTOCK[®] HiK) excited by symmetrical microstrip feed. These rectangular dielectric

resonators are supported by Taconic substrate. On the bottom of the substrate a partial ground with a stub connected at the centre, which is used to achieve wideband along with good mutual coupling among the resonator.

Fig. 2.16 Geometry of the proposed DRA [157]

To create a band-notched at WLAN band (4.98-6.08 GHz) with high isolation, an L-shaped parasitic strips connected to the dielectric resonator. Actually, L-shaped parasitic strip disturbed the field distribution due to generation of two horizontally polarised modes resembling $TE_{\delta 01}^x$ and $TE_{\delta 11}$ associated with 4.65 GHz and 7.3 GHz respectively. Similarly, Introduction of stub at the ground plane does not disturb TE_{112}^x associated with the 10.3 GHz and improves isolation between the resonators. This UWB MIMO DRA can provide an impedance bandwidth ranging from 3.29 to 10.74 GHz with band rejection from 4.98 to 6.08 GHz. Isolation between the ports is well below 15 dB across the preferred frequency band. From the radiation pattern plot at three different frequencies, namely 3.5, 7.5 and 10 GHz, it is observed that an omnidirectional pattern in xy-plane is slightly distorted by the presence of second DRA, similarly a dipole like pattern at xz-plane with axis tilted from z-axis due to presence of substrate and inherent asymmetry of the DRA. The cross-polarization level in both the plane is slightly high in comparison with the normal value which is acceptable in multi-path environment.

2.4.2 Dual-band DRA Based MIMO Antenna

In this section, dielectric resonator based multiband antennas are discussed. Das et al. presents dual-band MIMO antenna utilizing combination of modified annular ring and cylindrical dielectric resonator antenna (CDRA), as shown in Fig. 2.17. The first band at 2.1 GHz can originate due to the excitation of TM_{11} mode inside the modified annular ring. Mathematical prediction of the TM_{11} mode is also given in the paper [158]. Second band which consist of two resonant peaks at 3.8 GHz and 5.2 GHz, is due to excitation of $HEM_{11\delta}$ and $TE_{01\delta}$ modes in the CDRA, respectively.

Fig. 2.17. Fabricated Photograph of MIMO Antenna [158]

In this case, modified annular ring also acts as a magnetic dipole and is accountable for the excitation of $HEM_{11\delta}$ and $TE_{01\delta}$ modes in the CDRA. So, this antenna is a hybrid combination of modified annular ring and CRDA. Isolation between the antennas can be improved by inserting a slit at the corner of the ground plane. In the second band isolation is better between the ports due to excitation of orthogonal modes in the CDR. Position of both the antennas is in such a way that they radiate in opposite direction. Also,

maximum radiation intensity of the one antenna coincides with the minimum radiation intensity of the other antenna, which further improves isolation in the second band. The measured impedance bandwidth of the antenna is around 40%. Similarly, isolation between the port in first band and second band is 20dB and 25 dB respectively. Polarization diversity is also achieved in this hybrid combination of the resonator. Different MIMO performance parameter are also calculated and found in the acceptable limit.

Khan et al. presents, a study about the design of dual band MIMO based DRA antenna for WiMAX and WLAN application [159]. This antenna has maintained a compact design due to stacking and defected ground structure (DGS) techniques for isolation between the ports. Structure of the antenna, consisted of segmented DRA with upper layer, has high permittivity and different height in comparison to lower layer. Resonant frequency of the segmented structure is calculated by weighted average model of the dominant mode. Overall design is arranged in L-shape structure consisting of a Via in upper layer and two metallic strips at the corner of the structure, as shown in the Fig. 2.18.

Fig. 2.18 Geometry of the MIMO antenna [159]

This segmented DRA consist of two port, one port excites $TE_{\delta 11}^x$ and $TE_{d 21}^x$ modes at 5.2 GHz, whereas other port excites $TE_{1 \delta 1}^y$ and $TE_{2 \delta 1}^y$ modes at 3.6 GHz, where $0 \leq \delta \leq 1$. The via along with metallic strips improve matching and broadens the bandwidth at each band. Good isolation between the ports in each band can be achieved by applying DGS at the ground. S-parameter of the segmented DRA. Radiation pattern at 3.6 GHz and 5.2 GHz

are same and cross polarization level can be below the co-polarization level. Due to presence of higher order mode and dielectric resonator with different permittivity, radiation pattern have been squinted off in the broadside direction. In [160-162] dual band MIMO DRA based antennas are presented for different wireless applications.

Fig. 2.19 Dimensions of the antenna [163]

Similarly, in [163] a compact MIMO DRA for automotive communication using LTE band operated around 790 MHz–860 MHz, 1700 MHz–2200 MHz, and 2500 MHz–2700MHz frequency bands. The DRA has been installed in a limited space on the vehicle rooftop, considering rooftop as an infinite ground plane. First resonant, modes in the DRA is TE_{101} , inserting parasitic strip at the side wall excites hybrid modes at 1.8 GHz and 2.42 GHz. Exciting hybrid modes in the DRA provides wide impedance bandwidth. Geometry of DRA is shown in the Fig. 2.19. Simulated and measured S parameters results are in a good agreement, and they exhibit broadband and multiband DRA since it covers 790 MHz–860 MHz, 1575 MHz–2200 MHz, and 2500 MHz–2700 MHz frequency bands. A radome is integrated with the DRA. Further, the antenna performances are more disturbed on the lowest band since the radome is closer in terms of λ_0 at lower frequencies. The working frequency of the first band is little bit shifted to the lower frequencies, i.e., there is a 20MHz frequency shift around 800 MHz is observed. The proposed DRA antenna also works as a pattern diversity, which depends on the excitation of the DRA. Diversity performance of the DRA

can be well within the limit. Therefore, the proposed DRA structure has been validated in measurement with performances fitting with the LTE wireless module specifications.

In [164] a dual frequency MIMO antenna has been designed using cylindrical dielectric resonator antenna, as shown in the Fig. 2.20. It consists of 4x4 MIMO configurations, in which one group operates at 2.4 GHz and others at 5.8 GHz WLAN bands with 100 MHz bandwidth in each band. Isolation in both the bands are more than -17 dB. Slot coupling mechanism was used for the excitation of $HEM_{11+\delta}$ and $TE_{01+\delta}$ modes, respectively in the both operating band. A metallic reflector is used at the centre of the antenna element to reduce mutual coupling between the antennas.

Fig. 2.20. Dual Frequency MIMO Configuration (a) Top view, (b) Side view. Dashed lines are on the bottom layer, and slots are on the top ground plane layer [164]

A minimum measured BW of 90 MHz is obtained in the lower band and 200 MHz in the higher band with an isolation of at least 16 dB. This means that there is no need to use complex and costly isolation enhancement structures. Results are in agreement and it should be mentioned that all these measurements and simulations were completed without the placement of the centre reflector. The ECC was evaluated using the simulated 3D field

patterns at the centre frequencies of the two bands as well as the two frequency points where $S_{11} = -10$ dB. The ECC values obtained in both bands did not exceed 0.17 signifying good MIMO operation and advising diversity behaviour for the proposed MIMO antenna system.

2.4.3 Circularly Polarized DRA based MIMO antenna

A dual-port dielectric resonator (DR) based circularly polarized multi-input multi-output (MIMO) antenna is reported for wireless local area network (WLAN) applications [165]. In this antenna, a corner truncated V-shaped DR is used to obtain circular polarization (CP) radiation as shown in Fig. 2.21. Along with this, two symmetric orthogonal feed networks are deployed to lessen mutual coupling between the ports.

Fig. 2.21 MIMO DRA [165]

Fig. 2.22 S-parameters and Axial ratio graphs of Antenna [165]

Simulation outcomes demonstrate that the reported MIMO antenna has a 10-dB impedance bandwidth of 10.28% (4.89-5.42 GHz) and a 3-dB axial ratio (AR) bandwidth of 4.17% (5.16-5.38 GHz) which is shown in Fig. 2.22. Also, diversity performance of proposed MIMO antenna is evaluated by using envelope correlation coefficient (ECC) and diversity gain (DG).

Fig. 2.23 Geometry of antenna [176]

Two self-complementary L-shaped DR are presented as MIMO antenna for WiMAX applications in [176] as shown in Fig. 2.23. In this antenna structure, isolation between two DRs has been achieved by DGS technique. DRs has been excited using probe method. This MIMO structure demonstrates IBW from 5.2-6.08 GHz and ARBW from 5.2-5.58 GHz as shown in Fig. 2.24. Two C-shaped slits are introduced in the ground to make it a DGS structure which improves isolation between two ports. Probe feed method is used to excite L-shaped DRA. Because circular polarization in DRA based MIMO antenna is emerging field, recent studies in this field is also very few. But advantages of CP MIMO DRA certainly encourage the future research in this direction.

Fig. 2.24 S-parameters and Axial Ratio of antenna [176]

To evaluate diversity performance in circularly polarized DRA based MIMO antennas ECC is preferably calculated using radiation pattern technique. TARC and MEG are also considered as good performance evaluation parameters to comment on diversity performance of DRA based MIMO antenna. To discuss in depth circular polarization performance, these antennas are also measured for Co-polarization and cross-polarization in maximum radiation direction. In next section MIMO performance parameters and their physical significance are discussed in detail to understand their contribution in diversity performance evaluation. Table 2.4 summarizes recently presented MIMO DRAs by comparing their performance parameters.

Table 2.4 Comparison of recent MIMO DRAs

S.No.	Impedance Bandwidth (GHz)	ARBW (GHz)	Gain (dBi)	No. of DRA	Excitation	Isolation between ports (dB)	No. of Ports	Ref
1	653 MHz and 520 MHz, Bandwidth 13.5 MHz and 35 MHz	--	3.96 and 3.19	1	aperture coupled and probe	30	2	153
2	615 MHz to 836 MHz	--	3.86	2	slot feed	15	2	154
3	3.4–8.2 GHz	--	3	2	microstrip line	20	2	155
4	5.08–9.50 GHz	--	7.4	1	microstrip	20	1	156
5	3.29 to 10.74 GHz.	--	--	2	microstrip feed	-15	2	157
6	1.75–2.4 and 3.5–5.5 GHz	--	3	2	microstrip line	20	2	158
7	(3.4–3.7) GHz and (5.15–5.35) GHz	--	5.7 and 6.61	1	probe	13, 16	2	159
8	(1.43–1.50) GHz (2.50–2.69) GHz	--	3 and 6.48	1	microstrip feed and probe	23 dB	2	160
9	(1.41–1.49 GHz) and (2.2–2.85 GHz)	--	4.83 and 4.92	1	probe	-6	2	161

Table 2.4 (Continued)

10	3.42–3.80 , 4.97–5.50	--	5.2 , 6.38	1	aperture coupled	20	2	162
11	1.710–2.170 GHz and 2.490– 2.690 GHz	--	4	1	Probe	--	1	163
12	2.4 GHz (90 MHz)and 5.8GHz (200MHz)	--	6.5, 8.9	8	microstrip line feed	15,18	8	164
13	10.28% (4.89- 5.42 GHz)	4.17% (5.16- 5.38 GHz).	5.04	1	aperture coupled	12	2	165
14	port1-880MHz, port2-870 MHz port3-2.61 GHz at center freq 9.48 GHz 880 MHz (9.12– 10 GHz), 870 MHz (8.97–9.84 GHz), and 2.61 GHz (8.9–11.5 GHz)	--	8.1dB, 7.5 dB, 7.4 dB	1	aperture coupled and probe	-20	3	166
15	5.25–5.92	--	5	2	Probe and microstrip line	20	3	167
16	5.4–6.0	--	5	2	microstrip line	18	4	168
17	4.07, 2.7%	--	--	1	probe	14.4	2	169
18	1.69– 1.96GHz)	--	--	1	microstrip	18	2	170
19	2.56–2.64 GHz	--	--	1	microstrip feed	20	2	171
20	6.5% at 2.45 GHz and 3% at 5.2 GHz	--	--	1	probe	10	2	172
21	25% (2.40–3.09 GHz)	--	4.51	1	CPW and probe	20	2	173

Table 2.4 (Continued)

22	2.30–3.14 GHz	--	1.85	1	CPW	33	2	174
23	2.21–3.13, 3.40–3.92, and 5.30–6.10 GHz 34.45%, 14.2%, and 14%	--	1.5, 4.1 2.3	2	microstrip line	20	2	175
24	15.6% (5.2–6.08 GHz)	7.05% (5.2–5.58 GHz)	4	2	probe	19	2	176
25	11.81% (5.18–5.83 GHz)	--	5.94	1	microstrip	30	2	177
26	59.7% (3.24–6.0 GHz)	--	6.03–7.45	2	microstrip	20	2	178
27	3.27 GHz (IBW 5.52%) and 5.40 GHz (IBW 2.97%)	--	4.88 and 5.32	4	Aperture coupled	20	4	179
28	1.5–2.55, 3.21–4.0 and 4.59–5.98 GHz with the fractional bandwidth 51.21, 21.91 and 26.30%	--	2.19, 3.5 and 5.0	2	microstrip line feed	25	2	180
29	3.78–4.07 GHz	--	5.1	1	Multiple feed line	16	2	181
30	5.1–6.25 GHz (15%)	--	4.7	2	Slot coupled	25	2	182
31	38.51% (3.50–4.95 GHz)	20.82% (3.58–4.40 GHz)	6.28	2	Probe	28	2	183

Table 2.4 (Continued)

32	2.45 GHz/5.8 GHz with 100 MHz bandwidth	--	9	8	Microstrip Line Feed	15	8	184
33	At 30 GHz with Bandwidth of 2GHz	--	9	8	Microstrip Line Feed	-	2	185
34	At 29.4 GHz with Bandwidth of 6.7%	--	-	16	Microstrip Line Feed	15	4	186
35	7 dB impedance bandwidth from 1.0 GHz to 1.62 GHz	--	-	1	Slot coupled	-	8	187
36	3.15-3.93 GHz	3.3-4.0 GHz	4.83	2	Cross Aperture coupled	26	2	188
37	5.6-5.9 GHz	-	4.8	4	CPW strip line and aperture coupling	20	8	189
38	0.9, 1.8, 2.3 GHz with 4.4%, 11.36%, 2.54% resp.	-	4.1, 4.2, 1.4	2	Microstrip line feed with meander line	15, 17, 47	2	190

2.5 MIMO Performance Parameters

To study and evaluate the MIMO or diversity performance of the proposed antenna, four key parameters have been analyzed which are envelope correlation coefficient (ECC), total active reflection coefficient (TARC), diversity gain (DG) and mean effective gain (MEG). ECC is main performance metric of MIMO system which describes isolation

and correlation of communication channel with each other [191,192]. ECC can be calculated using radiation pattern of the antenna mentioned in Eq. (2.24).

$$ECC = \frac{|\iint_{4\pi} [\vec{F}_1(\theta, \varphi) * \vec{F}_2(\theta, \varphi)] d\Omega|^2}{\iint_{4\pi} |\vec{F}_1(\theta, \varphi)|^2 d\Omega \iint_{4\pi} |\vec{F}_2(\theta, \varphi)|^2 d\Omega} \quad (2.24)$$

Where $\vec{F}_i(\theta, \varphi)$ is the three-dimensional field radiation pattern of the antenna when i^{th} port is excited and Ω is the solid angle. This mathematical relation needs three-dimensional radiation pattern measurement and integration and it is applicable when isotropic environment conditions are considered for testing and measurement. ECC can also be calculated using S-parameters. This method is easy but gives approximate values in comparison to ECC calculated using Eq. (2.25).

$$ECC = \frac{|S_{ii}^* S_{ij} + S_{ji}^* S_{jj}|^2}{(1 - |S_{ii}|^2 - |S_{ji}|^2)(1 - |S_{jj}|^2 - |S_{ij}|^2) \eta_{radi} \eta_{radj}} \quad (2.25)$$

where S_{ij} is the S-parameter between i^{th} and j^{th} coupling and η_{radi} , η_{radj} are radiation efficiencies of elements i and j , respectively.

$$Isolation = -10 \log_{10}(|S_{ij}|) \quad (2.26)$$

Low coupling between input ports yields high isolation which can be calculated using S-parameters as mentioned in Eq. (2.26). It is required for a good diversity performance of a MIMO antenna to demonstrate high isolation and low ECC. Second most important parameter to characterize efficiency and bandwidth of MIMO radiator is TARC. It is defined as the ratio of the square root of the total reflected power divided by the square root of the total incident power [191,192] as mentioned in Eq. (2.27).

$$TARC = \sqrt{\frac{\text{Total reflected power}}{\text{Total incident power}}} \quad (2.27)$$

TARC always vary between 0 and 1 where a 0 means no reflected power or all power is radiated and 1 means no power radiated. For a two port MIMO antenna system TARC mentioned by Sharawi [191] is given in Eq. (2.28).

$$TARC = \sqrt{\frac{(|S_{11} + S_{12} e^{j\theta}|)^2 + (|S_{21} + S_{22} e^{j\theta}|)^2}{2}} \quad (2.28)$$

Where θ is input feeding phase, S_{aa} is reflection coefficient of port a and S_{ab} is the coupling between the two ports a and b .

Directive gain identifies the amount of improvement that can be seen in MIMO in comparison to SISO (single input single output) system [192] [170]. Directive gain is a very important parameter to assess performance of MIMO antenna system. It is measure of diversity performance which is generally achieved when transmitter receiver different signals sent through different channels by multiple antennas, if all the signals are uncorrelated then high signal to noise ratio achieved at receiver. It is defined as the difference between the time averaged signal to noise ratio (SNR) of all the combined signals received from multiple antennas in MIMO system and time averaged SNR of a single antenna system. DG is defined by Eq. (2.29) mentioned in [192].

$$DG = \left[\frac{\gamma_c}{SNR_c} - \frac{\gamma_1}{SNR_1} \right] P(\gamma_c < \frac{\gamma_s}{SNR}) \quad (2.29)$$

In Eq. (2.24) SNR_c and γ_c are the mean SNR and instantaneous SNR for MIMO diversity antenna system and SNR_1 and γ_1 are the mean SNR and instantaneous SNR for single branch having maximum values in the diversity system. Rayleigh probability distribution is assumed for uncorrelated signals. DG and correlation coefficient are related to each other such that for lower values of correlation coefficient, higher diversity gain has been observed. In [192-195] DG is approximated using ECC mentioned in Eq. (2.30)

$$DG = 10\sqrt{(1 - ECC^2)} \quad (2.30)$$

MEG measures amount of the power received by the MIMO antenna in comparison to a standard antenna in the standard environment. For a good diversity performance of MIMO antenna, difference between MEG1 and MEG2 should be less than 3 dB [192-195] as mentioned in Eq. (2.34). MEG can be calculated using Eq. (2.31) [192-195]. Here N is the number of MIMO elements or ports.

$$MEG_i = 0.5 \left[1 - \sum_{j=1}^N |S_{ij}|^2 \right] \quad (2.31)$$

$$MEG_1 = 0.5[|S_{11}|^2 - |S_{12}|^2] \quad (2.32)$$

$$MEG_2 = 0.5[|S_{21}|^2 - |S_{22}|^2] \quad (2.33)$$

$$|MEG_1 - MEG_2| < 3 \text{ dB} \quad (2.34)$$

2.6 Summary

In this chapter, literature of DRA has been reviewed. Chapter started with introduction to DRA and its types. In general, DRAs have been categorized in conventional and non-conventional DRA. RDRA and CDRA have been compared in Table 2.1 and Table 2.3. Further in this chapter a review of MIMO DRA has been studied and compared the recent MIMO DRAs in Table 2.4. A detailed overview of different MIMO performance parameters has been presented also.

CHAPTER 3

CIRCULARLY POLARIZED DIELECTRIC RESONATOR ANTENNA

3.1 Introduction

In present time, simplicity, ease of design and cost of antenna are paramount factors which should be backed by admirable performance, so that production cost of antenna is less and quality of reception is commendable. Antenna as a sensor have advantage of passive operation, low profile, small size, multiplexing capability compatibility with dielectric substrate etc. Antenna has flexibility of dual function of communication and sensing. So, an antenna for sensing application requires minimum number of components. These features discussed above make antenna sensor as a vital tool in sensing application. A scheme of antenna integration with electronics circuits such as processing, conditioning and biasing circuits are shown in [196, 197]. Different types of antenna as a sensing element is demonstrated in [198,199]. They are used for the measurement of the various physical parameters. This chapter basically covers operational features and introduction of battery less antenna sensor. Microwaves are now also used for a near field microwave image sensing in breast cancer detection [200]. The advent of more compact antennas are increasing its application in microwave sensors, astronomy, remote sensing, medical imaging and wide array of scientific and medical application. At mm wave band many researchers proposed antenna for image sensing application by using different design methodology. In [201] C

Jang-Soon Park et al., proposed tilted beam antenna at 28 GHz with beam scanning capability using waveguide WR28 for feeding antenna. In [202] Philip Ayiku Dzagbletey et al., proposed stacked 1x7 microstrip linear antenna array at 28GHz for 5G using Taconic TLY-5 substrate with 14.7dBi gain at resonant frequency. In [203] Gerhard F. Hamberger et al., proposed Beamforming antenna array (1x10) having 15 dBi gain and 1GHz impedance bandwidth using RO4350B substrate material. In [204] Chun-Xu Mao et al., reported 4x4 array for 5G communication using double substrate material which are RO 4003C and RO 5880. In [205] Osama Haraz et al., proposed patch antenna using EBG Ground Structure and Dielectric Superstrate at 28GHz using RT5880 substrate material. Researchers are motivated to find sensor applications in mm wave band so that in future 5G communications can be well equipped with microwave sensors. Wearable sensor is another challenge because it requires compact size and light weight sensors. Dielectric Resonator are widely used in present times due to their advantages of low metallic losses, wide bandwidth, low dielectric losses, high gain and easy to achieve circular polarisation (CP) at higher modes. Circular polarisation antennas are always preferred over their linear polarized counterparts because of less multipath fading, ease of receiving of signals and less polarisation losses. In, [124] M. Chauhan et al., proposed cylindrical DRA for wireless sensor applications using Rogers RO3210 which gives 3.6 dB gain at resonant frequency 6.7 GHz and peak gain of 6.8dB in operating band. Dash et al [139], proposed a triangular dielectric resonator antenna by using spiral fed for remote sensing application with gain 2.15 dBi and 3.69 dBi.

Rectangular DRA is easy to fabricate in comparison to cylindrical DRA which is widely discussed in literature because of different mathematical interpretation given by researchers [2,3]. Major theoretical study on DRA is on dielectric resonator having permittivity $\epsilon_r > 10$ because of various advantages of high permittivity resonator, such as good coupling, large storage of energy etc. In [101] Yong-Mei Pan et al, compared performances of low permittivity DRA ($\epsilon_r = 5$) with high permittivity DRA ($\epsilon_r = 10$) and authors concluded that a lower permittivity DRA is recommendable for increasing the bandwidth of the DRA but size of DRA is also increased then and mode excitation in low permittivity DRA is also tough.

In this chapter, a dielectric resonator antenna, which is simple and highly compact, is discussed with its applications. Major advantages of discussed antenna are wide bandwidth, high gain all across mm wave band. Major applications of the discussed radiator can be considered in microwave image sensing applications in mm wave band. This DR is excited using microstrip line feed network. This feed network consists of circular loop type network which maintain phase difference of 90^0 to produce circular polarization. The gain of antenna is approximately 8.6 dBi on 25-26 GHz band and 3 dB axial ratio bandwidth is almost 1 GHz from 25.2-26.2 GHz. 10 dB impedance bandwidth is 24-27 GHz. There are various applications of discussed antenna such as in microwave image sensing and wearable sensors applications, due to its compact size ($30 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$), in mm wave band.

3.2 Antenna Design

The DRA structure consists of a conventional FR-4 substrate as a DR and a circular loop with four feeds. The circular ring microstrip line with four feeds is used to excite TE_{118} mode in the DR. Major achievements of this antenna are simple design (no slot or probe feed is used), small size and low cost.

Fig. 3.1. Fabricated prototype

Table 3.1 Design parameters (in mm)

w	R1	R2	h	wsub	Lf	s	L1
1.93	12.29	10.35	0.8	30	2.8	1.645	10.5

The proposed DRA is working in 24-27 GHz frequency band exhibit flat gain around 8.6 dBi and 3 dB AR bandwidth of approximately 1 GHz. Fig. 3.1 shows simulated and fabricated DRA. Antenna Design was simulated using HFSS software and mathematical equations are computed using MATLAB software. Fig. 3.1 displays the fabricated prototype of proposed antenna. Fig. 3.2 demonstrates, the dimensional details and complete layout of the proposed DRA. Table 3.1 shows design parameters in mm. The proposed DRA consist of a circular loop with four feeds printed on a FR-4 substrate having $\epsilon_r=4.4$, $h=0.8$ mm, $\tan\delta=0.02$. An FR-4 substrate having dimension $5.85 \text{ mm} \times 5.85 \text{ mm}$ is utilized as a DR ($\epsilon_r=4.4$, $h_{dra}=4.8$ mm, $\tan\delta=0.02$) is placed on the DR such that it can cover four feed lines symmetrically. Width of circular ring microstrip line is calculated by using design equations given in [206].

3.2.1 Design of the DRA

Mongia and Ittipiboon [30] studied DRA for dielectric constant ranging from 10-100. However, Eq. (2.14-2.17) has been used to calculate the dimensions of DRA.

(a) Feed Layout

(b) Complete Layout with DRA

Fig. 3.2. Layout of proposed design

By using MATLAB we obtain two values of the square DRA, which can satisfy Eq. (2.14-2.17), which are $5.62 \text{ mm} \times 5.62 \text{ mm} \times 1.6$ and $4.34 \text{ mm} \times 4.34 \text{ mm} \times 4.8 \text{ mm}$ respectively at frequency of interest. When designing a DRA by using these dimensions it did not resonated at the desired frequency. It was because of low dielectric constant DR material. So, the parametric analysis is performed to find out new dimension of the DRA which operated at desired frequency. After optimization, new dimension of the DRA is $5.85 \text{ mm} \times 5.85 \text{ mm} \times 4.8 \text{ mm}$ operation at 25.5 GHz which is chosen as middle value of targeted band 24-27 GHz.

3.3 Operating Principle of the DRA

For the analysis of the proposed DRA, design and development of the DRA are divided in to two parts, part one describes describe feed network and part two explain working of the DRA.

Single line feed. Low Bandwidth, less gain and No CP	Four feeds are used But isolation between feeds was poor.	Single line feed with four inputs to DRA maintaining quadrature phase producing CP, large gain and wide bandwidth

Fig. 3.3 Design steps of Antenna

Part 1: Figure 3.2 shows the proposed configuration of the feed networks. Design steps are shown in Fig. 3.3. First step is shifted microstrip feed to excite DRA but it was unable to excite modes in DRA. In second step, four strips are used to excite modes in DRA which works good but isolation of all four feeds was very poor. In third step, a circular feed loop is added so that single feed can achieve the results. All the four strips are at equal distance on the circumference of the circular loop so that a 90^0 phase difference should be maintained between any two strips. So, when a signal applied to the feed, all four feeds experience current quadrature phase difference with each other.

Part 2: A rectangular DRA placed centrally over the feed network. The DRA is coupled with four strip which have provided excitation of the rectangular DRA, which led the rectangular DRA to resonate at 25.6 GHz. interestingly, this circular loop setup provides excitation to the rectangular DRA with 90^0 phase difference hence provide circular polarization.

The excitation of different mode in rectangular DRA depends upon feed mechanism. Here, the rectangular DRA is excited by using four strips. Rectangular DRA produce pure modes when excited in isolated condition but grounded DRA with four sequential feeds with single main feed, excites DRA asymmetrically, which gave $TE_{11\delta}$ mode which is confirmed by magnetic field distribution, as shown in Fig. 3.4 (a, b), as explained in [207]. It is also confirmed from Fig. 3.4(c), which were defined by [30] for $TE_{11\delta}$. It was

worth mentioning that radius of circular loop also participate in performance of DRA. We optimized the circular loop radius for best impedance matching, wide axial ratio (AR) bandwidth and commendable gain throughout band.

Fig. 3.4 Magnetic Field distribution on DRA on y-z plane at 25.6 GHz (a) Magnitude (b) Vector (c) Theoretical

3.4 Parametric Analysis

Various dimensions have been analyzed to get broad impedance bandwidth with good stable gain. To understand behavior of design parameters, a parametric analysis is studied. It was studied while doing analysis that radius of circular loop (R1) and height of DRA (hdra) affects the results of proposed antenna in terms of gain and bandwidth.

3.4.1 Effect of Radius of Loop

First parametric analysis was implemented for studying effect of radius of loop. Parameters observed are reflection coefficient, gain and axial ratio which are shown in Fig. 3.5-3.7. It was observed that reflection coefficient is achieved less than -10 dB for all variation of loop radius and gain also varies with respect to loop radius. Gain is maximum for loop radius of 12.29 mm. Table 3.2 summarizes all the finding of parametric analysis for effect of loop radius. It is clearly visible from Table 3.2 that AR bandwidth is achieved only for the case of radius 12.29 mm and also flat gain around 8.6 dB is achieved for this optimized radius of loop.

Table 3.2 Summary of Parametric effects of loop radius

Radius of Loop (mm)	Impedance Bandwidth (GHz)	Resonant Frequency (GHz)	Reflection Coefficient (dB)	Peak Gain (dB)	AR Bandwidth (GHz)
11	24-27	25	-16	6.2	-
12	24-27	25	-25	8.2 (Flat Gain)	-
12.29	24-27	24.9	-28	8.6 (Flat Gain)	25.2-26.2
13	24-26	25	-42	6.8	-

Fig. 3.5 Reflection coefficient (dB) vs. frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of loop radius with fixed height of DRA of 4.8 mm

Fig. 3.6 Gain (dB) vs. frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of loop radius with fixed height of DRA of 4.8 mm

Fig. 3.7 Axial Ratio (dB) vs. frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of loop radius with fixed height of DRA of 4.8 mm

3.4.2 Effect of height of DRA

Second parametric analysis is studied for height of DRA which is taken multiple of 1.6 mm as it is easily available commercially. Variation of standard parameters like reflection coefficient, gain and axial ratio with respect to change in height of DRA is shown in Fig. 3.8 - 3.10. It was analyzed from Fig. 3.8 - 3.10, that reflection coefficient achieved at 24.9 GHz frequency is -28 dB for height of DRA 4.8 mm and as we increase or decrease height reflection coefficient at resonant frequency increases. Major observation is that gain becomes stable for 4.8mm height for 24.5-26.5 GHz band. Next performance parameter which confirms our proposed height is axial ratio bandwidth. Axial ratio bandwidth of approximately 1 GHz is achieved centered around resonant frequency 25.6 GHz for 4.8 mm height. Table 3.3 summarizes all the findings of parametric study of effect of height of DRA. It can be concluded from both parametric analysis that our choice of taking height of DRA and radius of loop is justified to achieve circular polarization, wide impedance bandwidth and high stable gain all over the band of interest.

Fig. 3.8 Reflection coefficient (dB) vs. frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of height of DRA with loop radius of 12.29 mm

Fig. 3.9 Gain (dB) vs. frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of height of DRA with fixed loop radius of 12.29 mm

Fig. 3.10 Axial Ratio (dB) vs. frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of height of DRA with fixed loop radius of 12.29 mm

Table 3.3 Summary of parametric effects of height of DRA

Height of DRA (mm)	Impedance Bandwidth (GHz)	Resonant Frequency (GHz)	Reflection Coefficient (dB)	Peak Gain (dB)
1.6	24-27	26.3	-12	2
3.2	24-27	26.3	-18	8.55
4.8	24-27	24.9	-28	8.6 (Flat Gain)
6.4	24-27	26.2	-22	7.6

3.5 Results and Discussion

In this section, validation of proposed rectangular DRA is discussed. A prototype antenna based on the FR-4 DR is fabricated, which is shown in the Fig. 3.1. Figure 3.11 shows, the simulated and measured $|S_{11}|$ of the rectangular DRA.

Fig. 3.11 Reflection coefficient (dB) vs frequency (GHz) comparison between simulated and measured results

It can be observed that measured and simulated impedance bandwidth cover the 24-27 GHz frequency band. Similarly, 3 dB AR Bandwidth of 1 GHz (25.2 GHz to 26.2 GHz) is achieved, as shown in the Fig. 3.12. A close agreement can be observed between 3-dB axial ratio bandwidth of measured and simulated plots. The measured and simulated radiation pattern in broadside direction is plotted in the Fig. 3.13. From the radiation pattern half power beamwidth of 70° and Front to back ratio of 16.9 dB is calculated. Figure 3.14 shows co-polarisation and cross polarisation graph which shows good separation of 20 dB between co-pol and x-pol component in H-plane ($\phi=90^\circ$) at resonance frequency 25.6 GHz. Our prototype agrees with measured results with some deviation due to fabrication constraints at noncommercial level.

This DRA also supports linear polarisation in UWB from 22.5-27 GHz with peak gain of 8.6 dBi. Figure 3.15 demonstrates linear polarisation and circular polarisation bandwidth. It shows gain and reflection coefficient variation with respect to frequency.

Fig. 3.12 Axial ratio (dB) vs. Frequency (GHz) comparison between simulated and measured results

Fig. 3.13 Comparison of simulated and measured radiation pattern of antenna

Fig. 3.14 Gain (Co-polarisation) dB vs. frequency (GHz) and Gain (Cross-Polarisation) dB vs. frequency (GHz) comparison between simulated and measured results

Area covered by red rectangle with bandwidth 25.2-26.2 GHz covers circular polarisation with high gain but remaining band from 22.5-27 GHz have variable gain and may be used for broad bandwidth applications. When transmitters and receivers are static or fixed then linear polarisation is also preferred depending upon the application. In microwave sensing application often sensors may be fixed at certain position such as in satellites, mobile communication. Presently, high permittivity DR are used only, due to their multiple advantages.

In microwave image sensing, cost is an important factor to consider because a sensor is always followed by signal processing circuitry, so overall cost of the system will be increased. For the microwave image sensing application, the gain of the device should be high and stable. The proposed DRA fulfill all the basic condition of the sensor. Proposed DRA can offer wide impedance bandwidth and AR bandwidth which is also desirable feature of the sensor.

Fig. 3.15 Gain (dB), Reflection Coefficient (dB) versus frequency (GHz) plot

3.6 Summary

So, to reduce overall cost of system and improve performance, proposed prototype can be a good choice for image sensing applications at mm wave band such as

satellite communication applications, 5G communications etc. CEPT documentation available on [209] concludes that 24.5-27.5 GHz band is good candidate for 5G communication and harmonization is possible on this band all over the globe. According to [210], 28 GHz band is proposed for ESIM (Earth Stations in Motion) remote sensing and IMT (International Mobile Telecommunications) standards which are relevant to microwave remote sensing. Our proposed antenna covers this band and can be used as an image sensor in IMT standards and ESIM remote sensing applications. It is very small size comparable to wrist watch dial and DRA height 0.48 cm, so it can also be used in wearable body sensors in mm wave band. Due to its low-cost commercial scalability is also possible. In the next chapter a non-conventional shaped DRA is discussed with dual polarization.

Sumer Singh
Singhwal

CHAPTER 4

V-SHAPED DRA WITH DIRECTIONAL CP

4.1 Introduction

The advent of efficient antennas has revolutionized the field of communication. In the pursuit of efficient antennas, in 1983 Long *et al.* [11,12] proposed cylindrical and rectangular dielectric resonator antennas (DRA). In 1984 Long *et al.* [13] presented hemispherical DRA. DRA is a relatively new concept of using dielectric material as antenna instead of metallic antennas which were used previously. Now a days, DRA antennas have been popular due to its various advantages over existing metallic antennas. Major advantages of DRA are wide impedance bandwidth as radiation area is more as compared to patch, low losses due to the dielectric body of the DRA, flexible excitation schemes as a number of options of excitation increases due to three-dimension body of the DRA, more design parameters (degree of freedom) and high radiation efficiency [2-3].

Circular polarization is also a much-sought property in antennas for satellite communication and radar applications due to low polarization losses, ease in the alignment of the antenna and ability to combat multipath interference and fading. The benefits of circular polarization in mobile services and communication are explained in [67,68]. Circular polarization can be achieved by single-feed, multi-feed and different DR shapes, however the mono feed method is easier and compact. Different feed methods already discussed in the literature [2-3]. Initially, in the 1990s, basic geometrical shapes such as cylindrical and rectangular DRAs were studied at length discussed in detail in chapter-II. Directional circular polarization is one of the desired property in some of the applications like satellite communication and RADAR. Directional CP feature antenna showcase linear polarization in all around direction except some pointed direction where antenna produce circular polarized

wave also. It signifies, an antenna can be supposed to have dual polarization operation which is good feature. Most of the satellite communication applications lies in C-band and X- band. Recent research have shown interest in designing dual polarized antennas in these bands where RADAR and satellite communication applications exists.

In this chapter, V-shaped DRA is proposed for X band applications. A prototype of the proposed DRA is also fabricated to validate the results as shown in Fig. 4.1. Measured impedance bandwidth and measured axial ratio bandwidth (ARBW) of the proposed antenna are 25% (7.85-10.1 GHz) and 4% (8.35-8.7 GHz), respectively. This antenna can also be used in the MIMO antenna system and smart antenna array because of its directional circular polarization property. Proposed antenna operates in X band which has a plethora of applications as discussed in [211,212] such as Radar and satellite communication. Smart beam steering antenna array is also one of the emerging applications in X band.

Fig. 4.1 Fabricated V-Shaped DRA Prototype

4.2 Antenna Design

Here, V-shaped DRA fed with the probe is proposed, as shown in Fig. 4.1. It comprises Eccostock Hik bar having relative dielectric constant 10. Width of microstrip line is calculated by using Eq. (4.1-4.2) given in [213]. Height of substrate is taken as $h=0.8$ mm.

So, W/h ratio is always greater than one for FR4 substrate. So, equations for $\frac{W}{h} \geq 1$ is used here to calculate value of microstrip line width.

Table 4.1 Design Parameters (in mm)

L	W	F	hdra	r1	PH	D	GW
17	11	6	11.1	4.85	7.4	44	100

Fig. 4.2 Geometry of proposed DRA

$$\epsilon_{re} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left(1 + 12 \frac{h}{W}\right)^{-0.5} \quad (4.1)$$

$$Z_{0m} = \frac{\eta}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{re}}} \left\{ \frac{W}{h} + 1.393 + 0.667 \ln \left(\frac{W}{h} + 1.444 \right) \right\}^{-1} \quad (4.2)$$

Mongia and Ittipiboon in [30] studied DRA for dielectric constant from 10-100.

However, we have taken low permittivity DRA, but we find Eq. (2.14-2.17) suitable for rectangular DRA for lowest order mode $TE_{11\delta}^z$. The Eccostock bar has been moulded in V-shape, a copper plate has been used as ground, two copper patches have been embedded on the surface of the DRA and a copper probe having diameter 1 mm has been used for feeding the structure. The schematic of the DRA is shown in Fig. 4.2. Table 4.1 shows the dimensional details of the antenna. Antenna design steps are shown in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Design steps of V-shaped DRA

Steps	Design	Impedance BW	ARBW
Step-1- RDRA		7.7-10.2 GHz	-
Step-2- V-Shaped DRA		9.2-9.6 GHz	9.08-9.12 GHz
Step-3- V-Shaped DRA with a single circular patch		8.25-9.8 GHz	-
Step-4- V-Shaped DRA with two circular patches		7.8-10 GHz	8.44-8.86 GHz

In step-1, dimensions of the rectangular dielectric resonator antenna (RDRA) have been obtained using design Eq. (2.14-2.17), as mentioned by Mongia et al. [30]. Approximate parameter values obtained from design equations were further optimized using high-frequency structural simulator (HFSS). The dimension of the RDRA-1 is $6\text{ mm} \times 17\text{ mm} \times 11.1\text{ mm}$ which resonates at 9.6 GHz. In step-2, a V-shaped DRA is obtained by joining two RDRA and excited by a probe of diameter 1 mm at the center of the structure, as shown in Fig. 4.3.

Fig. 4.3 Comparison of simulated impedance bandwidth of different antennas as shown in Table 4.2

In the next step, a circular patch is etched on one surface of the V-shaped DRA which results dual resonance at 8.75 GHz and 9.65 GHz, as shown in the Fig. 4.3. Second resonance is due to circular patch etched on the surface of the DRA, having diameter $1.1\lambda_0/4$, where λ_0 corresponds to free space wavelength at resonant frequency 8.65 GHz. In the fourth step, two circular patches are etched on both sides of the DRA. These circular patches fed by probe are equivalent to monopole antenna as discussed by Dash et al. [139]. Consequently, the resonance frequency of the DRA shifts from 8.65 GHz to 8.1 GHz. Figure 4.3 shows the comparison of simulated impedance bandwidths in all the steps explained above. From the observation of the Fig. 4.3, it is concluded that impedance bandwidth in step-1 is wide enough but ARBW is null. Step-2 aims to design a DRA with wide impedance bandwidth as well as pleasing ARBW. In this step, due to even symmetry in V-shape along the joint, DRA exhibits directional circular polarization. It shows RHCP at $\varphi = 50^\circ$ direction and LHCP at $\varphi = -50^\circ$ direction. But the ARBW is still narrow, from 9.08-9.12 GHz (40 MHz), as shown in Fig. 4.4.

Fig. 4.4. Comparison of simulated AR of different antennas as shown in Table 4.2. All ARs are at $\theta=50^\circ$ and $\phi=50^\circ$

To increase ARBW, in step 3 a circular patch was etched on one side of DRA which still results in diminished circular polarization due to asymmetrical structure. In step-4, ARBW has been increased from 40 MHz to 420 MHz by embedding two circular patches on both sides of the DRA, as depicted in Fig. 4.4. Figure 4.5 shows simulated AR for different elevation angles in coarser and finer views respectively. It is noticed that the minimum AR frequency point shifts wr.t. the elevation angle. So, circular polarization is stronger at $\phi=\pm 50^\circ$ and $45^\circ < \theta < 55^\circ$. In Fig. 4.5 (a) θ is taken $45^\circ, 50^\circ, 55^\circ$ and 60° which signifies better results of ARBW around $\theta=50^\circ$. To achieve more insight in this a finer view with $\theta=50^\circ, 51^\circ, 52^\circ, 53^\circ, 54^\circ, 55^\circ$ is plotted in Fig. 4.5 (b). This view clarifies that Antenna have been observed good ARBW throughout this region and CP is achievable for wide range of angle θ . Figure 4.6 shows the comparison between gain (LHCP and RHCP) and axial ratios simulated for $\phi=\pm 50^\circ$ direction.

(a) $\theta=45^{\circ}, 50^{\circ}, 55^{\circ}, 60^{\circ}$

(b) $\theta=50^{\circ}, 51^{\circ}, 52^{\circ}, 53^{\circ}, 54^{\circ}, 55^{\circ}$

Fig. 4.5 Simulated Axial Ratio Vs frequency variation for different values of elevation angle (θ) with a constant azimuth angle ($\phi = 50^{\circ}$)

Fig. 4.6 Simulated Gain (LHCP and RHCP) and AR graphs in $\phi = \pm 50^\circ$ and $\theta = 50^\circ$ direction

Fig. 4.7 Three dimensional radiation pattern in XY Plane showing the direction of RHCP and LHCP radiation at 8.65 GHz

Due to the symmetry of proposed antenna, gain (LHCP) at $\phi=-50^\circ$ and gain (RHCP) at $\phi=50^\circ$ have approximately same values, gain (RHCP) at $\phi=-50^\circ$ and gain (LHCP) at $\phi=50^\circ$ have also approximately same values. Simulated axial ratios in $\phi=\pm 50^\circ$ directions are also nearly same. Fig. 4.7 shows 3D radiation pattern plotted in XY plane and directions of circular polarization wave radiation with respect to antenna placement.

Similarly, simulated impedance bandwidth and axial ratio bandwidth of the proposed design are 7.8-10 GHz (24%) and 8.44-8.86 GHz (5%) respectively, as shown in Fig. 4.3 and Fig. 4.4. The Proposed DRA exhibits gain from 2.5-5 dB and good AR bandwidth in the range $45^\circ < \theta < 55^\circ$ at $\phi=\pm 50^\circ$. So, the proposed antenna demonstrates directional CP which can be used in smart beam steering antenna array system. Two design parameters, height of DRA and radius of circular patch on surface of DRA, have been used for parametric analysis. In the next section, effect of these two parameters on impedance bandwidth and axial ratio bandwidth has been studied in detail.

4.3 Effect of Height of DRA

The height of any antenna plays a major role in its radiation properties. In case of DRA, bandwidth and mode degeneracy can be controlled by proper choice of resonator dimensions [2]. When the height of DRA varied it is observed that resonant frequency due to DRA also varied. To study the effect of the height of the proposed DRA, the design was simulated for four heights viz. 10 mm, 11 mm, 12 mm, 13 mm. S-parameters and axial ratio graphs are shown in Fig. 4.8 for various heights. The resonant frequencies and ARBW at various heights are tabulated in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3 Resonant frequencies at various heights of DRA

Height of DRA (in mm)	Resonant Frequency (in GHz)	ARBW (in GHz)
10	9.7	8.12-8.22, 8.52-9.1
11	8.1 and 9.7	8.4-8.82
12	8.25 and 9.5	8.45-8.65
13	8.25 and 9.3	-

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4.8 Simulated S₁₁ and AR against frequency for different heights of DRA. AR is at $\theta=50^\circ$ and $\phi=50^\circ$ (a) S₁₁ (b) AR

Alteration in surface current distribution and field distribution along the surface can be subtly observed due to the variation in the height of DRA. The orthogonal fields must have equal magnitude and must be in time phase quadrature for exciting circular polarization. Circular polarization depends on how effectively fields cross each other orthogonally. So, it is observed that when the height of DRA is 10 mm, circularly polarization is maximum but has poor impedance matching which can be improved by increasing the height of DRA to 11.1 mm. However, the circular polarization is reduced a little bit but an improved impedance matching along the band is observed. Circular polarization further diminishes at 12 mm and 13 mm heights. Henceforth, circular polarization and impedance bandwidth are achieved at the optimized height of 11.1 mm, after observing its effects on different parameters.

4.4 Effect of Radius of Circular Patch

Circular patch antennas can behave as a monopole antenna when etched on the surface of the dielectric substrate. Radiation properties of the monopole antenna change with respect to surface area and shape of the patch [139]. To study the effect of a change in surface area and size of the circular patch on radiation properties of DRA, the proposed antenna was simulated for different radii of the patch. Figure 4.9 shows the variation of S_{11} and axial ratio against frequency for different radii of the patch. For radii less than 4 mm it has been found that excitation probe does not directly feed the circular patch, instead the energy has been coupled electromagnetically with the circular patch. Due to this, poor impedance bandwidth has been observed for radii less than 4 mm, as shown in the Fig. 4.9 (a). The resonant frequencies and ARBW at various radii are also tabulated in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4 Resonant frequencies at various radii of Patch

Radius of Patch (in mm)	Resonant Frequency (in GHz)	ARBW (in GHz)
3	7.7	8.5-8.95
3.5	7.5	7.95-8.75
4	8.3	7.65-8.3
4.5	8.2 and 9.9	7.75-7.95
4.85	8.1 and 9.6	8.44-8.86
5	8 and 9.3	8.55-8.95

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4.9 Simulated S11 and AR against frequency for different radius of patches etched on surfaces of DRA. AR is at $\theta=50^\circ$ and $\phi=50^\circ$ (a) S11 (b) AR

The resonance at 8.1 GHz is due to patch whose diameter corresponds to $\lambda_0/4$, where λ_0 is free space wavelength corresponding to resonant frequency. Table 4.4 shows increase in patch radius improves impedance bandwidth. Henceforth, circular polarization and impedance bandwidth are achieved at the optimized radius of 4.85 mm, after observing its effects on different parameters.

4.5 Characterization and Result Validation

This section contains characterization of antenna parameters and validation of these characteristics with their practically measured counterparts. The performance characteristics of the proposed DRA have been analyzed, investigated, and optimized by utilizing HFSS. A prototype of V-shaped DRA is fabricated with Eccostock HiK dielectric bar ($\epsilon_r=10$) as shown in Fig. 4.1. The circular patch was cut down in shape manually by using copper foil tape of thickness 0.07 mm. Manual cutting with precise dimension is difficult at such a small scale. So, measurement was done using a circular patch on both sides having radius around 4.8 mm as shown in Fig. 4.1. This approximation of radius and manual fabrication results in concomitant imperfections which are slight dislocation of the circular patch on the DRA surface, soldering deformity and deposits, and adhesive applied for placing the DRA on the copper plate. These limitations produce variation in simulated and measured results which can be minimized in commercial fabrication. Fig. 4.10 shows the comparison between simulated and measured results of impedance bandwidth and axial ratio. Simulated and measured impedance bandwidths of proposed DRA are 24% (7.8-10 GHz) and 25% (7.85-10.1 GHz) respectively. Simulated and measured axial ratio bandwidths of proposed DRA are 5% (8.44-8.86 GHz) and 4% (8.35-8.7 GHz) respectively. Measured results show agreement with simulated results with some variations due to manufacturing deformities. Fig. 4.11 shows simulated and measured gain and simulated radiation efficiency of proposed DRA at $\theta=50^\circ$ and $\phi=50^\circ$. Maximum radiation efficiency is 94.5% and the maximum measured gain is 4.8 dBi in comparison to maximum simulated gain 5.6 dBi. Measured gain is less than simulated gain because of experimental approximations and fabrication deformities.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4.10 Comparison of simulated and measured results (a) S_{11} (b) AR DRA in $\theta=50^\circ$ and $\varphi=50^\circ$ direction

Fig. 4.11 Simulated gain, measured gain and radiation efficiency at $\theta=50^\circ$ and $\phi=50^\circ$ of proposed V-shaped DRA

(a) E Plane

(b) H Plane

Fig. 4.12 Measured and simulated radiation pattern of the proposed DRA at 9.6 GHz frequency

Fig. 4.13 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of the proposed DRA at 8.65 GHz and $\varphi=50^{\circ}$ for circular polarization

Figure 4.12 shows the radiation pattern at 9.6 GHz. The antenna exhibits linear polarization at 9.6 GHz. Figure 4. 13 shows gain (LHCP and RHCP) radiation pattern at 8.65 GHz. The antenna exhibits circular polarization at 8.65 GHz. Dash et. al [139] proposed dual-band circularly polarized triangular DRA with narrow AR bandwidth and low gain. Fakhte et. al [129] achieved high AR bandwidth of 6% using four stacked rotated rectangular DRAs. Kishk et. al [140] discussed elliptical DRA with 14% impedance bandwidth and 3.5% AR bandwidth. In comparison to these recent DRAs operating in X band, proposed fabricated DRA exhibits wide impedance bandwidth (25%) and pleasing AR bandwidth (4%).

An anechoic chamber is the most widely used electromagnetic measurement system. The results of the proposed antenna prototype have been measured in a rectangular shaped anechoic measurement chamber. A horn antenna has been used as a reference antenna. The measuring antenna is placed in line with the reference antenna. The photograph of the anechoic measurement chamber is shown in Fig. 4.14. Two-antenna method has been used to measure the axial ratio as explained in [215,216]. Receiving antenna is placed at Fraunhofer region in respect to the frequency of interest, from the transmitting antenna which is a fabricated prototype in this case. Anritsu vector network analyzer (MS2038C) that ranges

up to 20 GHz has been used to measure S-parameters of the prototype. Surface current movement at the surface of DRA is shown in Fig. 4.15, at different phase angles 0° , 90° , 180° and 270° . It shows RHCP movements of the current vector on DRA surface.

Fig. 4.14 Measurement setup of VDRA in an anechoic chamber

Fig. 4.15 Simulated surface current at 8.65 GHz at different phase angles (0° , 90° , 180° , 270°)

4.6 Summary

A wideband circularly polarized V-shaped DRA is discussed in this chapter. The maximum gain of the antenna is 4.8 dBi measured and 5.6 dBi simulated with pleasing circular polarization bandwidth of 8.35-8.7 GHz. The antenna operates in 7.85-10.1 GHz band which lies in X band. The proposed antenna is equipped with various advantages like its compact design with the height of just 11 mm and volume 1848 mm^3 with acceptable circular polarization and impedance bandwidth. The DRA falls in the category of the deserving candidate to be validated as compact design for it exhibits a directional circular polarization and a better average gain. This antenna can be used in various applications of

X-band which includes satellite communication, RADAR and military applications. This antenna also demonstrates directional circular polarization which is required feature in some of high end applications where security matters such as military applications. Proposed antenna is good candidate for X band applications.

Sumer Singh
Singhwal

CHAPTER 5

WIDEBAND CIRCULARLY POLARIZED MDRA

5.1 Introduction

Dielectric resonator antennas (DRA) are preferred choice in the spurting field of wireless communications because of their plenty of advantages. Advantages of DRA include their small size, wide operating bandwidth, low losses, multiple excitation schemes and multiple design parameters. They display wide bandwidth because their radiation area is greater than microstrip patch antenna. DRA have more degree of freedom to design such as length, width and height in rectangular DRA and radius and height in cylindrical DRA. They showcase low losses because of absence of metallic boundary and surface. DRA can work in different modes depending upon the type of feeding scheme used. Petosa et al. [39] explained that radiation efficiency of a DRA is substantially unaffected by the dielectric constant of DRA and low loss dielectric material with ($2 \leq \epsilon_r \leq 140$) can be used for the purpose of antenna. Now a days, Circular polarization is much pursued property in antenna because of its various advantages. In [67,68], benefits of circular polarisation in mobile services and communications are explained; few of them are low polarisation losses and better performance against multipath interference and fading. Ullah, [71] reviewed recent wideband CP DRA having different shape, feeding technique and applications. In [101] Yong-Mei Pan et al, compared performances of low permittivity DRA ($\epsilon_r=5$) with high permittivity DRA ($\epsilon_r=10$) and concluded that a lower permittivity DRA is recommendable for achieving wide bandwidth but size of DRA is also increased, and mode excitation in low permittivity DRA

is also difficult in comparison with high permittivity DRA. In [125] Sun et al. use K9-glass a low dielectric constant material ($\epsilon_r=6.85$) to make a dual band dual polarized cylindrical DRA. Also, with the use of lower dielectric constant materials ($5 \leq \epsilon_r \leq 20$), and proper choices of the dimensions in case of cylindrical DRA, radiation fields of DRA can be enhanced [11]. As per our study, we conclude that the design of an efficient DRA using low dielectric material is always a challenge. Also, the hemispherical DRA is preferred because of easy theoretical analysis and simple geometry as it does not need magnetic wall assumption [20, 45]. Another important factor is shape of hemispherical DRA provides simple interface between free space and itself.

In this chapter a new type of DRA named Mushroom DRA is investigated which is combination of cylindrical and hemispherical DRA and which radiates over large bandwidth. To achieve circular polarization two orthogonal feeds are used. Antenna operates at 3-5 GHz frequency range. Impedance bandwidth of antenna is 34.5% having range 3.5-5.1 GHz. Axial ratio bandwidth is 33% from 3.55-5 GHz. Peak gain at broadside direction is 6.5 dBi and average gain throughout operating band is 5.5 dBi. Latest International Telecommunication Union documentation [216] suggests lower 5G bands for 5G communication are 3.5-5 GHz. Proposed MDRA operates precisely in this band with added advantage of CP ($AR < 3\text{dB}$) throughout the operating band.

(a) Dimetric view (b) Top View with scale

Fig. 5.1-Fabricated MDRA Prototype

5.2 Design and Operating Principle of MDRA

5.2.1 Design Methodology

Configuration of the wideband circularly polarized MDRA is shown in Fig. 5.2 which has dimensional parameters given in Table 5.1. Here, DRA material is chosen with low dielectric constant $\epsilon_{DRA}=4.4$, FR4 fiberglass epoxy. Albeit, formulas to determine radius and height of DRA are available for $\epsilon_r \geq 10$ [40], so these design relations cannot be applied here directly.

Fig. 5.2- Design layout of proposed MDRA.

Table 5.1 Design parameters (in mm)

hdra	hsub	h1	h2	wsub	Lf	r1	r2	w	ϵ_{DRA}	ϵ_{SUB}	Probe radius
20	0.8	9	15	72	14	12	11	2.4	4.4	2.33	1

However, dimension of any dielectric resonator antenna is proportional inversely to $\sqrt{\epsilon_r}$ [3]. Inverse methodology adopted here, first finding dimension of DRA for $\epsilon_r = 10$ using Eq. (2.20) and then rescaling dimension to present case of $\epsilon_r = 4.4$ followed by fine tuning of parameters using HFSS simulator. The substrate is RT/duroid5870 with dielectric constant of 2.33, area of 72x72 mm² and height of 0.8 mm. Perpendicular feed configurations with width 2.4 mm and heights 9 mm and 15 mm, respectively has been adopted to excite MDRA orthogonally, so that our proposed antenna produces circular polarization

Fig. 5.3 Comparison between results of design step1 and step2 of MDRA

Design methodology involves two steps, first step is to design a cylindrical DRA (CDRA) with height hdra=20 mm, and in second step, placing a hemisphere of radius r2=11 mm on the top CDRA's improve its results. The final structure after placing hemisphere on the top of the cylinder is called MDRA. Comparison of impedance bandwidth, Gain and AR

bandwidth between step-1 and step-2, are shown in the Fig. 5.3. All of the above parameters in case of step-2 (MDRA) are improved effectively without any change in the resonance frequency. So, a hemisphere is coupled with the CDRA in such a way that resonance frequency remains same but circular polarization increases due to increase in surface area, in case of MDRA. Circular polarization can be achieved in the MDRA by adopting hybrid feeding configuration, which is a combination of microstrip feed line and probe feed. This hybrid feeding consist of a L shaped microstrip feed line network with two orthogonal, conformal, engraved probes, as shown in Fig. 5.2 (a). So, the proposed MDRA are excited by two conformal probes, which are engraved on MDRA and placed at orthogonal position with one another. Here phase quadrature condition is obtained between orthogonal hybrid modes ($HE_{11\delta}^x$ and $HE_{11\delta}^y$) by modifying corresponding probe lengths.

Fig. 5.4 S11 comparison of MDRA with Probe-1, Probe-2 and both probes

5.2.2 Operational Principle

Operation of MDRA is explained in three steps. In step one MDRA is excited by single probe-1 such that $HE_{11\delta}^x$ mode dominates but no circular polarisation. In second step MDRA is excited by single probe-2 such that $HE_{11\delta}^y$ mode dominates but no circular

polarisation. By using theory of generation circular polarization by using orthogonal excitation given in literature [2, 3], in third step MDRA is excited by both the probes (probe-1 and probe-2) which results merging of both the $HE_{11\delta}^x$ and $HE_{11\delta}^y$ modes and produce circular polarisation. Heights of probe-1 and probe-2 are to be optimized for attaining phase quadrature condition between two orthogonal hybrid modes, to achieve circular polarisation. Two dips at 3.7 GHz and 4.6 GHz in axial ratio plot shown in Fig. 5.3 confirm presence of both the modes. Figure 5.4 illustrates S_{11} parameters of all three operational steps corresponding to MDRA excited by probe-1, probe-2 and both the probes, respectively. Electric field inside MDRA corresponding to all three steps explained above is shown in Fig. 5.5.

Fig. 5.5 E Field of MDRA with Probe-1, Probe-2 and both probes respectively

5.3 Parametric Analysis

Parametric study can be done to study effect of a single parameter on performance characteristics of the MDRA keeping all other design parameters constant. To achieve optimized design, exhaustive parametric analysis is necessary. There are three main parameters which are to be studied in detail. These are (1) radius of cylindrical DRA and hemispherical DRA (2) height of probe-1 and probe-2 (3) effect of dielectric constant of DRA. In following sub-section, effect of these parameters on impedance bandwidth, axial ratio bandwidth (ARBW) and gain has been studied.

5.3.1 Radius of cylindrical DRA and hemisphere DRA

Parametric variation of radius of cylindrical DRA is shown in Fig. 5.6. Parametric response is shown for four radii 10 mm, 11 mm, 12 mm, 13 mm. It is observed that impedance bandwidth widens and resonance frequency shifts w.r.t. radius (r_1), as resonance frequency is inversely proportional to radius. Gain varies between 3.5 to 6.5 dB for all radius (r_1). Axial ratio bandwidth widens as radius (r_1) increases. Parametric variation of radius of hemispherical DRA is depicted in Fig. 5.7. Parametric response is shown for four radii 10 mm, 11 mm, 12 mm and 13 mm. It is observed that axial ratio bandwidth improves as radius (r_2) increases. So, radius of hemisphere controls circular polarisation in DRA keeping impedance bandwidth same. Thus radius of hemisphere gives additional degree of freedom in MDRA.

5.3.2 Height of probe

Similarly, parametric variation with the height of probe (h_1) is shown in Fig. 5.8. Although parametric variation studied for 1-20 mm probe lengths but here parametric response had shown for four lengths 9 mm, 10 mm, 11 mm and 12 mm. It is observed that gain, impedance bandwidth decreases and axial ratio bandwidth dips, as h_1 increases. It is to be noted that $h_1=9\text{mm}$ is approximately equal to quarter wavelength ($0.26 \lambda_{\text{eff}}$), where $\lambda_{\text{eff}} = \lambda_0 / \sqrt{\epsilon_{r\text{DRA}}}$. Parametric variation of height of probe h_2 is shown in Fig. 5.9. Again, in this case, parametric variation studied for 1-20 mm probe lengths but here parametric response had shown for four lengths 12mm, 13mm, 14 mm and 15 mm just for brevity. It is observed that the resonant frequency will shift and the gain of the MDRA dips along with increase in axial ratio bandwidth, as h_2 increases. It is to be observed that $h_2=15\text{ mm}$ is approximately half wavelength ($0.45 \lambda_{\text{eff}}$) at resonant frequency.

5.3.3 Effect of Dielectric constant of DRA

To investigate role of dielectric constant chosen, a parametric study is also carried with respect to variation in dielectric constant of MDRA. Parametric response is shown for five dielectric constants 4.4, 6, 8, 10. So, it is evident from Fig. 5.10, that low dielectric material DR antenna has wide bandwidth as discussed in [11,101].

Fig. 5.6 Parametric variations of S11, Gain and AR for radius of cylindrical DRA (r_1)

Fig. 5.7 Parametric variation of S11, Gain and AR for radius of hemisphere DRA (r_2)

Fig. 5.8 Parametric variation of S11, Gain and AR for height of probe h_1

Fig. 5.9 Parametric variations of S11, Gain and AR for height of probe h_2

Fig. 5.10 Parametric variations of S11, Gain and AR for different dielectric constants of MDRA

5.4 Results and Discussion

For the verification of the simulation results a prototype of the proposed DRA is fabricated, as shown in Fig. 5.1. Approximation of radius, height, smoothness and manual fabrication, results concomitant imperfections which are slight dislocation of the MDRA on line feed surface, soldering deformity and deposits, adhesive applied for placing MDRA on substrate. These limitations produce variation in simulated and measured results which can be minimized by when fabrication is done commercially by the manufacturers. Figure 5.10 shows comparison between simulated and measured reflection coefficient and gain. Measured results are in approximate agreement with simulated results because manual design of MDRA. Figure 5.10 shows comparison between simulated and measured AR in broadside direction ($\theta=0^0$, $\Phi=0^0$) and simulated radiation efficiency. It is observed from Fig. 5.10 that radiation efficiency maximizes up to 66% at center frequency. This moderate radiation efficiency is due to lossy FR4 material used in construction of DRA. Impedance bandwidth is 34% (3.5-5.1 GHz) with center frequency of 4.3 GHz. Axial ratio bandwidth is almost covering the complete operating band (3.55-5 GHz). Peak gain in broadside direction is 6.5 dB whereas average gain is around 5.5 dB throughout the operating band.

To verify circular polarization in complete operating band, three frequencies in the operating frequency range radiation pattern at three frequencies (3.75 GHz, 4.3 GHz, 4.6 GHz) are plotted as shown in the Fig. 5.11. It shows uniformity in radiation pattern at all the three frequencies which confirm uniform behaviour of radiation pattern throughout the operating frequency band. It shows E-plane and H-plane co-polarization and x-polarization

field radiation pattern at 3.75 GHz, 4.3 GHz and 4.6 GHz frequencies. It is also observed that, for both E and H Planes measured Co-Pol fields are greater than X-Pol fields by ~20dB in the broadside direction ($\theta=0^0$, $\Phi=0^0$).

Fig. 5.11 Comparison of simulated and measured S11, Gain and AR. Simulated Radiation Efficiency

Fig. 5.12 Radiation pattern of antenna in E-plane (a, b, c) and H-plane (d, e, f) at frequencies 3.75 GHz, 4.3 GHz, 4.6 GHz

Table 5.2 represents other antenna metrics such as half power Beam width (HPBW), front to back ratio (F/B), side lobe level (SLL), first null beam width (FNBW) for three frequencies. Radiation characteristics were examined at other frequencies of operating band and found stable across complete operating band. Figure 5.12 shows, the electric field distribution inside the MDRA at 4.3 GHz. Electric field distribution inside MDRA for different phase angles at frequency 4.3 GHz is illustrated in Fig. 5.13. It confirms left hand circularly polarized (LHCP) field in MDRA as the direction of field rotates accordingly for

phase angles 0° , 90° , 180° and 270° . An anechoic chamber is the most widely used electromagnetic measurement system. The results of the proposed antenna prototype have been measured in a rectangular shaped anechoic measurement chamber. A horn antenna has been used as a reference antenna. The measuring antenna is placed in line with the reference antenna.

Table 5.2 Antenna Radiation parameters of proposed DRA

Frequency	HPBW	F/B	SLL	FNBW
3.75 GHz	80°	11.1 dB	11.1 dB	300°
4.3 GHz	90°	11.6 dB	9.99 dB	310°
4.6 GHz	110°	11.3 dB	9.39 dB	260°

Fig. 5.13 Electric Field distribution inside MDRA at (a) 0° (b) 90° (c) 180° (d) 270° phase angles at 4.3 GHz

The photograph of the anechoic measurement chamber is shown in Fig. 5.14. Two-antenna method has been used to measure the axial ratio as explained in [214, 215]. Receiving antenna is placed at Fraunhofer region in respect to the frequency of interest, from the transmitting antenna which is a fabricated prototype in this case. Anritsu vector network analyzer (MS2038C) that ranges up to 20 GHz has been used to measure S-parameters of the prototype. A Circularly polarized DRA is essential in communication system as Luk and Leung [2] quoted regarding CP DRA, “Sometimes, however, systems using circular polarisation (CP) are preferred because they are insensitive to the transmitter and receiver orientations. In some applications, such as satellite communications, it also offers less

sensitivity to propagation effects. In contrast, an LP signal cannot be received properly when the transmitter is orthogonal to the received field. Consequently, more effort has been devoted to the CP DRA in recent years.” The present CP DRA offered wide ARBW with good impedance bandwidth making it suitable for various wireless applications.

Fig. 5.14 Antenna Measurement Setup

5.5 Summary

In this chapter a novel shape mushroom shaped DRA is discussed. Major performance measurement factors such as impedance bandwidth, gain and axial ratio bandwidth is satisfactory for discussed radiator. It exhibits 34.5% impedance bandwidth and 33% axial ratio bandwidth with peak gain of 6.5 dBi. One of the advantages of this antenna is its simplicity in construction without any cuts and slots. An L shaped microstrip feed line network with two orthogonal, conformal, engraved probes are used to excite hybrid modes in MDRA. Circular polarized antennas are more acceptable in practical applications because of various advantages over linear polarized antennas. The proposed MDRA also exhibits wide circular polarization bandwidth which makes it good choice for practical applications. Advantages of proposed antenna are ease of design and complete overlapping of impedance

bandwidth and ARBW with good gain. ITU documentation [216] suggests that 3.5-5 GHz band is to be proposed for lower 5G band communication. Proposed antenna is good candidate for 5G communication in this band.

Sumer Singh
Singhwal

CHAPTER 6

DUAL-PORT MIMO DRA WITH SINGLE DR ELEMENT

6.1 Introduction

Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) technology uses multiple transmitters and receivers to transfer more data at the same time. The advent of MIMO antennas is boon for human kind, seeking high speed wireless data transmission in various applications. Initially patch antenna based MIMO antennas were proposed in literature until Ishmiya et. al. [65,66] proposed DRA based MIMO antenna which have more degree of freedom for designing and low loss due to absence of metal in DRA. Advantages of MIMO technology, combines with advantages of DRA, forming a new technology called DRA based MIMO antenna. In the literature, researchers proposed different DRA based MIMO antenna for different applications. Yan et al. [153] proposed split cylindrical DRA based MIMO antenna for LTE femtocell base stations. Thamae et al. [169] proposed dual-port cylindrical DRA with two orthogonal feeds. Yan et al. [154] proposed dual-port frequency agile MIMO DRA for dynamic spectrum access applications in cognitive radios. Roslan et al. [174] investigated MIMO rectangular DRA (RDRA) for 4G applications. Johnstone et. al. [187] proposed eight port cylindrical DRA MIMO antenna. Sharawi et al. [184] proposed eight-element, dual-band, low profile MIMO antenna system using cylindrical DRA for wireless access points. Hussain et al. [186] proposed eight CDRA based MIMO linear antenna array system for

mm-wave applications. Roslan et al. [174] proposed two F shaped DRAs based MIMO antenna by exciting two orthogonal modes at two ports for 4G applications. Nasir et al. [171] presented single rectangular DRA based MIMO antenna fed by two microstrip lines for 4G applications. Sharma et al. [156] proposed two element mushroom shaped DRA excited by a conformal trapezoidal patch to achieve wideband operation. Sharma et al. [180] proposed two element CDRA based hybrid MIMO antenna for WLAN and WiMAX applications. Das et al. [168] presented a compact back-to-back DRA-based four-port MIMO antenna system with bi-directional diversity.

Fig. 6.1. Fabricated prototype of DRA

Fig. 6.2 Fabricated prototype of MIMO DRA

In this chapter, first, a single feed DRA is presented and fabricated which is extended to dual feed MIMO DRA. Prototypes of both the antennas, as shown in Fig. 6.1 and Fig. 6.2, have been fabricated to validate the simulated results. The measured impedance bandwidth of single feed DRA is 5-6 GHz (18%) and of dual feed MIMO DRA impedance bandwidth is 4.7-6.2 GHz (27.5%). Maximum gain has been measured 7.5 dBi (DRA) and 7.4 dBi (MIMO DRA). 10 dB port isolation bandwidth for MIMO DRA has been measured 5-6 GHz which is under impedance bandwidth and covers 5 GHz IEEE (802.11a/h/j/n/ac/ax) band for WLAN. Envelope correction coefficient (ECC), total active reflection coefficient (TARC), diversity gain (DG) and Mean effective gain (MEG) are measured within accepted range for MIMO operation.

Antenna design layouts of single feed DRA and dual feed MIMO DRA are shown in Fig. 6.3. In Fig. 6.3 (a, b) single feed DRA is shown and in Fig. 6.3 (c, d) dual feed MIMO DRA is shown. Figure 6.3 (e, f, g) shows trimetric and side views to demonstrate six metallic patches etched on body of DRAs.

Table 6.1 Design Parameters (in mm)

a	24.8	f	4.2	k	10.5	p	5
b	17.8	g	4	l	3	r	5
c	8.2	h	4.8	m	8	s	18
d	34.8	I	34	n	4.2	t	1.6
e	20.8	J	6.5	o	5.6	w	10.5

1.2 Antenna Design

Roger RT duroid substrate with ϵ_r 2.2 and height 1.6 mm is cut down in octagonal shape and a aperture coupled feed is etched on substrate. In Fig. 6.3 (a, b) single feed DRA is shown and in Fig. 6.3 (c, d) dual feed MIMO DRA is shown. Figure 6.3 (e, f, g) shows trimetric and side views to demonstrate six metallic patches etched on body of DRAs. Roger RT duroid substrate with ϵ_r 2.2 and height 1.6 mm is cut down in octagonal shape and an aperture coupled feed is etched on the substrate. Major steps involved to reach the proposed

Fig. 6.3 Geometry of the Antenna

Fig. 6.4 Steps involved in design of proposed DRA

DRA are shown in Fig. 6.4. Using Eq. (2.14-2.17) mentioned in chapter 2, for TE_{111} mode, a Rectangular DRA (RDRA) with dimensions $34 \times 34 \times 18 \text{ mm}^3$ resonating at 5 GHz has been designed. To improve gain and bandwidth of this RDRA, a cuboid has been cut from one of the sides of RDRA such that it has become a L-shaped DRA. By optimizing size of cuboid to cut from RDRA, Antenna-1 as shown in Fig. 6.4 has been obtained. A cylindrical DRA (CDRA) with optimized radius has been merged at the center of Antenna-1. Height of cylindrical DRA kept same as that of RDRA. In next step, four cylindrical air gaps with optimized radii and distance between each other, has been introduced in Antenna-2. It was noted that the air gap increases the operation frequency and, in addition, lowers the resonance impedance. The 3-dB bandwidth, however, is not significantly affected by the air gap [2]. In last step, six metallic patches with optimized width and height have been etched on the surface of DRA of Antenna-3. By image theory, effective shape of DRA has been changed in discrete manner as per placement of vertical patches etched on the surface of DRA and connected to ground [2]. So, these vertically patches result multiple resonances and high gain. Simulated impedance bandwidth and gain of Antenna-1, Antenna-2, Antenna-3 and Antenna-4 are shown in Fig. 6.4. In each step, optimization of different parameters has been done using simulation software ANSYS HFSS. From Fig. 6.5 it is observed that impedance bandwidth of Antenna-4 is largest among all four antennas. Figure 6.6 depicts that gain of Antenna-4 is highest among all four antennas and maximum simulated gain of Antenna-4 is 7.85 dBi. Figure 6.3 (c, d) shows geometry of dual feed MIMO DRA. It is a symmetrical structure which leads to similar S_{11} , S_{22} and S_{12} , S_{21} plots.

Fig. 6.5 Simulated S_{11} of Antenna-1, Antenna-2, Antenna-3 and Antenna-4

Fig. 6.6 Simulated Gain of Antenna-1, Antenna-2, Antenna-3 and Antenna-4

6.3 Results and Discussion

In this section, various results of fabricated prototypes have been discussed and compared with their simulated counterparts. Two prototypes have been fabricated one is single feed DRA and other is dual feed MIMO DRA. Adhesive has been used to stick dielectric resonators on substrate. Soldering deformity of connectors and adhesive on DRA may be responsible for variation in measured results.

Fig. 6.7 Simulated and measured S-parameters of proposed DRA

Fig. 6.8 Simulated and measured S-parameters of proposed MIMO DRA

Fig. 6.9 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of proposed DRA at 5.1 GHz and 5.7 GHz. E-plane (a, b) and H-plane (c, d)

Fig. 6.10 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of proposed MIMO DRA at 5.1 GHz and 5.7 GHz. E-plane (a, b) and H-plane (c, d)

Far field results have been measured in anechoic chamber with corrugated horn antenna as reference antenna while keeping other port matched with 50 Ω . Simulated and measured impedance bandwidth of DRA is shown in Fig. 6.7. Measured impedance bandwidth is 18% (5-6 GHz).

Fig. 6.11 Simulated and measured gain of proposed DRA and MIMO DRA

Figure 6.8 displays simulated and measured S_{11} and S_{12} of MIMO DRA. Due to symmetry of structure S_{22} is same as that of S_{11} and not shown in Fig. 6.8. It has been calculated that measured impedance bandwidth of fabricated MIMO DRA is 27.5% (4.7-6.2 GHz) and 10 dB isolation bandwidth is 5-6.2 GHz. Far field co-pol and x-pol radiation pattern has been measured at different frequencies and found suitable gap between co-pol and x-pol values at broadside [65] direction. Far field co-pol and x-pol radiation pattern measured at 5.1 GHz and 5.7 GHz which covers complete band of 5-6 GHz as shown in Fig. 6.9. Co-pol radiation is at least 10 dB better than x-pol radiation pattern in broadside direction at all frequencies. Figure 6.10 shows radiation pattern of MIMO DRA at 5.1 GHz and 5.8 GHz. Simulated and measured gain variation of both the antennas with respect to frequency is shown in Fig. 6.11.

Fig. 6.12 Simulated and Measured ECC and DG of proposed MIMO DRA

Fig. 6.13 Simulated and Measured MEG1, MEG2 and TARC of MIMO Antenna

It is observed that maximum gain of DRA is 7.5 dBi and of MIMO DRA is 7.3 dBi. MIMO performance metrics have also been studied to justify performance of proposed dual feed MIMO DRA. In chapter 2 detailed study of MIMO performance parameters is given. Figure 6.12 depicts simulated and measured ECC and DG of proposed MIMO DRA. Figure 6.13 depicts simulated and measured values of mean effective gain of both ports and total active reflection coefficient of proposed MIMO DRA. It has been concluded from Fig. 6.13 that MEG1 and MEG2 have almost same values in entire operating band and difference between MEGs is less than 3 dB whereas TARC value over entire operating band has been less than -15 dB which is good for MIMO operation.

Fig. 6.14 Simulated input impedance of proposed DRA and MIMO DRA

Maximum gain of single feed DRA is 6.5 dBi and maximum gain of dual feed MIMO DRA is 7.3 dBi. Figure 6.14 depicts simulated input impedance of both the antennas. The photograph of the anechoic measurement chamber is shown in Fig. 6.15. Two-antenna method has been used to measure the axial ratio as explained in [214, 215]. Receiving antenna is placed at Fraunhofer region in respect to the frequency of interest, from the transmitting

antenna which is a fabricated prototype in this case. Anritsu vector network analyzer (MS2038C) that ranges up to 20 GHz has been used to measure S-parameters of the prototype.

Fig. 6.15 (a) DRA and (b) MIMO DRA in anechoic chamber during measurement

6.4 Summary

In this chapter, single feed DRA is discussed followed by dual feed MIMO DRA. In both the DRAs aperture coupled feed is used to achieve wide bandwidth. Both the antennas have been fabricated to validate simulated results. Performance parameters of both the antennas are found with in satisfactory practical range and hence can be used for any practical applications such as WLAN. Discussed single feed DRA exhibits 18% (5-6 GHz) impedance bandwidth whereas dual feed MIMO DRA exhibits 27.5% (4.7-6.2 GHz) impedance bandwidth which is considered to be wide range for this frequency of operation. Gain of antenna is major concern for practical application. Discussed DRA and MIMO DRA also satisfies on gain parameters with maximum gain of the single feed DRA is 7.5 dBi and dual feed MIMO DRA is 7.3 dBi. Both the antennas are suitable for 5 GHz IEEE (802.11a/h/j/n/ac/ax) WLAN applications. Advantages of proposed antennas are wide bandwidth, high gain and compact substrate size of area 32.8 cm^2 . Due to its compact size, these antennas can easily be mounted on any surface covered with radome to protect it from physical damage.

CHAPTER 7

DUAL-PORT MIMO DRA WITH CP AGILITY

7.1 Introduction

The fifth-generation (5G) wireless communication system can provide many advantages such as high capacity, higher data rate, and shorter latency. One of the promising 5G frequency band for wireless communication has been proposed around 3.5 GHz also known as Sub-6 GHz band and mid-band (1GHz-6GHz) [219-221]. This mid-band spectrum will be more diverse and scarcer; therefore, capacity enhancement can be achieved by means of spectral efficiency. In order to meet these requirements multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technology has been deployed for 5G wireless operations. MIMO technology improves channel capacity, link reliability in multipath propagation and assures higher transfer data rates. WiMAX (Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access) is a family of wireless broadband communication standards based on the IEEE 802.16 set of standards. There are various applications of WiMAX; some of them are, providing portable mobile broadband services all across countries, providing VoIP (Voice over Internet Protocol) and IPTV (Internet Protocol Television) services, smart grid and metering services etc. In the present scenario, a large number of users can access information at anytime, anywhere with high data rates due to WiMAX. The thirst for higher data rates in wireless communication technology leads to concept of multiple input multiple output (MIMO) antenna. Applications of MIMO antenna in transmit/receive systems, help passing through the previous limit of

single antenna proposed by Claude Shannon [151, 152]. MIMO antennas have now become synonymous to high-speed wireless communication technology such as long term evolution (LTE), 5G communications, wireless local area network (WLAN) and WiMAX. MIMO technology improves channel capacity, link reliability in multipath propagation and assures higher transfer data rates in wireless communication [222,223]. Initially, MIMO antenna was proposed and implemented using microstrip patch antenna technology, until Ishmiya et al. [65,66] presented a concept of MIMO using DRA for 802.11n applications. It paved the way for the different DRA based MIMO designs. It is observed that polarization diversity is often implemented by a dual-polarized antenna by utilizing linear polarization.

In comparison to LP antennas, circularly polarized (CP) antennas demonstrate several advantages such as effectiveness in combating multipath interference, robustness during polarization mismatching, etc. Due to these reasons, CP antennas have somewhat constantly received signal strength, which is very useful property in wireless communication where receiver antenna frequently changes its location in respect to the transmitter antenna [69]. Johnstone et al. presented eight-port CDRA for MIMO system with different polarization states (LHCP, RHCP, and LP) [187]. But here different polarizations (RHCP, LHCP, LP) were achieved using various combinations of phased input at eight ports and isolation between ports was also refrained from discussion. Sahu et al. discussed DRA based CP MIMO antenna for WLAN applications (5.2 GHz) [165]. However, it suffered with low impedance bandwidth (simulated 10.28%) and minimum isolation was also reported to be around -14 dB. The research area of CP dielectric resonator based MIMO antenna is still in nurturing phase, and this paper provides a good coupling in present catena of research. This article proposes the novel concept of CP agility in DRA based MIMO antenna. Here, CP bandwidth can be controlled by inserting different cylindrical shells of different radii into the ring DRA. It is notable that minimum AR frequency has been varied comfortably without much variation in 10 dB impedance bandwidth. In this paper, two dual-port DRA based CP agile MIMO antennas are proposed for WiMAX applications at 3.5 GHz. Two prototypes, as shown in the Fig. 7.1, are fabricated and measured results are compared with simulated data, obtained from ANSYS' FEM-based high-frequency structural simulator (HFSS).

Measured impedance bandwidth of the antenna-1 with CDRA and antenna-2 with RDRA are 21.2% (3.15-3.9 GHz) and 22.2% (3.12-3.9 GHz), respectively. The measured axial ratio bandwidth (ARBW) of antenna-1 and antenna-2 are 5.66% (3.26-3.45 GHz) and 4.25% (3.45-3.6 GHz) in broadside direction ($\theta = 0; \varphi = 0$). Isolation between ports is better than 20 dB over the entire impedance bandwidth and maximum gain of the antenna-1 and antenna-2 is 7.3 dBi and 7.2 dBi, respectively. MIMO performance metrics such as envelope correction coefficient (ECC), diversity gain (DG), mean effective gain (MEG) and total active reflection coefficient (TARC) have also been measured and found well within acceptable limits. In particular, ECC is below 0.001, DG is above 9.99 dB MEG1 and MEG2 of both the ports have difference less than 3 dB and TARC is less than -20 dB for both the antennas.

Fig. 7.1 Photographs of proposed Antenna-1 and Antenna-2

7.2 Antenna Geometry and CP Agility

7.2.1 Geometry of Antenna

Antenna design layout is shown in Fig. 7.2. It comprises a properly shaped ground plane hosting an octagonal substrate, an L type feed network, conformal probes and two DRAs. All the design parameters, optimized using HFSS simulation software, are shown in Table 7.1.

Fig. 7.2 Geometry of Antenna

RT Duroid with dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 2.33$, thickness 0.8 mm and $\tan\delta = 0.0012$ have been used as substrate and Eccostock Hik bar with $\epsilon_r = 9.8$, $\tan\delta = 0.001$ have been used as dielectric resonator antenna material. The height of DRA is 18 mm . Each single DRA has been excited by two conformal probes having heights $H1=9 \text{ mm}$, $H2=15 \text{ mm}$ and radius 1 mm as shown in Fig. 7.1(b). The conformal probe excitation is an easy and effective feed method where it is required to couple field energy between DRA and feed line. It also helps in matching by adjusting height of probe and excitation of $HE_{11\delta}$ mode. Conformal probe 1 excites $HE_{11\delta}^x$ and probe-2 excites $HE_{11\delta}^y$ mode in CDRA, as shown in Fig. 7.3.

Fig. 7.3 Generation of fundamental orthogonal hybrid modes in cylindrical DRA

A CP field can be attained in a DRA by exciting two orthogonal components of fields with same magnitude and in phase quadrature. Probe-1 and probe-2, as shown in Fig. 7.1(b) and Fig. 7.2, have been placed on L type feed network. Orthogonal modes inside DRA have been excited by these two probes. Phase quadrature relationship between both the orthogonal field components is controlled by optimizing the heights ($H1$ and $H2$) of the probes. Width of L-type microstrip feed line corresponds to 50Ω characteristic impedance line is calculated and optimized using HFSS software. Design equation used in [40] for $HE_{11\delta}$ mode in CDRA is given in Eq. (2.20). Dimensions of CDRA have been calculated using Eq.

(2.20) and optimized using HFSS simulation software. In antenna-1 two CDRAs are placed on the substrate whereas in antenna-2 two RDRAs are placed on the substrate. A comparison between simulated S-parameters of antenna-1 and antenna-2 is shown in Fig. 7.4. It is observed from Fig. 7.4 that there are two resonance due to dual probe excitation.

Table 7.1 Design parameters (in mm)

L1	85.5	L5	35	D2	5
L2	38.5	F1	31.2	W	2.4
L3	15.5	F2	13.6	Hsub	0.8
L4	51	D1	25	Hdra	18
H1	9	H2	15		

Fig. 7.4: Simulated S-parameters comparison of Antenna-1 and Antenna-2

7.2.2 CP Agility

CP agility describes the quickness of changing, minimum AR frequency by mechanical insertion of concentric cylindrical shells in the ring DRAs.

(a) Axial Ratio

(b) S_{11}

Fig. 7.5 Simulated AR and S_{11} for different radii of concentric cylindrical shells in Antenna-4

Simulated ARs and S_{11} for different radii of concentric cylindrical shells, which are to be inserted in the ring DRA, are shown in Fig. 7.5. It shows simulated ARs and S_{11} corresponding to radius $R_2 = 0 - 5$ mm increased in step size of 0.5 mm.

It is pertinent to note that minimum AR frequencies for different air gap cylinder radii, as shown in Fig. 7.5(a), are always in their respective 10 dB impedance bandwidths as shown in Fig. 7.5(b). Mechanical snatching, insertion, extraction of concentric cylindrical shells in ring DRA can be accomplished by robotic tool changer or robotic quick change system [217]. Practical implementation of robotic quick change system is superbly done by Yaskawa America, Inc., Motoman Robotics [218]. Figure 7.6 shows five step insertion and extraction process using mechatronics robotic tool changer system. Antenna-1 can be configured when all the cylindrical shells are inserted in the ring DRA. Effect of gap between concentric cylindrical shells has also been studied and no significant effects on performance of antenna has been found, considering gap of 0.1-0.2 mm. Minimum AR frequency can easily be shifted by extracting cylindrical shells 1-5, in succession as shown in Fig. 7.6.

Fig. 7.6 Mechanical insertion and extraction of concentric cylindrical shells to achieve CP agility

7.3 Results and Discussion

In this section, analysis of results and their implications are discussed. Two prototypes of dual-port circularly polarized DRA with MIMO capability have been fabricated as shown in Fig. 7.1. Simulated and measured results of antenna-1 and antenna-2 are shown in Fig. 7.7. Simulated results are in good agreement with measured results. Measured

impedance bandwidth of antenna-1 and antenna-2 are 21.2% (3.15-3.9 GHz) and 22.2% (3.12-3.9 GHz), respectively.

Fig. 7.7 Simulated and measured responses of antenna-1 and antenna-2 (a) S-Parameters (b) Axial ratio at broadside direction (c) Gain and radiation efficiency at broadside direction

Fig. 7.8 Simulated Z_{in} of Antenna-1 and Antenna-2

According to Balanis [1], “The sense of rotation is always determined by rotating the phase-leading component toward the phase-lagging component and observing the field rotation as the wave is viewed as it travels away from the observer. If the rotation is clockwise, the wave is right-hand (or clockwise) circularly polarized; if the rotation is counterclockwise, the wave is left-hand (or counterclockwise) circularly polarized. The rotation of the phase-leading component toward the phase-lagging component should be done along the angular separation between the two components that is less than 180° . Phases equal to or greater than 0° and less than 180° should be considered leading whereas those equal to or greater than 180° and less than 360° should be considered lagging.” Following these guidelines given in literature, the 3 dB ARBWs of antenna-1 and antenna-2 have been measured 190 MHz and 150 MHz in broadside direction, respectively. Port isolation is also greater than 20 dB over the complete impedance bandwidth and maximum gain of the antenna-1 and antenna-2 is 7.3 dBi and 7.2 dBi, respectively. Envelope correction coefficient (ECC), diversity gain (DG), mean effective gain (MEG) and total active reflection coefficient (TARC) have also been measured for both antennas. Figure 7.7 (c) reports simulated gain, measured gain and simulated radiation efficiency of antenna-1 and antenna-2. Simulated

radiation efficiency is greater than 95% for both the antennas whereas measured radiation efficiencies are well above 90%. Maximum gain 7.3 dBi and 7.2 dBi are obtained for antenna- 1 and antenna-2. Input impedance of both the antennas are shown in Fig. 7.8.

Fig. 7.9 Measured and simulated E-plane (left) and H-Plane (right) radiation pattern of Antenna-1 at 3.35 GHz

Fig. 7.10 Measured and simulated E-plane (left) and H-Plane (right) radiation pattern of Antenna-2 at 3.5 GHz

It is observed from Fig. 7.8 that real impedance is around 50Ω in the entire operating band. Figure 7.9 shows simulated and measured radiation field pattern (LHCP and RHCP) of antenna-1 in E-Plane and H-Plane whereas Fig. 7.10 shows the same for antenna-2. Left hand CP component is greater than its right hand counterpart by more than acceptable limits for both the antennas. Radiation patterns have been plotted at minimum AR frequency for both the antennas.

Table 7.2 MIMO Parameters of Antenna-1 and Antenna-2

	ECC	DG	MEG1	MEG2	TARC
Simulated (Antenna-1 at 3.35 GHz)	1.3×10^{-4}	9.99	-13.98	-13.88	-44.98
Measured (Antenna-1 at 3.35 GHz)	2.7×10^{-5}	9.99	-13.8	-13.5	-43.2
Simulated (Antenna-2 at 3.5 GHz)	1.2×10^{-4}	9.99	-14.2	-14.1	-35.02
Measured (Antenna-2 at 3.5 GHz)	5.4×10^{-5}	9.99	-14.4	-14.3	-34.5

According to Sharawi [191], “The correlation coefficient is a measure that describes how much the communication channels are isolated or correlated with each other. This metric considers the radiation pattern of the antenna system, and how much the patterns affect one another when operated simultaneously (which is the case in a MIMO antenna system). The square of the correlation coefficient is known as the envelop correlation coefficient.” Simulated and measured ECC has been obtained less than 0.001 which satisfies the limit $ECC < 0.3$ mentioned in [192-195]. Desirable value of TARC for MIMO system is less than 0 dB. For both the proposed antennas MEG1 and MEG2 have almost same values in entire operating band and difference between MEGs is less than 3 dB whereas TARC value over entire operating band has been less than -15 dB which is good enough for MIMO operation. Table 7.2 summarizes the MIMO performance metrics results of antenna-1 and antenna-2 at 3.35 GHz and 3.5 GHz, respectively. An anechoic chamber is the most widely

used electromagnetic measurement system. The results of the proposed antenna prototype have been measured in a rectangular shaped anechoic measurement chamber. A horn antenna has been used as a reference antenna. The measuring antenna is placed in line with the reference antenna. The photograph of the anechoic measurement chamber is shown in Fig. 7.11. Two-antenna method has been used to measure the axial ratio as explained in [214, 215]. Receiving antenna is placed at Fraunhofer region in respect to the frequency of interest, from the transmitting antenna which is a fabricated prototype in this case. Anritsu vector network analyzer (MS2038C) that ranges up to 20 GHz has been used to measure S-parameters of the prototype. Simple adhesive (glue) has been used to stick DRAs on substrate which resulted difference in measured and simulated results. Soldering deformity of connectors with ground and feed line might also be responsible for alteration of results. Far field results have been measured in anechoic chamber using horn antenna as reference antenna and keeping second port matched with 50Ω . A photograph of measurement setup is shown in Fig. 7.11.

Fig. 7.11 Measurement of Antenna parameters in Anechoic chamber

7.4 Summary

In this chapter, a novel concept of CP agility is presented with two antennas configurations. Two dual-port multiple input multiple output DRAs are proposed. Antennas

are fabricated on Rogers RT Duroid substrate having dielectric constant 2.33 and thickness 0.8 mm. Both the fabricated antennas exhibit good impedance bandwidth of 21.2% and 22.2% and low mutual coupling between ports with minimum isolation of -20 dB. Both the proposed antennas also exhibit circular polarization with axial ratio bandwidth of 190 MHz and 150 MHz. Proposed antennas evinced the CP agility by mechanical insertion and extraction of concentric cylindrical shells of different radii using robotic tool changer or robotic quick change system. Proposed antenna is good candidate for 5G communication in this band.

Sumer Singh
Singhwal

CHAPTER 8

DUAL BAND CIRCULARLY POLARIZED MIMO DRA

8.1 Introduction

The field of wireless communication is growing rapidly, to fulfill human need of high-speed data transfer applications. MIMO technology is a boon for high speed data communication because of various advantages such as diversity performance and improved channel capacity [152, 222,223]. In addition, the use of circular polarization in MIMO systems are also advantageous due to low polarization loss, less multipath interference, better performance and reliability [69]. There are various types of antennas to adopt MIMO functionality and out of these antennas, DRAs are the promising ones due to their advantages such as high radiation efficiency, less surface wave loss and low ohmic losses [40]. Nowadays dual frequency antennas are mostly desired because of increasing wireless applications. In [172], authors proposed dual band MIMO DRA for WLAN applications, but isolation at upper band was around 12 dB only. Khan et.al. [159-162] proposed dual band MIMO DRA for WiMAX/WLAN applications. In [175], authors proposed dual polarized triple band (2.21–3.13, 3.40–3.92, and 5.30–6.10 GHz) MIMO DRA for WLAN/WiMAX applications. In this work, Sahu et. al. achieved circular polarization bandwidth for upper band only. Reported gain in the three bands are 1.5 dBi, 4.2 dBi and 2.3 dBi respectively. Sharma et. al. [179] proposed dual band MIMO DRA for LTE/WLAN application using half split cylindrical dielectric resonator. In [180] a tri-band dielectric resonator based hybrid antenna for WLAN/WiMAX application is reported. In this work, circular ring with T-shaped

printed line produces dual hybrid radiating modes in cylindrical dielectric resonator antenna (CDRA). In this letter, a dual band compact MIMO DRA is proposed with circular polarization operating in 3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz bands. Very few research articles have been published so far in the area of dual band circularly polarized MIMO DRA. In the present work, two ring DRAs have been excited by arc-shaped line feed and conformal probes. Total substrate size is $110 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ which makes it compact for WiMAX applications (3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz). Envelope correlation coefficient (ECC) is below 0.02 and diversity gain (DG) is around 9.99 dB for both bands.

8.2 Antenna Structure and Theory

The geometry of the proposed antenna is shown in Fig. 8.1. The used substrate is RT Duroid with dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 2.33$, thickness $h=0.8 \text{ mm}$ and $\tan \delta = 0.0012$. Moreover, Eccostock Hik bar with $\epsilon_r = 9.8$, $\tan \delta = 0.001$ has been used as DRA material. Antenna structure comprises *i)* a ($110 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$) sized rectangular substrate, *ii)* two arc shaped microstrip lines feed, *iii)* two conformal probes per Ring DRA with heights 9 mm and 15 mm, *iv)* two ring shaped DRAs, *v)* a DGS structure with a rectangle cut in the ground. In this antenna, conformal probes have been chosen to excite the $HE_{11\delta}$ mode and $HE_{12\delta}$ mode having different resonant frequencies in the Ring DRA. Naturally comprehended ‘conformal probe’ has been designed, optimized by using HFSS software, and experimentally proved with a promise. In $HE_{11\delta}$ mode in the Ring DRA is excited by using probe feed technique, which provides good impedance matching.

However, the coupling will be weak for the higher order modes excited with the probe feed techniques. To realize the dual mode excitation (for the structure supporting both the modes) with a single feed requires a proper feed network, which excites two orthogonal modes at each frequency. The conformal feed consists of two probes, which excite two orthogonal components of fields with same magnitude and in time-phase quadrature in the Ring DRA.

Fig. 8.1 Antenna Structure and Design Parameters (in mm)

So, the conformal probe excitation is an easy and effective feed method where it is required to couple field energy between DRA and feed-line [102]. It should be relevant to note that the conformal probe feed structure should also be helpful to realize circular polarization. Principle of generation of CP states that, CP field can be attained in a DRA by exciting two orthogonal components of fields with same magnitude and in time-phase quadrature. Following this principle, in the proposed antenna, arc-shaped line feed provides orthogonality in field input and heights of probes decides time phase quadrature relationship. Both the probes, as shown in Fig. 8.1, have been placed on arc-shaped feed line. These probes excite orthogonal modes inside DRA because each of them can generate an x-polarized and y-polarized electric field lines. Time-phase quadrature relationship between both orthogonal

field components is controlled by optimized the heights of the two probes. Coupling of field components between the probe and Ring DRA, and impedance matching depends on the feed network configuration, which can be optimized by choosing different width of the arc-shaped line and feed line. Width of feed line and arc-shaped line corresponds to 50Ω and 70Ω characteristic line impedance, respectively.

Fig. 8.2 S-Parameters and ARBW comparison with Ring DRA, with CDRA and without DRA

By adjusting the height of probes the $HE_{11\delta}$ mode in the Ring DRA can be excited. Conformal probe-1 excites $HE_{11\delta}^x$ mode while probe- 2 excites $HE_{11\delta}^y$ mode in the Ring DRA. As a proof two dips at 3.3 GHz and 3.6 GHz, respectively, in S-parameter graph in Fig. 8.2 can be observed. Design equation used to calculate the resonant frequency of the Ring DRA is given in Eq. (2.14-2.17). The resonant frequency of the $HE_{12\delta}$ mode is approximated as 1.6 times of that of $HE_{11\delta}$ mode [118, 180]. The second resonance at 5.5

GHz is due to $HE_{12\delta}$ mode. Details about how to calculate second resonance frequency band is also explained in [118]. Figure 8.2 shows simulated responses of the proposed antenna with Ring DRA, with CDRA and without DRA. From Fig. 8.2, it is clear that the Ring DRA provides lower frequency band while upper frequency band is the combined effect of Ring DRA and conformal probes. Antenna with Ring DRA has improved impedance bandwidth, isolation and ARBW in comparison to antenna with CDRA. An optimization aiming to find the diameter of the hole in the Ring DRA has been performed using HFSS software. A rectangular slot is cut from ground to increase isolation between ports. Minimum isolation measured between ports in lower and upper operating band is -16.2 dB and -16.5 dB, respectively. Radius of arc-shaped feed is optimized using HFSS simulation software. In the case of $HE_{12\delta}$ mode, resonant frequency is approximated as in Eq. (8.1) from [118, 180]. Second resonance at 5.5 GHz is due to $HE_{12\delta}$ mode which is confirmed from field distribution as shown in Fig. 8.3.

$$f_{r(HEM_{12\delta})} = 1.6 \times f_{r(HEM_{11\delta})} \quad (8.1)$$

Fig. 8.3 Field distribution on the surface of Ring DRA at 3.5 GHz (top) and 5.5 GHz (bottom) at Phase= 0, 90, 180, 270 degrees

8.3 Results and Validation

To validate the simulated results, a prototype of proposed antenna has been fabricated and measured results have been compared to simulated counterparts. Figure 8.4 shows different views of fabricated prototype. S-parameters of lower and upper bands are shown in Fig. 8.5. It is observed from Fig. 8.5 that simulated and measured impedance bandwidths agree each other by acceptable margins which is due to manual measurement setup and soldering deformities.

Fig. 8.4 Different views of Fabricated Prototype

The 3 dB axial ratio bandwidths (ARBW) for both bands are shown in Fig. 8.6. Simulated and measured results are in good agreement with some reduced variations due to fabrication tolerance and soldering imperfections. Measured 10 dB impedance bandwidths are 3.1 GHz -3.75 GHz (19%) and 5.3 GHz -5.6 GHz (9.4%); the 3 dB ARBWs are 3.425 GHz -3.6 GHz (5%) and 5.45 GHz -5.55 GHz (2%), respectively, in broadside direction. Isolation between ports at 3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz have been measured -16.2 dB and -16.5 dB, respectively. Orientation of polarization can be observed by field distribution on the surface of Ring DRA at different phase angles as shown in Fig. 8.3.

Fig. 8.5 S-Parameters of Proposed Antenna

Fig. 8.6 ARBW of proposed Antenna

Fig. 8.7 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of proposed antenna at 3.5 GHz E-plane (Left) and H-Plane (Right)

Fig. 8.8 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of proposed antenna at 5.5 GHz E-plane (Left) and H-Plane (Right)

Simulated and measured radiation pattern at 3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz are shown in Fig. 8.7 and Fig. 8.8, respectively. Simulated and measured radiation pattern results concur with each other. Figure 8.7 and Fig. 8.8 shows that left hand CP wave dominates over right hand counterpart by acceptable margin in both the bands centered at 3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz. According to Sharawi [191], “The terms coupling and isolation are usually inter changed in the literature as low coupling yields high isolation. More specifically, isolation is usually found directly from the S parameters. It is important to mention that the isolation and

correlation coefficient are two different quantities. Although lower coupling (high isolation) yields lower correlation, it only accounts for isolation between the input ports of the antennas through the antenna's structure, and does not account for radiated field coupling. Low coupling (high isolation) thus does not guarantee a low correlation coefficient, and vice versa. High isolation and low correlation coefficients are required for a MIMO antenna system to provide good diversity performance." MIMO performance has been evaluated by calculating ECC and DG using Eq. (2.24-2.30) mentioned in chapter 2. ECC shows amount of channel isolation in a wireless communication link. Simulated and measured ECC and DG for lower and upper bands are shown in Fig. 8.9. ECC is well below 0.5 throughout the lower and upper operating bands and correlation coefficient (square root of ECC) is well below 0.3. DG is above 9.8 dB for both the operating bands. For better analysis, simulated and measured ECC and DG at 3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz have been displayed in Table 8.1.

Fig. 8.9 ECC and DG of proposed Antenna in lower (left) and upper (right) frequency band of operation

Figure 8.10 shows surface current distribution on the ground plane to visualize isolation between ports at both the resonant frequencies. According to Balanis [1], "The sense of rotation is always determined by rotating the phase-leading component toward the phase-lagging component and observing the field rotation as the wave is viewed as it travels away from the observer. If the rotation is clockwise, the wave is right-hand (or clockwise) circularly polarized; if the rotation is counterclockwise, the wave is left-hand (or

counterclockwise) circularly polarized. The rotation of the phase-leading component toward the phase-lagging component should be done along the angular separation between the two components that is less than 180° . Phases equal to or greater than 0° and less than 180° should be considered leading whereas those equal to or greater than 180° and less than 360° should be considered lagging.”

Table 8.1 MIMO Performance Metrics of Antenna at 3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz

	ECC(3.5GHz)	DG(3.5GHz)	ECC(5.5GHz)	DG(5.5GHz)
Simulated	0.001852	9.99	0.000414	9.99
Measured	0.002314	9.99	0.000314	9.99

Fig. 8.10 Surface current distribution on ground at 3.5 GHz (left) and 5.5 GHz (right)

An anechoic chamber is the most widely used electromagnetic measurement system. The results of the proposed antenna prototype have been measured in a rectangular shaped anechoic measurement chamber. A horn antenna has been used as a reference antenna. The measuring antenna is placed in line with the reference antenna. The photograph of the anechoic measurement chamber is shown in Fig. 8.11. Two-antenna method has been used to measure the axial ratio as explained in [214, 215]. Receiving antenna is placed at Fraunhofer region in respect to the frequency of interest, from the transmitting antenna which is a fabricated prototype in this case. Anritsu vector network analyzer (MS2038C) that ranges

up to 20 GHz has been used to measure S-parameters of the prototype. ECC is calculated using measured field radiation pattern of MIMO DRA.

Fig. 8.11 MIMO DRA in anechoic chamber during measurement

8.4 Summary

In this chapter, a dual-band MIMO ring dielectric resonator antenna with appreciated CP performance have has been discussed. The proposed antenna operates on at 3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz bands. The structure consists of two ring DRAs excited by arc-shaped line feed and conformal probes. The total substrate size is $50 \times 110 \text{ mm}^2$ which makes it compact for sub- 6 GHz band applications (3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz). Measured ECC for both the bands is below 0.02 and DG is above 9.99 dB for both bands. Measured impedance bandwidths are 19% and 9.4% and ARBWs are 175 MHz and 100 MHz in broadside direction at 3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz resonant frequencies respectively. It demonstrates circular polarization in both the bands and size of antenna is also compact ($110 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$) which makes it good choice for WiMAX dual band applications. Envelope correlation coefficient

(ECC) is below 0.5 and diversity gain (DG) is around 9.8 dB for both the bands. Main advantages of proposed antenna are: *(i)* Simple and ease of fabrication: the shape of DRs, the microstrip line feed and the DGS structure are very simple, *(ii)* Compact in size with dual-elements on the substrate, *(iii)* Circular polarization bandwidth is available in both the operating bands. ITU documentation [216] suggests that 3.5-5 GHz band is to be proposed for lower 5G band communication, so discussed MIMO DRA can also be good candidate for upcoming 5G communication at lower band.

Sumer Singh
Singhwal

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

9.1 Conclusion

To summarize and conclude all the chapters of the thesis, chapter wise conclusions are given here.

In chapter 3 an antenna for microwave image sensing application is proposed. Presently only high permittivity DR are used due their multiple advantages. In microwave image sensing, cost is an important factor to consider because a sensor is always followed by signal processing circuitry, so overall cost of the system will be increased. For the microwave image sensing application, the gain of the device should be high and stable. The proposed DRA fulfill all the basic condition of the sensor. Proposed DRA can offer wide impedance bandwidth and AR bandwidth which is also desirable feather of the sensor. So, to reduce overall cost of system and improve performance, proposed prototype can be a good choice for image sensing applications at mm wave band such as satellite communication applications, 5G communications etc. CEPT documentation available on [209] concludes that 24.5-27.5GHz band is good candidate for 5G communication and harmonization is possible on this band all over the globe. According to [220], 28 GHz band is proposed for ESIM (Earth Stations in Motion) remote sensing and IMT (International Mobile Telecommunications) standards which are relevant to microwave remote sensing. Our proposed antenna covers this band and can be used as an image sensor in IMT standards and ESIM remote sensing applications. It is very small size comparable to wrist watch dial and

DRA height 0.48 cm, so it can also be used in wearable body sensors in mm wave band. Due to its low cost, commercial scalability is also possible.

In chapter 4, a wideband circularly polarized V-shaped DRA is presented. The maximum gain of the antenna is 4.8 dBi measured and 5.6 dBi simulated with pleasing circular polarization bandwidth of 8.35-8.7 GHz. The antenna operates in 7.85-10.1 GHz band which lies in X band. The proposed antenna is equipped with various advantages like its compact design with the height of just 11 mm and volume 1848 mm³ with acceptable circular polarization and impedance bandwidth. The DRA falls in the category of the deserving candidate to be validated as compact design for it exhibits a directional circular polarization and a better average gain.

In chapter 5, a mushroom shaped DRA is constructed which exhibits 34.5% impedance bandwidth and 33% axial ratio bandwidth with peak gain of 6.5dB. Proposed design idea is novel and simple in construction without any cuts and slots. An L shape microstrip feed line network with two orthogonal, conformal, engraved probes are used to excite hybrid modes in MDRA. Advantages of proposed antenna are ease of design and complete overlapping of impedance bandwidth and ARBW with good gain. ITU documentation [216] suggests that 3.5-5 GHz band is to be proposed for lower 5G band communication. Proposed antenna is good candidate for 5G communication in this band.

In chapter 6, a novel concept of CP agility is presented with two antennas configurations. Two dual-port multiple input multiple output DRAs are proposed. Antennas are fabricated on Rogers RT Duroid substrate having dielectric constant 2.33 and thickness 0.8 mm. Both the fabricated antennas exhibit good impedance bandwidth of 21.2% and 22.2% and low mutual coupling between ports with minimum isolation of -20 dB. Both the proposed antennas also exhibit circular polarization with axial ratio bandwidth of 190 MHz and 150 MHz. Proposed antennas evinced the CP agility by mechanical insertion and extraction of concentric cylindrical shells of different radii using robotic tool changer or robotic quick-change system. Diversity performance is also analyzed and entire analysis confirms that proposed MIMO antennas can be a good candidate for WiMAX applications.

In chapter 7, single feed DRA is proposed followed by dual feed MIMO DRA. Aperture coupled feed is used to achieve wide bandwidth. Both the antennas have been fabricated to validate simulated results. Proposed DRA exhibits 18% (5-6 GHz) impedance bandwidth whereas proposed dual feed MIMO DRA exhibits 27.5% (4.7-6.2 GHz) impedance bandwidth. Maximum gain of the proposed DRA is 7.5 dBi and proposed MIMO DRA is 7.3 dBi. Both the antennas are suitable for 5 GHz IEEE (802.11a/h/j/n/ac/ax) WLAN applications. Advantages of proposed antennas are wide bandwidth, high gain and compact substrate size of area 32.8 cm^2 .

In chapter 8, a dual-band MIMO ring dielectric resonator antenna with appreciated CP performance has been proposed. The proposed antenna operates at 3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz WiMAX bands. Measured ECC for both bands are below 0.02 and DG is above 9.99 dB for both bands. Measured impedance bandwidths are 19% and 9.4% and ARBW are 175 MHz and 100 MHz in broadside direction at 3.5 GHz and 5.5 GHz resonant frequencies respectively. It demonstrates circular polarization in both bands and size of antenna is also compact ($110 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$) which makes it good choice for WiMAX dual band applications.

9.2 Future Scope

In the future there is a scope to design MIMO antenna by using hybrid arrangement of microstrip resonator and DR. Similarly, very few papers are published in MIMO DRA having circular polarization capability, so in future there is good scope to design circularly polarised MIMO Antenna. At last, the scopes of MIMO dielectric resonator antennas are as follows: High gain MIMO DRA, CP MIMO DRA, hexaband MIMO DRA, hepta-band MIMO DRA, MIMO DRA using non-conventional shapes, MIMO DRA for 5G communication, MIMO DRA for smart phones, MIMO DRA for mobile terminal etc. In the present scenario and near future one can easily foresee that communication trend will become totally wireless. Like creators imagine in any Sci-Fi film, present generation is wishing for high end communications media. Even in the field of electricity, power and robotics and wireless communication, antennas are becoming essential part. MIMO based DRA antennas

become practical reality in near future in the field of high-speed wireless communication. It is also predictable that in future DRA can be used in medical applications and artificial intelligence to help medical science such as vision assistance for blinds/partially blinds. There are infinite possibilities of DRA as the hunt for best antennas is never ending one.

Sumer Singh
Singhwal

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Sumer Singh
Singhwal

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

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1. **Sumer Singh Singhwal**, Binod Kumar Kanujia, Ajit Singh, Jugul Kishor, “Novel circularly polarized dielectric resonator antenna for microwave image sensing application”, *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, Wiley Publishers, July 2019, vol. 61, issue 7, pp. 1821-1827.
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5. **Sumer Singh Singhwal**, Binod Kumar Kanujia, Ajit Singh, Jugul Kishor, Ladislau Matekovits, “Dual band circularly polarized MIMO DRA for sub-6 GHz

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7. **Sumer Singh Singhwai**, Binod Kumar Kanujia, Ajit Singh, Jugul Kishor, “Dual Band Circularly Polarized Antenna for Ka Band Applications” presented in *IEEE International Women Institute of Technology Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering (WITCON-ECE)-2019* on 22-23 Nov. 2019. (IEEE digital xplora library)

CURRICULUM VITAE

Sumer Singh Singhwal has completed B.E. in Electronics and Communication Engineering from M.D. University Rohtak in 2003 with distinction. He has earned his M.E. in Microwave Engineering from Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra, Ranchi in 2012 with distinction. He has also passed National Examination for Assistant Professorship (UGC-NET) in 2013. He has teaching experience in UG engineering colleges, of more than 13 years and industry experience, of more than 2 years. He has also worked as Junior Telecom Officer in government undertaking public sector unit Bharat Sanchar Nigam Limited for 2 years, which he left to pursue his PhD.

Mr. Singhwal has a keen interest in learning new techniques and languages. He has in-depth knowledge of MATLAB and Python script programming. He has strong knowledge of simulation software like ANSYS HFSS and MWS CST for Antenna design. Besides, he has possessed good knowledge of statistical programming using R programming language and spreadsheet software like MS Excel. He was among top 5% topper in a twelve weeks course “Antennas”, conducted by Prof. Girish Kumar, IIT Bombay in association with Government of India e-learning platform NPTEL. To understand research methodologies better, he has also undergone a four week

course from University of London MOOC through www.coursera.org on the topic “Understanding Research Methods”.

Mr. Singhwal has a major interest in designing of new antennas for wireless applications. He has been enthralled by rapid progress in dielectric resonator antennas in field of communications. Further, DRA based MIMO antennas are yet to be explored extensively. He has great interest in designing circularly polarized dielectric resonator antennas and MIMO antennas. He has published/presented several research articles in refereed journals and international conferences in the field of interest.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Circularly polarized V-shaped dielectric resonator antenna

Sumer S. Singhal^{1,5} | Binod K. Kanaujia²

¹Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun, India

²School of Computational and Integrative Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India

³Department of Computer Science Engineering, BTK Institute of Technology, Dwarahat, Uttarakhand, India

⁴Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Delhi, India

⁵Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, HMR Institute of Technology and Management, Delhi, India

Correspondence

Jugul Kishor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Delhi, India.
Email: er.jugulkishor@gmail.com

Abstract

In this article, a probe fed V-shaped dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) loaded with circular patches, is proposed for X band applications. A prototype was fabricated to validate the results. Circular polarization is achieved by the geometry of DRA integrated with the circular patches on its surface. These circular patches behave as a monopole antenna. To achieve circular polarization two orthogonal fields have been excited in the DRA, which are in time phase quadrature. Due to the symmetry of design, it shows dual polarization, both Left Hand Circular Polarization (LHCP) and Right Hand Circular Polarization (RHCP), in two orthogonal directions. The fabricated prototype exhibits wide impedance bandwidth of 7.85-10.1 GHz (25%) and circular polarization (CP) Bandwidth (BW) of 8.35-8.7 GHz (4%). Maximum measured gain of 4.8 dBi has been obtained in comparison with the simulated gain of 5.6 dBi. Applications of the proposed antenna include satellite communication, telemetry tracking and control, Synthetic aperture radar (SAR), weather radar, and military radar in X band. Directional CP performance is useful in designing a smart antenna and multiple input multiple output (MIMO) antenna.

KEYWORDS

directional circular polarization, DRA, smart antenna, X band, circularly polarized DRA, V shaped DRA.

1 | INTRODUCTION

The advent of efficient antennas has revolutionized the field of communication. In the pursuit of efficient antennas, in 1983, Long et al.^{1,2} proposed cylindrical and rectangular dielectric resonator antennas (DRA). In 1984, Long et al.³ presented hemispherical DRA. DRA is a relatively new concept of using dielectric material as antenna instead of metallic antennas, which were used previously. Nowadays, DRA antennas have been popular due to its various advantages over existing metallic antennas. Major advantages of DRA are wide impedance bandwidth as radiation area is more than compared to patch, low losses due to the dielectric body of the DRA, flexible excitation schemes as a number of options of excitation increases due to three-dimension body of the DRA, more design parameters (degree of freedom) and high radiation efficiency.⁴⁻⁷

Circular polarization is also a much-sought property in antennas for satellite communication and radar applications due to low polarization losses, ease in the alignment of the antenna and ability to combat multipath interference and fading. The benefits of circular polarization in mobile services and communication are explained in.^{8,9} Circular polarization can be achieved by single-feed, multi-feed and different DR shapes, however the mono feed method is easier and compact. Different feed methods already discussed in the literature refs. [4,5]. Initially, in the 1990s, basic geometrical shapes such as cylindrical and rectangular DRAs were studied at length.¹⁻⁷ Subsequently, different shapes of DRA were also analyzed such as trapezoidal,¹⁰ hexagonal,¹¹ ring,¹² and L-shaped¹³ to achieve circular polarization. Pan et al.¹⁰ discussed wideband circularly polarized trapezoidal DRA operating in 3-3.98 GHz band but, with a high volume of

16,800 mm³. V. Hamasakutty et al.¹¹ discussed hexagonal shape DRA operating in 3-3.475 GHz band with 15% CP bandwidth. Mongia et al. discussed several shapes of DR including spherical, ring, and so forth, in ref. [12]. Shen et al.¹³ discussed L-shaped DRA excited using Y-shaped microstrip line feed, operating in two bands with CP bandwidth 11.8-12.3 GHz and 14.3-14.8 GHz. In addition, the quest for wide circular polarization and impedance bandwidth with different DRA structure is still pursued.

In this article, V-shaped DRA is proposed for X band applications. A prototype of the proposed DRA is also fabricated to validate the results. Measured impedance bandwidth and measured axial ratio bandwidth (ARBW) of the proposed antenna are 25% (7.85-10.1 GHz) and 4% (8.35-8.7 GHz), respectively. This antenna can also be used in the MIMO antenna system and smart antenna array because of its directional circular polarization property. Proposed antenna operates in X band which has a plethora of applications as discussed in refs. [14,15] such as Radar and satellite communication. Smart beam steering antenna array is also one of the emerging applications in X band.

2 | ANTENNA DESIGN

2.1 | Antenna configurations

In this article, V-shaped DRA fed with the probe is proposed, as shown in Figure 1. It comprises Eccostock Hik bar having relative dielectric constant 10 and its effective permittivity varies from 9.8-7 with respect to height of DRA from 1-11 mm, calculated using Equation (4.29) of.¹⁶ The Eccostock bar has been molded in V-shape, a copper plate has been used as ground, two copper patches have been embedded on the surface of the DRA and a copper probe having diameter 1 mm has been used for feeding the structure. The schematic of the DRA is shown in Figure 2. Table 1 shows the dimensional details of the antenna. Antenna design steps are shown in Table 2.

FIGURE 1 Fabricated V-shaped DRA prototype

FIGURE 2 Geometry of proposed DRA. DRA, dielectric resonator antenna

TABLE 1 Design Parameters (in mm)

L	W	F	hdra	r1	PH	D	GW
17	11	6	11.1	4.85	7.4	44	100

In step-1, dimensions of the rectangular dielectric resonator antenna (RDRA) have been obtained using design Equations (2-5), as mentioned by Mongia et al.⁷ Approximate parameter values obtained from design equations were further optimized using high-frequency structural simulator (HFSS). The dimension of the RDRA-1 is $6 \times 17 \times 11.1$ mm³ which resonates at 9.6 GHz. In step-2, a V-shaped DRA is obtained by joining two RDRA and excited by a probe of diameter 1 mm at the center of the structure, as shown in Figure 3. In the next step, a circular patch is etched on one surface of the V-shaped DRA which results dual resonance at 8.75 and 9.65 GHz, as shown in the Figure 3. Second resonance is due to circular patch etched on the surface of the DRA, having diameter $1.1\lambda_0/4$, where λ_0 corresponds to free space wavelength at resonant frequency 8.65 GHz. In the fourth step,

TABLE 2 Antenna Design Steps

Steps	Design	Impedance BW	ARBW
Step-1- RDRA		7.7-10.2 GHz	-
Step-2- V-Shaped DRA		9.2-9.6 GHz	9.08-9.12 GHz
Step-3- V-Shaped DRA with a single circular patch		8.25-9.8 GHz	-
Step-4- V-Shaped DRA with two circular patches		7.8-10 GHz	8.44-8.86 GHz

Abbreviation: DRA, dielectric resonator antenna.

FIGURE 3 Comparison of simulated impedance bandwidth of different antennas as shown in Table 2

FIGURE 4 Comparison of simulated AR of different antennas as shown in Table 2. All Axial Ratios (ARs) are at $\theta = 50^\circ$ and $\phi = 50^\circ$

two circular patches are etched on both sides of the DRA. These circular patches fed by probe are equivalent to monopole antenna as discussed in.¹⁷ Consequently, the resonance frequency of the DRA shifts from 8.65 to 8.1 GHz. Figure 3 shows the comparison of simulated impedance bandwidths in all the steps explained above.

From the observation of the Figure 3, it is concluded that impedance bandwidth in step-1 is wide enough but ARBW is null. Step-2 aims to design a DRA with wide impedance bandwidth as well as pleasing ARBW. In this step, due to even symmetry in V-shape along the joint, DRA exhibits directional circular polarization. It shows Right Hand Circular Polarization (RHCP) at $\phi = 50^\circ$ direction and Left Hand Circular Polarization (LHCP) at $\phi = -50^\circ$ direction. But the ARBW is still narrow, from 9.08 to 9.12 GHz (40 MHz), as shown in Figure 4. To increase ARBW, in step 3 a circular patch was etched on one side of DRA which still results in diminished circular polarization due to asymmetrical structure. In step-4, ARBW has been increased from 40 to 420 MHz by embedding two circular patches on both sides of the DRA, as depicted in Figure 4. Figure 5 shows simulated Axial Ratio (AR) for different elevation angles in coarser and finer views, respectively. It is noticed that the minimum AR frequency point shifts wr.t. the elevation angle. Therefore, circular polarization is stronger at $\phi = \pm 50^\circ$ and $45^\circ < \theta < 55^\circ$.

Figure 6 shows the comparison between gain (LHCP and RHCP) and axial ratios simulated for $\phi = \pm 50^\circ$ direction. Due to the symmetry of proposed antenna, gain (LHCP) at $\phi = -50^\circ$ and gain (RHCP) at $\phi = 50^\circ$ have approximately same values, gain (RHCP) at $\phi = -50^\circ$ and gain (LHCP) at $\phi = 50^\circ$ have also approximately same values. Simulated axial ratios in $\phi = \pm 50^\circ$ directions are also nearly same. Figure 7 shows 3D radiation pattern plotted in XY plane and directions of circular polarization wave radiation with respect to antenna placement.

FIGURE 5 Simulated Axial Ratio vs frequency variation for different values of elevation angle (θ) with a constant azimuth angle ($\phi = 50^\circ$)

FIGURE 6 Simulated Gain (LHCP and RHCP) and AR graphs in $\phi = \pm 50^\circ$ and $\theta = 50^\circ$ direction

FIGURE 7 Three-dimensional radiation pattern in XY Plane showing the direction of RHCP and LHCP radiation at 8.65 GHz

FIGURE 8 Simulated S_{11} and AR against frequency for different heights of DRA. AR is at $\theta = 50^\circ$ and $\phi = 50^\circ$ (A) S_{11} (B) AR. DRA, dielectric resonator antenna

Similarly, simulated impedance bandwidth and ARBW of the proposed design are 7.8–10 GHz (24%) and 8.44–8.86 GHz (5%) respectively, as shown in Figures 3 and 4. The Proposed DRA exhibits gain from 2.5 to 5 dB and good AR bandwidth in the range $45^\circ < \theta < 55^\circ$ at $\phi = \pm 50^\circ$. Therefore, the proposed antenna demonstrates directional CP which can be used in smart beam steering antenna array system.

2.2 | Effect of height of DRA

The height of any antenna plays a major role in its radiation properties. In case of DRA, bandwidth and mode degeneracy can be controlled by proper choice of resonator dimensions.⁵ When the height of DRA varied it is observed that resonant frequency due to DRA also varied. To study the effect of the height of the proposed DRA, the design was simulated for four heights viz. 10, 11, 12, and 13 mm. S-parameters and axial ratio graphs are shown in Figure 8 for various heights. The resonant frequencies and ARBW at various heights are tabulated in Table 3.

Alteration in surface current distribution and field distribution along the surface can be subtly observed due to the variation in the height of DRA. The orthogonal fields must have equal magnitude and must be in time phase quadrature for exciting circular polarization. Circular polarization depends on how effectively fields cross each other orthogonally. Therefore, it is observed that when the height of DRA is 10 mm, circularly polarization is maximum but has poor impedance matching which can be improved by increasing the height of DRA to 11.1 mm.

However, the circular polarization is reduced a little but an improved impedance matching along the band is observed. Circular polarization further diminishes at 12 and 13 mm heights. Henceforth, circular polarization and impedance bandwidth are achieved at the optimized height of 11.1 mm, after observing its effects on different parameters.

2.3 | Effect of the radius of circular patch

Circular patch antennas can behave as a monopole antenna when etched on the surface of the dielectric substrate. Radiation properties of the monopole antenna change with respect to surface area and shape of the patch.¹⁷ To study the effect of a change in surface area and size of the circular patch on radiation properties of DRA, the proposed antenna was simulated for different radii of the patch. Figure 9 shows the variation of S_{11} and axial ratio against frequency for different radii of the patch. For radii less than 4 mm it has been found that excitation probe does not directly feed the circular patch, instead the energy has been coupled electromagnetically with the circular patch. Due to this, poor impedance bandwidth has been observed for radii less than 4 mm, as shown in the Figure 9A.

TABLE 3 Resonant frequencies at various heights of DRA

Height of DRA (in mm)	Resonant frequency (in GHz)	ARBW (in GHz)
10	9.7	8.12–8.22, 8.52–9.1
11	8.1 and 9.7	8.4–8.82
12	8.25 and 9.5	8.45–8.65
13	8.25 and 9.3	-

Abbreviations: ARBW, axial ratio bandwidth; DRA, dielectric resonator antenna.

FIGURE 9 Simulated S_{11} and AR against frequency for different radius of patches etched on surfaces of DRA. AR is at $\theta = 50^\circ$ and $\phi = 50^\circ$ (A) S_{11} (B) AR. DRA, dielectric resonator antenna

The resonant frequencies and ARBW at various radii are also tabulated in Table 4.

The resonance at 8.1 GHz is due to patch whose diameter corresponds to $\lambda_0/4$, where λ_0 is free space wavelength corresponding to resonant frequency. Table 4 shows the

increase in patch radius improves impedance bandwidth. Henceforth, circular polarization and impedance bandwidth are achieved at the optimized radius of 4.85 mm, after observing its effects on different parameters.

3 | CHARACTERIZATION AND RESULT VALIDATION

The performance characteristics of the proposed DRA have been analyzed, investigated, and optimized by utilizing HFSS. A prototype of V-shaped DRA is fabricated with Eccostock HiK dielectric bar ($\epsilon_r = 10$) as shown in Figure 1. The circular patch was cut down manually by using copper foil tape of thickness 0.07 mm. Manual cutting with precise dimension is difficult at such a small scale. Therefore, measurement was done using a circular patch on both sides having radius around 4.8 mm as shown in Figure 1. This approximation of radius and manual fabrication results in concomitant imperfections, which are slight dislocation of the circular patch on the DRA surface, soldering deformity and deposits, and adhesive applied for placing the DRA on the copper plate. These limitations produce variation in simulated and measured results, which can be minimized in commercial fabrication. Figure 10

TABLE 4 Resonant frequencies at various radii of Patch

Radius of patch (in mm)	Resonant frequency (in GHz)	ARBW (in GHz)
3	7.7	8.5-8.95
3.5	7.5	7.95-8.75
4	8.3	7.65-8.3
4.5	8.2 and 9.9	7.75-7.95
4.85	8.1 and 9.6	8.44-8.86
5	8 and 9.3	8.55-8.95

Abbreviation: ARBW, axial ratio bandwidth.

FIGURE 10 Comparison of simulated and measured results (A) S_{11} (B) AR of the DRA in $\theta = 50^\circ$ and $\varphi = 50^\circ$ direction. DRA, dielectric resonator antenna

shows the comparison between simulated and measured results of impedance bandwidth and axial ratio. Simulated and measured impedance bandwidths of proposed DRA are 24% (7.8-10 GHz) and 25% (7.85-10.1 GHz), respectively. Simulated and measured ARBWs of proposed DRA are 5% (8.44-8.86 GHz) and 4% (8.35-8.7 GHz), respectively. Measured results show agreement with simulated results with some variations due to manufacturing deformities. Figure 11 shows simulated and measured gain and simulated radiation efficiency of proposed DRA at $\theta = 50^\circ$ and $\varphi = 50^\circ$. Maximum radiation efficiency is 94.5% and the maximum measured gain is 4.8 dBi in comparison to maximum simulated gain 5.6 dBi. Measured gain is less than simulated gain because of experimental approximations and fabrication deformities.

Figure 12 shows the radiation pattern at 9.6 GHz. The antenna exhibits linear polarization at 9.6 GHz. Figure 13 shows gain (LHCP and RHCP) radiation pattern at 8.65 GHz. The antenna exhibits circular polarization at 8.65 GHz.

FIGURE 11 Simulated gain, measured gain and radiation efficiency at $\theta = 50^\circ$ and $\varphi = 50^\circ$ of proposed V-shaped DRA. DRA, dielectric resonator antenna

FIGURE 12 Measured and simulated radiation pattern of the proposed DRA at 9.6 GHz frequency. DRA, dielectric resonator antenna

FIGURE 13 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of the proposed DRA at 8.65 GHz and $\varphi = 50^\circ$ for circular polarization. DRA, dielectric resonator antenna

Table 5 displays a comparison of proposed V-shaped DRA with recent circularly polarized DRAs operating in X band. Shen et al.¹³ achieved 14% and 9.6% impedance bandwidth

with 4% and 3% AR bandwidth using L-shaped DRA. Dash et al.¹⁸ proposed dual-band circularly polarized triangular DRA with narrow AR bandwidth and low gain. Fakhte et al.¹⁹ achieved high AR bandwidth of 6% using four stacked rotated rectangular DRAs. Kishk et al.²⁰ discussed elliptical DRA with 14% impedance bandwidth and 3.5% AR bandwidth. In comparison to these recent DRAs operating in X band, proposed fabricated DRA exhibits wide impedance bandwidth (25%) and pleasing AR bandwidth (4%).

An anechoic chamber is the most widely used electromagnetic measurement system. The results of the proposed antenna prototype have been measured in a rectangular shaped anechoic measurement chamber. A horn antenna has been used as a reference antenna. The measuring antenna is placed in line with the reference antenna. The photograph of the anechoic measurement chamber is shown in Figure 14. Two-antenna method has been used to measure the axial ratio as explained in refs. [21,22]. Receiving antenna is placed at Fraunhofer region in respect to the frequency of interest, from the transmitting antenna, which is a fabricated prototype in this case. Anritsu vector network analyzer (MS2038C) that ranges up to 20 GHz has been used to measure S-parameters of the prototype.

TABLE 5 Comparison with recent DRAs operating in X band

Ref.	DRA Shape	BW(%)	ARBW(%)	Gain(dBi)	Frequency (GHz)	Feed Type
13	L-shaped	149.6	43.4	-	11.9-13.7 14.9-16.4	Y shape Microstrip feed line
18	Triangular	12.37, 4.8	1.6, 1.8	2.15, 3.69	7.5, 8.7	Probe feed
19	Rectangular	21	6	6.5	10	Aperture Coupled
20	Elliptical	14	3.5	-	9.4	Probe
Proposed	V-shaped	25	4	4.8	8.65GHz	Probe

Abbreviations: ARBW, axial ratio bandwidth; DRA, dielectric resonator antenna.

FIGURE 14 Measurement setup in an anechoic chamber

FIGURE 15 Simulated surface current at 8.65 GHz at different phase angles (0, 90, 180, and 270°)

Surface current movement at the surface of DRA is shown in Figure 15, at different phase angles 0, 90, 180, and 270°. It shows RHCP movements of the current vector on DRA surface.

4 | CONCLUSION

A wideband circularly polarized V-shaped DRA is presented in this article. The maximum gain of the antenna is 4.8 dBi measured and 5.6 dBi simulated with pleasing circular polarization bandwidth of 8.35–8.7 GHz. The antenna operates in 7.85–10.1 GHz band which lies in X band. The proposed antenna is equipped with various advantages like its compact design with the height of just 11 mm and volume 1848 mm³ with acceptable circular polarization and impedance bandwidth. The DRA falls in the category of the deserving candidate to be validated as compact design for it exhibits a directional circular polarization and a better average gain.

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ORCID

Binod K. Kanaujia <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7849-5299>

Jugul Kishor <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1108-998X>

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Sumer S. Singhwai did Bachelor of Engineering in 2003 and Master in Engineering in 2012 from Birla Institute of Technology Mesra Ranchi. He is currently pursuing PhD from Uttarkhand Technical University, Dehradun. He has interest in Dielectric resonator antennas, MIMO antenna, patch antennas, and so forth. He has published papers in refereed journals.

Binod K. Kanaujia is working as a Professor in the School of Computational and Integrative sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi since August 2016. Before joining Jawaharlal Nehru University, he had been in the Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering in Ambedkar Institute of Advanced Communication Technologies & Research (formerly Ambedkar Institute of Technology), Delhi as a Professor

since February 2011 and Associate Professor (2008-2011). Dr. Kanaujia held the positions of Lecturer (1996-2005) and Reader (2005-2008) in the Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering, and as the Head of the Department in the M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, India. Prior to his career in academics, Dr. Kanaujia had worked as an Executive Engineer in the R&D division of M/s UPTRON India Ltd. Dr. Kanaujia had completed his BTech degree in Electronics Engineering from KNIT Sultanpur, India in 1994. He did his MTech and PhD in 1998 and 2004; respectively, from the Department of Electronics Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India. He has been awarded Junior Research Fellowship by UGC Delhi in the year 2001-2002 for his outstanding work in electronics field. Dr. Kanaujia has keen research interest in design and modeling of microstrip antenna, dielectric resonator antenna, left-handed Metamaterial microstrip antenna, shorted microstrip antenna, ultra wideband antennas, reconfigurable and circular polarized antenna for wireless communication. He has been credited to publish more than 150 research papers with more than 430 citations with h-index of 12 in peer-reviewed journals and conferences. He had supervised 50 MTech and 08 PhD research scholars in the field of microwave engineering. Dr. Kanaujia is a reviewer of several journals of international repute, that is, IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation, IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters, Wireless Personal Communications, Journal of Electromagnetic Wave and Application, Indian Journal of Radio and Space Physics, IETE Technical Review, International Journal of Electronics, International Journal of Engineering Science, IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, AEU-International Journal of Electronics and Communication, International Journal of Microwave and Wireless Technologies, and so forth. Dr. Kanaujia had successfully executed four research projects sponsored by several agencies of Government of India, that is, DRDO, DST, AICTE, and ISRO. He is also a member of several academic and professional bodies, that is, IEEE, Institution of Engineers (India), Indian Society for Technical Education, and The Institute of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineers of India.

Ajit Singh is working as Associate Professor in B. T. Kumaon Institute of Technology, Dwarahat, Almora, Uttarakhand, India. He did his MTech in 2003 from Netaji Subhas Institute of Technology, New Delhi and PhD in 2012 from Singhanian University, Rajasthan. He has published several papers in refereed journals.

Jugul Kishor is working as Assistant Professor, in Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, National Institute of Technology, New Delhi. Dr. Kishor had completed his BTech degree in Electronics Engineering from KNIT Sultanpur, India in 2002. He did his M. Tech in 2008 from University of Delhi and PhD in 2017 from Indian Institute of Technology (Indian school of Mines), Dhanbad. His recent research interest activities have focused on the design and development of microwave passive components,

dielectric resonator filters, antennas and metamaterial. He has been credited to publish more than 35 papers with various reputed International journals and conferences with citation and h-index.

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Sumner Singh
Singhwal

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Novel circularly polarized dielectric resonator antenna for microwave image sensing application

Sumer Singh Singhwal¹ |
Binod Kumar Kanaujia² | Ajit Singh³ |
Jugul Kishor⁴

¹Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India

²School of Computational and Integrative Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India

³BTK Institute of Technology, Dwarahat, Uttarakhand, India

⁴Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Delhi, India

Correspondence

Jugul Kishor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Delhi, India.
Email: jugulkishor@gmail.com

Abstract

In this article, a novel, simple, and compact structure of dielectric resonator antenna is proposed, which provides wide bandwidth across proposed mm wave band for microwave image sensing with considerable gain using a lossy FR-4 epoxy substrate and thick FR4 as DRA. A DR can be excited using four-line feed using a circular loop type feed network. These line feeds maintain phase difference of 90° to produce CP. This antenna provides approximate constant gain of 8.6 dB on 25–26 GHz band and 3 dB axial ratio bandwidth is almost 1 GHz from 25.2 to 26.2 GHz, Impedance bandwidth of the proposed antenna is 3 GHz (24–27 GHz). This antenna can be used in microwave image sensing and wearable sensors applications, due to its compactness ($30 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$), in mm wave band.

KEYWORDS

circular polarization, microwave image sensing, mm wave, rectangular DRA

1 | INTRODUCTION

In today's time simplicity, ease of design, and cost of antenna are paramount factors which should be backed by admirable performance, so that production cost of antenna is less and quality of reception using antenna is commendable. Antennas as a sensor have advantage of passive operation, low profile, small size, multiplexing capability compatibility with dielectric substrate, etc. Antennas have flexibility of dual function of communication and sensing. Therefore, an antenna for sensing application required minimum number of components. These features discussed above make antenna sensor as a vital tool in sensing application. A scheme of antenna integration with electronics circuits such as processing, conditioning, and biasing circuits are shown in Refs. 1, 2. A different type of antenna as a sensing element is demonstrated in Ref. 3. They are used for the measurement of the various physical parameters. This chapter basically covers operational features and interrogation of battery less antenna sensor. Microwaves are now also used for a near field microwave image sensing in breast cancer detection.⁴ With the advent of more compact antennas are increasing its application in microwave sensors is also observed in astronomy, remote sensing, medical imaging and wide array of scientific and medical application. At mm wave band many researchers proposed antenna for image sensing application by using different design methodology. In Ref. 5 Park et al., proposed tilted beam antenna at 28 GHz with beam scanning capability using waveguide WR28 for feeding antenna. In Ref. 6 Philip Ayiku Dzagbletey et al., proposed stacked 1×7 microstrip linear antenna array at 28 GHz for 5G using Taconic TLY-5 substrate with 14.7 dBi gain at resonant frequency. In Ref. 7 Hamberger et al., proposed Beamforming antenna array (1×10) having 15 dBi gain and 1 GHz impedance bandwidth using RO4350B substrate material. In Ref. 8 Mao et al., reported 4×4 array for 5G communication using double substrate material which are RO 4003C and RO 5880. In Ref. 9 Haraz et al., proposed patch antenna using EBG Ground Structure and Dielectric Superstrate at 28GHz using RT5880 substrate material. Researchers are motivated to find sensor applications in mm wave band so that in future 5G communications can be well equipped with microwave sensors. Wearable sensor is another challenge because it requires compact size and light weight sensors.

Dielectric resonator are widely used in present times due to their advantages of low metallic losses, wide bandwidth, low dielectric losses, high gain, and easy to achieve circular

FIGURE 1 Simulated and fabricated antenna prototype [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

polarization (CP) at higher modes. CP antennas are always preferred over their linear polarized counterparts because of less multipath fading, ease of receiving of signals and less polarization losses. In Ref. 10 Chauhan et al., proposed cylindrical DRA for wireless sensor applications using Rogers RO3210 which gives 3.6 dB gain at resonant frequency 6.7 GHz and peak gain of 6.8 dB in operating band. Dash et al.,¹¹ proposed a triangular dielectric resonator antenna by using spiral fed for remote sensing application with gain 2.15 and 3.69 dBi.

Rectangular DRA is easy to fabricate in comparison to cylindrical DRA which is widely discussed in literature because of different mathematical interpretation given by researchers.^{12,13} Major theoretical study on DRA is on dielectric resonator having permittivity $\epsilon_r > 10$ because of various advantages of high permittivity resonator, such as good coupling, large storage of energy etc. In Ref. 14 Pan et al., compared performances of low permittivity DRA ($\epsilon_r = 5$) with high permittivity DRA ($\epsilon_r = 10$) and authors concluded that a lower permittivity DRA is recommendable for increasing the bandwidth of the DRA but size of DRA is also increased then and mode excitation in low permittivity DRA is also tough.

Our proposed DRA structure consists of a conventional FR-4 substrate as a DR and a circular loop with four feeds. The circular ring microstrip line with four feeds is used to excite TE_{116} mode in the DR. Major achievements of this project are simple design (no slot or probe feed is used), small size, and low cost. The proposed DRA is working in 24–27 GHz frequency band exhibit flat gain around 8.6 dBi and 3 dB AR bandwidth of approximately 1 GHz. Figure 1 shows simulated and fabricated DRA. Antenna Design was simulated using HFSS software and mathematical equations are computed using MATLAB software.

2 | DESIGN OF THE PROPOSED DRA

Figure 1 shows the layout of the proposed DRA antenna and its prototype. Figure 2 shows, the dimensional details of the proposed DRA. The proposed DRA consist of a circular loop

with four feeds printed on a FR-4 substrate having $\epsilon_r = 4.4$, $h = 0.8$ mm, $\tan\delta = 0.02$. An FR-4 substrate having dimension 5.85 mm $\times$ 5.85 mm is utilized as a DR ($\epsilon_r = 4.4$, $h_{dra} = 4.8$ mm, $\tan\delta \approx 0.02$) is placed on the DR such that it

FIGURE 2 Layout of proposed design with parameters $w = 1.93$ mm, $R1 = 12.29$ mm, $R2 = R1 - w$, $h = 0.8$ mm, $w_{sub} = 30$ mm, $L_f = 2.8$ mm, $s = 1.645$ mm, $L1 = 10.5$ mm

FIGURE 3 Design steps of antenna [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

FIGURE 4 Magnetic field distribution on DRA on y-z plane at 25.6 GHz: A, Magnitude; B, Vector; and C, Theoretical [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

can cover four feed lines symmetrically. Width of circular ring microstrip line is calculated by using design equations given in Ref. 15.

2.1 | Design of the DR

Mongia and Ittipiboon¹⁶ studied DRA for dielectric constant ranging from 10 to 100. However, we have used the Equations 1-4^{12,14} for the calculation of the dimension

$$k_x = \frac{\pi}{a} ; k_y = \frac{\pi}{b} \tag{1}$$

$$k_z \tan(k_z d/2) = \sqrt{(\epsilon_r - 1) k_0^2 - k_z^2} \tag{2}$$

$$k_x^2 + k_y^2 + k_z^2 = \epsilon_r k_0^2 \tag{3}$$

$$k_0 = \frac{2\pi f_0}{c} \tag{4}$$

FIGURE 5 Reflection coefficient (dB) vs frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of loop radius with fixed height of DRA of 4.8 mm [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

FIGURE 6 Gain (dB) vs frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of loop radius with fixed height of DRA of 4.8 mm [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

FIGURE 7 Axial ratio (dB) vs frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of loop radius with fixed height of DRA of 4.8 mm [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

where, k_x, k_y, k_z denotes wavenumbers along x, y, z directions, respectively. k_0 denotes free space wavenumber corresponding to resonant frequency f_0 . By using MATLAB we obtain two values of the square DRA, which can satisfy Equations 1-4, which are $5.62 \text{ mm} \times 5.62 \text{ mm} \times 1.6$ and $4.34 \text{ mm} \times 4.34 \text{ mm} \times 4.8 \text{ mm}$, respectively, at frequency of interest. When designing a DRA by using these dimensions it did not resonated at the desired frequency. It was because of low dielectric constant DR material. So, the parametric analysis is performed to find out new dimension of the DRA which operated at desired frequency. After optimization, new dimension of the DRA is $5.85 \text{ mm} \times 5.85 \text{ mm} \times 4.8 \text{ mm}$ operation at 25.5 GHz which is chosen as middle value of targeted band 24-27 GHz.

2.2 | Operating principle of the DRA

For the analysis of the proposed DRA, design, and development of the DRA are divided in to two part, part one describes describe about feed network and part two explains about working of the DRA.

2.2.1 | Part 1

Figure 2 shows the proposed configuration of the feed networks. Design steps are shown in Figure 3. First step is

TABLE 1 Summary of parametric effects of loop radius

Radius of loop (mm)	Impedance bandwidth (GHz)	Resonant frequency (GHz)	Reflection coefficient (dB)	Peak gain (dB)	AR bandwidth (GHz)
11	24-27	25	-16	6.2	-
12	24-27	25	-25	8.2 (Flat gain)	-
12.29	24-27	24.9	-28	8.6 (Flat gain)	25.2-26.2
13	24-26	25	-42	6.8	-

FIGURE 8 Reflection coefficient (dB) vs frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of height of DRA with loop radius of 12.29 mm [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

FIGURE 9 Gain (dB) vs frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of height of DRA with fixed loop radius of 12.29 mm [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

shifted microstrip feed to excite DRA but it was unable to excite modes in DRA. In second step, four strips are used to excite modes in DRA which works good but isolation of all four feeds was very poor. In third step, a circular feed loop is added so that single feed can achieve the results. All the

FIGURE 10 Axial ratio (dB) vs frequency (GHz) for parametric variation of height of DRA with fixed loop radius of 12.29 mm [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

four strips are at equal distance on the circumference of the circular loop so that a 90° phase difference should be maintained between any two strips. So, when a signal applied to the feed, all four feeds experience current quadrature phase difference with each other.

2.2.2 | Part 2

A rectangular DRA placed centrally over the feed network. The DRA is coupled with four strip which have provided excitation of the rectangular DRA, which led the rectangular DRA to resonate at 25.6 GHz. interestingly, this circular loop setup provides excitation to the rectangular DRA with 90° phase difference hence provide circular polarization.

The excitation of different mode in rectangular DRA depends upon feed mechanism. Here, the rectangular DRA is excited by using four strips. Rectangular DRA produce pure modes when excited in isolated condition but grounded DRA with four sequential feeds with single main feed, excites DRA asymmetrically, which gave $TE_{11\delta}$ mode which is confirmed by magnetic field distribution, as shown in Figure 4A,B, as explained in Ref. 17. It is also confirmed from Figure 4C, which were defined by Ref. 16 for $TE_{11\delta}$.

It was worth mentioning that radius of circular loop also participate in performance of DRA. We optimized the circular loop radius for best impedance matching, wide axial ratio (AR) bandwidth, and commendable gain throughout band.

TABLE 2 Summary of parametric effects of height of DRA

Height of DRA (mm)	Impedance bandwidth (GHz)	Resonant frequency (GHz)	Reflection coefficient (dB)	Peak gain (dB)	AR bandwidth (GHz)
1.6	24-27	26.3	-12	2	-
3.2	24-27	26.3	-18	8.55	-
4.8	24-27	24.9	-28	8.6 (Flat gain)	25.2-26.2
6.4	24-27	26.2	-22	7.6	-

FIGURE 11 Reflection coefficient (dB) vs frequency (GHz) comparison between simulated and measured results [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

3 | PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS

Various dimensions have been analyzed to get broad impedance bandwidth with good stable gain. To understand behavior of design parameters, a parametric analysis is studied. It was studied while doing analysis that radius of circular loop (R_1) and height of DRA (h_{dra}) affects the results of proposed antenna in terms of gain and bandwidth.

3.1 | Effect of radius of loop

First parametric analysis was implemented for studying effect of radius of loop. Parameters observed are reflection coefficient, gain and axial ratio which are shown in Figures 5–7. It was observed that reflection coefficient is achieved less than -10 dB for all variation of loop radius and gain also varies with respect to loop radius. Gain is maximum for loop radius of 12.29 mm. Table 1 summarizes all the finding of parametric analysis for effect of loop radius. It is clearly visible from Table 1 that AR bandwidth is achieved only for the case of radius 12.29 mm and also flat gain around 8.6 dB is achieved for this optimized radius of loop.

3.2 | Effect of height of DRA

Second parametric analysis is studied for height of DRA which is taken multiple of 1.6 mm as it is easily available commercially. Variation of standard parameters like reflection

FIGURE 12 Axial ratio (dB) vs frequency (GHz) comparison between simulated and measured results [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

coefficient, gain, and axial ratio with respect to change in height of DRA is shown in Figures 8–10. It was analyzed from Figures 8–10 that reflection coefficient achieved at 24.9 GHz frequency is -28 dB for height of DRA 4.8 mm and as we increase or decrease height reflection coefficient at resonant frequency increases. Major observation is that gain becomes stable for 4.8 mm height for 24.5–26.5 GHz band. Next performance parameter which confirms our proposed height is axial ratio bandwidth. Axial ratio bandwidth of approximately 1 GHz is achieved centered around resonant frequency 25.6 GHz for 4.8 mm height. Table 2 summarizes all the findings of parametric study of effect of height of DRA.

It can be concluded from both parametric analysis that our choice of taking height of DRA and radius of loop is justified to achieve circular polarization, wide impedance bandwidth and high stable gain all over the band of interest.

FIGURE 14 Gain (dB), reflection coefficient (dB) vs frequency (GHz) plot showing circular polarization window from 25.2–26.2 GHz [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

4 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, validation of proposed rectangular DRA is discussed. A prototype antenna based on the FR-4 DR is fabricated, which is shown in the Figure 1. Agilent N5230A vector network analyzer is used to measure impedance bandwidth of the fabricated antenna (Figure 11). Figure 6A shows, the simulated and measured S_{11} of the rectangular DRA. It can be observed that measured and simulated impedance bandwidth cover the 24–27 GHz frequency band. Similarly, 3 dB AR bandwidth of 1 GHz (25.2–26.2 GHz) is achieved, as shown in the Figure 12. A close agreement can be observed between 3-dB axial ratio bandwidth of measured and simulated plots.

The measured and simulated radiation pattern in broadside direction is plotted in the Figure 13. From the radiation pattern half power beamwidth of 70° and Front to Back ratio of 16.9 dB is calculated. Our prototype agrees with measured results with some deviation due to fabrication constraints at

FIGURE 13 Simulated and measured Co-Pol and X-Pol radiation pattern at 25.6 GHz (A) E plane (B) H plane [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

noncommercial level. Our proposed DRA also supports linear polarization in UWB from 22.5 to 27 GHz with peak gain of 8.6 dB. Figure 14 demonstrates linear polarization and circular polarization bandwidth. It shows gain and reflection coefficient variation with respect to frequency. Area covered by red rectangle with bandwidth 25.2–26.2 GHz covers circular polarization with high gain but remaining band from 22.5 to 27 GHz have variable gain and may be used for broad bandwidth applications. When transmitters and receivers are static or fixed then linear polarization is also preferred depending upon the application. In microwave sensing application often sensors may be fixed at certain position such as in satellites, mobile communication.

5 | CONCLUSION

Presently only high permittivity DR are used due to multiple advantages. In microwave image sensing, cost is an important factor to consider because a sensor is always followed by signal processing circuitry, so overall cost of the system will be increased. For the microwave image sensing application, the gain of the device should be high and stable. The proposed DRA fulfill all the basic condition of the sensor. Proposed DRA can offer wide impedance bandwidth and AR bandwidth which is also desirable feather of the sensor.

So, to reduce overall cost of system and improve performance, proposed prototype can be a good choice for image sensing applications at mm wave band such as satellite communication applications, 5G communications,¹⁸ etc. CEPT documentation available on Ref. 19 concludes that 24.5–27.5 GHz band is good candidate for 5G communication and harmonization is possible on this band all over the globe. According to Ref. 20, 28 GHz band is proposed for Earth Stations in Motion (ESIM) remote sensing and International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT) standards which are relevant to microwave remote sensing. Our proposed antenna covers this band and can be used as an image sensor in IMT standards and ESIM remote sensing applications. It is very small size comparable to wrist watch dial and DRA height 0.48 cm, so it can also be used in wearable body sensors in mm wave band. Due to its low cost commercial scalability is also possible.

ORCID

Jugul Kishor <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1108-998X>

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Multiple input multiple output dielectric resonator antenna with circular polarized adaptability for 5G applications

S. S. Singhwal^{a,b}, B. K. Kanaujia^c, A. Singh^d, J. Kishor^e and L. Matekovits^f

^aDepartment of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun, India; ^bDepartment of Electronics and Communication Engineering, HMR Institute of Technology and Management, Delhi, India; ^cSchool of Computational and Integrative Science, Jawaharlal Nehru University, Delhi, India; ^dDepartment of Computer Science and Engineering, B.T.K. Institute of Technology, Dwarahat, Uttarakhand, India; ^eDepartment of Electronics and Communication Engineering, JIMS Engineering Management Technical Campus Greater Noida, India; ^fDipartimento di Elettronica e Telecomunicazioni, Politecnico di Torino, Torino, Italy

ABSTRACT

In this paper, the concept of the circularly polarized agile, multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) structure for fifth generation (5G) new radio application in mobile terminal is presented. Two prototypes have been fabricated, namely one with cylindrical DRA (CDRA) referred as A1 and a second one with ring DRA (RDRA) named as A2. These practical realizations of dual-port MIMO antennas have been mounted on a Rogers 5870 substrate of octagonal shape with proper ground architecture. The proposed dual-port MIMO antennas have been excited with conformal probes and L-type feed network aiming to achieve circular polarization (CP). Measured impedance bandwidth of A1 and A2 are 21.2% (3.15–3.9 GHz) and 22.2% (3.12–3.9 GHz), respectively. Moreover, for both antennas low mutual coupling between ports with minimum isolation of –20 dB over entire impedance bandwidth has been obtained by using triangular head slots in the ground plane. Measured axial ratio bandwidths in broadside direction ($\theta = 0$) are 5.66% (3.26–3.45 GHz) and 4.25% (3.45–3.6 GHz), respectively. Maximum gains are 7.3 and 7.2 dBi, in that order. MIMO antenna parameters such as envelope correction coefficient, diversity gain (DG), mean effective gain and total active reflection coefficient are also calculated to verify MIMO performance parameters. The proposed antennas also demonstrate CP agility with insertion of concentric cylindrical shells of different radii.

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1. Introduction

The fifth-generation (5G) wireless communication system can provide many advantages such as high capacity, higher data rate, and shorter latency. One of the promising 5G frequency band for wireless communication has been proposed around 3.5 GHz also known as sub-6 GHz band and mid-band (1–6 GHz) [1–3]. This mid-band spectrum will be more

CONTACT L. Matekovits ladislau.matekovits@polito.it

diverse and scarce, therefore capacity enhancement can be achieved by means of spectral efficiency. In order to meet these requirements multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technology has been deployed for 5G wireless operations. Applications of MIMO antenna in transmit/receive systems help passing through the previous limit of single antenna proposed by Shannon [4,5]. MIMO antennas have now become synonymous with high-speed wireless communication technology such as long-term evolution (LTE), wireless local area network (WLAN), Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMAX) and 5G communications. MIMO technology improves channel capacity, link reliability in multipath propagation and assures higher transfer data rates in wireless communication [6–8]. Initially, the MIMO antenna was proposed and implemented using microstrip patch antenna technology, until Ishmiya et al. [9,10] recommended a solution making use of dielectric resonator (DRA) for 802.11n applications. It paved the way for different DRA-based MIMO designs. It is observed that polarization diversity is often implemented by a dual-polarized antenna by using linear polarizations (LP). From [9–31] all the DRA-based MIMO antennas were LP examples. In comparison to LP antennas, circular polarization (CP) antennas demonstrate several advantages such as effectiveness in combating multipath interference and robustness during polarization mismatching. Due to these reasons, CP antennas constantly receive signal strength, which is a very useful property in wireless communication where the receiver antenna frequently changes its location with respect to the transmitter antenna [32]. The DRA-based CP MIMO antenna is a recent area of research, so very few research articles [28–38] are published in this domain. Johnstone et al. presented an eight-port CDRA for the MIMO system with different polarization states (LHCP, RHCP, and LP) [33]. However, different polarizations were achieved using various combinations of phased input at eight ports and isolation between ports was also refrained from discussion. Sahu et al. presented triple band MIMO DRA with gain 1.5, 4.2 and 2.3 dBi, but achieved CP only in one of the bands [34]. The same group also proposed a DRA-based CP MIMO antenna for WLAN applications (5.2 GHz) [35]. Though, it suffered from low impedance bandwidth (simulated 10.28%) and minimum isolation of around -14 dB. In [36], two self-complementary L-shaped DRAs were used in CP MIMO DRA. Here, isolation has been achieved by two self-complementary slots cut in the ground plane. In [37], two cylindrical DRAs have been used in the CP MIMO antenna using defected ground substrate (DGS) but measured axial radio bandwidth (ARBW) is not reported. In [38], two rectangular DRAs have been used with optimized conformal patch structure to excite it to yield a circularly polarized MIMO antenna. Isolation between elements is proposed using parasitic patch and diagonally positioned DRAs in [38]. In [39], two diagonal edge cut DRAs are excited by cross ring slot and Electromagnetic Band Gap (EBG) cells are used to enhance isolation. However, performance of this antenna is good but it suffers from design complexity. The literature review revealed the fact that research area of the CP dielectric resonator-based MIMO antenna is still in the nurturing phase and lot of scope of improvement is required in this field.

This article proposes the concept of CP agility in DRA-based MIMO antennas. Here, CP bandwidth can be controlled by inserting different cylindrical shells of different radii into the ring DRA. It is notable that minimum AR frequency has been varied comfortably without much variation in 10 dB impedance bandwidth. In particular, two dual-port DRA-based CP agile MIMO antennas are proposed for 5G communications at 3.5 GHz. Major advantages of the discussed design are (i) controllable CP, (ii) compactness in comparison to recent MIMO DRAs operating in the same band, (iii) simple isolation mechanism and (iv) simple RDRA

used instead of some complex structured DRA. The two prototypes have been fabricated and measured results have been compared with simulated data obtained from ANSYS FEM-based high-frequency structural simulator (HFSS). Measured impedance bandwidths of A1 (with CDRA, for details see below) and A2 (with RDRA) are 21.2% (3.15–3.9 GHz) and 22.2% (3.12–3.9 GHz), respectively. The measured ARBW of A1 and A2 are 5.66% (3.26–3.45 GHz) and 4.25% (3.45–3.6 GHz) in the broadside direction ($\theta = 0$). Isolation between ports is better than -20 dB over the entire impedance bandwidth and maximum gain of the A1 and A2 is 7.3 and 7.2 dBi, respectively. MIMO performance metrics such as ECC, DG, MEG and TARC have also been measured and found well within acceptable limits. In particular, ECC is below 0.001, DG is above 9.99 dB, MEG1 and MEG2 of both the ports have difference less than 3 dB and TARC is less than -20 dB for both the antennas.

2. Antenna geometry and CP agility

2.1. Geometry of the antennas

The antenna design layout is shown in Figure 1. It comprises a properly shaped ground plane hosting an octagonal substrate, two L type feed networks, conformal probes and two

Figure 1. Geometry of the antenna.

Table 1. Design parameters in mm.

L1	85.5	L4	51	D1	25	H1	9	Height of DRA	18
L2	38.5	L5	35	D2	5	H2	15	Substrate thickness	0.8
L3	15.5	F1	31.2	F2	13.6	W	2.4		

Figure 2. Generation of fundamental orthogonal hybrid modes in cylindrical DRA.

DRA. All the design parameters, optimized using HFSS simulation software, are shown in Table 1.

RT Duroid with dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 2.33$, thickness 0.8 mm and $\tan \delta = 0.0012$ has been used as the substrate and Eccostock Hik bar with $\epsilon_r = 9.8$, $\tan \delta = 0.001$ has been used as the dielectric resonator antenna material. The height of the DRA is 18 mm. Each single DRA has been excited by two conformal probes having heights $H_1 = 9$ mm, $H_2 = 15$ mm and radius 1 mm as shown in Figure 1. The conformal probe or patch excitation is an easy and effective feed method where it is required to couple field energy between DRA and the feed line [41]. It also helps in matching by adjusting height of the probe and excitation of the $HE_{11\delta}$ mode. Conformal probe-1 excites $HE_{11\delta}^x$ and probe-2 excites the $HE_{11\delta}^y$ mode in CDRA, as shown in Figure 2. A CP field can be attained in a DRA by exciting two orthogonal components of fields with the same magnitude and in phase quadrature. Probe-1 and probe-2, as shown in Figure 1, have been placed on the L-type feed network. Orthogonal modes inside DRA have been excited by these two probes. The phase quadrature relationship between both the orthogonal field components is controlled by optimizing the heights (H_1 and H_2) of the probes. The width of the L-type microstrip feed line corresponding to 50Ω characteristic impedance in no load condition is calculated and optimized using HFSS software. Design equation (1) used in [41] for the $HE_{11\delta}$ mode in cylindrical DRA (CDRA) has been used as the first guess which is further optimized using HFSS software

$$f_0 = \frac{c \times 6.324}{2\pi a \sqrt{\epsilon_{rDRA} + 2}} \left[0.27 + 0.36 \frac{a}{2H} + 0.002 \left(\frac{a}{2H} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

where a , H and ϵ_{rDRA} are the radius, height and dielectric constant of the DRA, respectively, and c is the velocity of light in vacuum.

Table 2 displays different antennas with their respective S parameters. In antenna at s.no.1, a square substrate having a dimension of 110×110 mm² has been used. It showed good impedance bandwidth of 22.8% around 3.5 GHz, but had two drawbacks which were large size of the substrate (12,100 mm²) and poor isolation between ports with minimum isolation of -15 dB. Antenna at s.no.2 presented improvement in antenna-1 with a

Table 2. S-parameters and ARBW of different stage antennas.

S.no.	Antenna	S-parameters	S_{11} (S_{22}) Bandwidth (GHz)	Min. Isolation S_{12} (S_{21}) dB	Axial ratio bandwidth (GHz)
1		3.1–3.9 (22.8%)	–15	3.4–3.5 (100 MHz)	
2		3.1–3.9 (22.8%)	–16.6	3.37–3.5 (130 MHz)	
3		3.05–3.88 (23.95%)	–19.2	3.3–3.44 (140 MHz)	
4		3.08–3.94 (24.5%)	–20	3.42–3.57 (150 MHz)	

reduced dimension of substrate, i.e. 9356 mm² (77% of the substrate area of antenna-1). To improve isolation between ports, antennas A1 and A2 have been designed. In A1 two CDRA are placed on the substrate, whereas in A2 two RDRA are placed on the substrate. A comparison between simulated S-parameters of the two antennas is shown in Figure 3. It is observed that there are two resonances due to dual-probe excitation. Isolation is achieved by introducing two triangular head slots cut in the ground plane with a linear slot at the middle of ground. Condition of the common ground which is essential for an MIMO antenna is attained by side slits on back of the substrate.

2.2. CP Agility

CP agility describes the quickness of changing, minimum AR frequency by mechanical insertion/extraction of concentric cylindrical shells in/from the ring DRAs. Simulated ARs and S_{11} for different radii of inner shells, which are to be extracted from the CDRA, are shown in Figures 4 and 5. These show simulated ARs and S_{11} corresponding to radius $R_2 = 0$ to 5 mm increased in a step size of 0.5 mm. It is pertinent to note that minimum AR frequencies for different air gap cylinder radii, as shown in Figure 4, are always in their respective 10 dB impedance bandwidths as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 6 shows five-concentric cylindrical shells to achieve CP agility. A1 can be configured when all the cylindrical shells are inserted in the ring DRA. The effect of gap between

Figure 3. Simulated S-parameters' comparison of A1 and A2.

Figure 4. Axial ratio for different radii of the inner shell of CDRA.

concentric cylindrical shells has also been studied and no significant consequences on the performance of antenna have been found, considering a gap of 0.1–0.2 mm. Minimum AR frequency can easily be shifted by extracting cylindrical shells 1–5, in succession as shown in Figure 6. In the literature, the concept of movement of CP band with respect to inner

Figure 5. S parameters $S_{11}(S_{22})$ for different radii of the inner shell of CDRA.

Figure 6. Mechanical insertion and extraction of concentric cylindrical shells to achieve CP agility.

vacuum cylinder diameter is not discussed especially in MIMO antennas where mutual operation of individual elements also affects its overall operation.

3. Results and discussion

In this section, analysis of results and their implications are discussed. Two prototypes of dual-port circularly polarized MIMO DRA have been fabricated. Adhesive (glue) has been used to stick DRAs on the substrate which resulted in the difference in the measured and simulated results. Soldering deformity of connectors with ground and feed line might also be responsible for alteration of results. Far-field results have been measured in an anechoic chamber with the corrugated horn antenna as the reference antenna while keeping other ports matched with 50Ω . Standard measurement procedures [42–46] adopted for parameter measurement and Equation (2)–(8) have been implemented in MATLAB. Input radiation parameters to MATLAB have been provided by HFSS simulation software and radiation parameters of the antenna were measured, for simulated and measured values, respectively. A photograph of the measurement setup is shown in the inset of Figure 7.

Figure 7. Simulated and measured S_{11} and S_{12} of A1 and A2.

Simulated and measured S-parameters of the antennas are shown in Figure 7. Simulated and measured AR of the antennas are shown in Figure 8. Simulated results are in good agreement with the measured data. Measured impedance bandwidths of the antennas are 21.2% (3.15–3.9 GHz) and 22.2% (3.12–3.9 GHz), respectively. The measured 3 dB ARBW are 190 and 150 MHz in the broadside direction. Port isolation is also greater than -20 dB over the complete impedance bandwidth and maximum gain of the antennas are 7.3 and 7.2 dBi, respectively. ECC, DG, MEG and TARC have also been measured for both antennas. Figure 9 reports simulated and measured values of gain and radiation efficiency of the antennas. Measured radiation efficiency is greater than 90% for both the antennas, whereas maximum gains of 7.3 and 7.2 dBi are obtained for the antennas, respectively. Figure 10 shows simulated and measured radiation field pattern (LHCP and RHCP) of A1 in the E-plane and H-plane, whereas Figure 11 shows the same for A2. The left-hand CP component is greater than its right-hand counterpart by more than acceptable limits for both the antennas. Radiation patterns have been plotted at a minimum AR frequency for both the antennas.

To study and evaluate the MIMO or diversity performance of the proposed antenna, ECC, DG, MEG and TARC have been analyzed. ECC is one of the main performance metric of the MIMO system which describes isolation and correlation of the communication channel with each other [8]. The DG identifies the amount of improvement that can be seen in MIMO in comparison to SISO (single input single output) system. In MIMO systems, the adjacent radiators when operating simultaneously can influence the performance of each other. This parameter is described by TARC. MEG measures the amount of power received by the MIMO antenna in comparison to a standard antenna in the standard environment. For a good diversity performance of the MIMO antenna, the difference between MEG1 and MEG2

Figure 8. Simulated and measured axial ratio of A1 and A2.

Figure 9. Gain (measured and simulated) and radiation efficiency (measured and simulated) of A1 and A2.

Figure 10. Measured and simulated E-plane (left) and H-plane (right) radiation pattern of A1 at 3.35 GHz.

Figure 11. Measured and simulated E-plane (left) and H-plane (right) radiation pattern of A2 at 3.5 GHz.

should be less than 3 dB [26]. ECC, DG and TARC have been calculated using Equation (2), Equation (3) and Equation (8), respectively, given in [8,47,48] whereas MEG is calculated by Equation (4) given in [26]. Simulated and measured ECC has been obtained less than 0.001 which satisfies the limit $ECC < 0.3$ mentioned in [8] for the MIMO system. DG is also approximately 10 dB over the entire bandwidth which is desired for the MIMO system [8].

A desirable value of TARC for an MIMO system is less than 0 dB

$$ECC = \frac{\left| \iint_{4\pi} [\vec{F}_1(\theta, \phi) * \vec{F}_2(\theta, \phi)] d\Omega \right|^2}{\iint_{4\pi} |\vec{F}_1(\theta, \phi)|^2 d\Omega \iint_{4\pi} |\vec{F}_2(\theta, \phi)|^2 d\Omega} \quad (2)$$

where $\vec{F}_i(\theta, \phi)$ is the three-dimensional field radiation pattern of the MIMO antenna when port- i is excited. Ω is the solid angle and * represents the Hermitian product operator

$$DG = 10\sqrt{1 - ECC^2} \quad (3)$$

$$MEG_i = 0.5 \left[1 - \sum_{j=1}^N |S_{ij}|^2 \right] \quad (4)$$

For the two port MIMO antenna, Equation (4) is expanded in Equations (5) and (6), whereas Equation (7) represents the condition of difference between two MEGs which should be less than 3 dB.

$$MEG_1 = 0.5 \left[1 - |S_{11}|^2 - |S_{12}|^2 \right] \quad (5)$$

$$MEG_2 = 0.5 \left[1 - |S_{21}|^2 - |S_{22}|^2 \right] \quad (6)$$

$$|MEG_1 - MEG_2| < 3 \text{ dB} \quad (7)$$

$$TARC = \sqrt{\frac{(S_{11} + S_{12}e^{j\theta})^2 + (S_{21} + S_{22}e^{j\theta})^2}{2}} \quad (8)$$

where θ is the input feeding phase.

Table 3 summarizes the MIMO performance metric results of A1 and A2 at 3.35 and 3.5 GHz, respectively. Figure 12 shows photographs of fabricated antennas, A1 with CDRA and A2 with two diameters of internal vacuum cylinder. Initially, A2 with diameter $D_2 = 2.5$ mm is fabricated and its results have been measured, then the measurement process was

Table 3. MIMO parameters of A1 and A2.

	ECC	DG	MEG1	MEG2	TARC
Simulated (A1 at 3.35 GHz)	1.3×10^{-4}	9.99	-13.98	-13.88	-44.98
Measured (A1 at 3.35 GHz)	2.7×10^{-5}	9.99	-13.8	-13.5	-43.2
Simulated (A2 at 3.5 GHz)	1.2×10^{-4}	9.99	-14.2	-14.1	-35.02
Measured (A2 at 3.5 GHz)	5.4×10^{-5}	9.99	-14.4	-14.3	-34.5

Figure 12. Structures of fabricated antennas with different diameters of internal vacuum cylinder in CDRA (a) $D_2 = 0$ mm, (b) $D_2 = 2.5$ mm and (c) $D_2 = 5$ mm (left to right).

Table 4. Comparison of the proposed antenna with other published MIMO DRA.

Ref.	Impedance bandwidth (GHz)	ARBW (GHz)	Gain (dBi)	Isolation (dB)
[23]	5.4–6.0	–	5	–18
[24]	3.4–8.2	–	3	–20
[25]	3.4–3.7, 5.15–5.35	–	5.7, 6.61	–13
[26]	3.42–3.8, 4.97–5.5	–	5.2, 6.38	–20
[29]	2.21–3.13, 3.4–3.92, 5.3–6.1	5.62–5.82	1.5, 4.1, 2.3	–20
[30]	4.89–5.42	5.16–5.38	5	–12
[31]	5.2–6.08	5.2–5.58	4	–19
[32]	5.25–6.25	Not given	4.7	–25
[33]	3.5–4.95	3.58–4.4	6.2	–28
[34]	3.15–3.93	3.3–3.8 (simulated)	7.4 (simulated)	–24
[35]	4.7–6.2	–	7.4	–15
[36]	5.27–5.65	–	5.99	–22
[37]	3.4–3.7, 5.15–5.35	–	5.6	–46
[38]	5.6–5.9	–	4.8	–20
[39]	1 GHz bandwidth around 30 GHz	–	6.9, 7.6	–27
[40]	3.24–6.0	–	7.45	–20
Proposed-A1	3.12–3.9	3.26–3.45 (190 MHz)	7.3	–20
Proposed-A2	3.15–3.9	3.43–3.58 (150 MHz)	7.2	–20

repeated after drilling the diameter $D_2 = 5$ mm. Measured results of all the three cases have been found in agreement with simulated results hence the concept of CP agility has been verified. Measured results of diameter $D_2 = 2.5$ mm of Figure 12 are not shown for brevity. Table 4 shows the comparison of the proposed MIMO DRA with other recently published MIMO DRA that includes circularly polarized and linearly polarized radiators. In Table 4 circularly polarized MIMO DRA are from [34–39]. The proposed MIMO DRA has comparable output parameters as that of Chen et al. [34]. But the major advantages of the proposed antenna in comparison to [34] are (1) simple ring DRAs instead of uneven cut DRA, (2) simple isolation mechanism in place of the complex EBG structure and (3) compact in size with a lesser surface area of the substrate.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, a concept of CP agility is presented with two antennas operating in the Sub-6 GHz band. Two dual-port multiple input multiple output DRAs are proposed. Antennas are fabricated on the Rogers RT Duroid substrate having a dielectric constant of 2.33 and a thickness of 0.8 mm. Two fabricated antennas exhibit good impedance bandwidth of 21.2% and 22.2% and low mutual coupling between ports with a minimum isolation of –20 dB. These antennas also exhibit CP with axial ratio bandwidths of 190 and 150 MHz. Diversity performance is also analyzed and the entire analysis confirms that the proposed MIMO antennas can be a good candidate for 5G communications in the Sub-6 GHz band.

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ORCID

L. Matekovits <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-0946-9561>

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Summer Singh
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Dual-band circularly polarized MIMO DRA for sub-6 GHz applications

Sumer Singh Singhwal^{1,2} | Binod K. Kanaujia³ | Ajit Singh⁴ |
Jugul Kishor⁵

¹Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun, India

²Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, HMR Institute of Technology and Management, Delhi, India

³School of Computational and Integrative Science, Jawaharlal Nehru University, Delhi, India

⁴Department of Computer Science & Engineering, B.T.Kumaon Institute of Technology, Dwarahat, Uttarakhand, India

⁵Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, JIMS Engineering Management Technical Campus Greater Noida, India

⁶Department of Electronics and Telecommunications, Politecnico di Torino, Torino, Italy

Correspondence

Ladislau Matekovits, Department of Electronics and Telecommunications, Politecnico di Torino, Torino, Italy.
Email: ladislau.matekovits@polito.it

Abstract

In this article, a dual-band circularly polarized multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) is proposed for 3.5 and 5.5 GHz bands, both being located under 6 GHz. Known as sub-6 (or as mid-band), they provide good coverage and capacity in the newly targeted fifth-generation (5G) systems. The proposed structure consists of two ring DRAs (RDRAs) etched on a 0.8 mm thick RT Duroid substrate. Measured impedance bandwidths in broadside direction are 3.1–3.75 GHz (19%) and 5.3–5.6 GHz (9.4%) and circular polarization (CP) bandwidths are 3.425–3.6 GHz (5%) and 5.45–5.55 GHz (2%), respectively. CP is achieved by exciting HE modes using two probes placed orthogonally to each other, that is, at an azimuthal angular distance of 90°. Varying the lengths of the probe allows achieving the necessary time-phase quadrature between modes. Comparison between recent multiband circularly polarized MIMO DRAs and proposed prototype has revealed that CP bandwidth in both bands is one of the highlighting advantages of the present configuration.

KEYWORDS

5G, circular polarization, dielectric resonator antenna, multiple-input-multiple-output, sub-6 GHz

1 | INTRODUCTION

The field of wireless communication is growing rapidly, to fulfill the need of high-speed data transfer applications. The 5G wireless communication system has been designed to support enhanced mobile broadband, ultra-reliability and low latency, massive machine type communication and fiber type speed to homes and businesses. It means 5G standards are defined in such a way to offer greater range of capability in comparison with previous generation mobile communications.¹ To support nationwide services, sub-6 GHz band can use channel size from 50 to 100 MHz. Multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) antenna technology is a key concept used to

enhance capacity of 5G networks because of its various advantages such as diversity performance and improved channel capacity.² In addition, the use of circular polarization (CP) in MIMO systems are also advantageous due to low polarization loss, less multipath interference, better performance and reliability.³ There are various types of antennas to adopt MIMO functionality and out of these antennas, DRAs are the most promising ones due to their advantages such as high radiation efficiency, less surface wave loss and low ohmic losses.⁴ Nowadays, dual frequency antennas are mostly desired because of increasing wireless applications. In the scientific literature, dual band MIMO DRAs are proposed, for example, in References 5–10, but the discussed solutions refer to

FIGURE 1 Antenna geometry with leading dimensions (numerical values are reported in Table 1). Top view (top), top view of the feeding circuit (center), side view (bottom)

Parameter	Dimensions (in mm)	Parameter	Dimensions (in mm)
L	110	W	50
A	53.8	C	28.8
W1	2.4	W2	1.3
H1	9	H2	15
Hs	5	H	16.5
Ddra	25.5	R	8.5
Ws	2.4	Ls	50
Lf	21	Wsub	0.8
Din	5		

TABLE 1 Design parameters

linearly polarized antennas. In Reference 11, a tri-band dielectric resonator based hybrid antenna for WLAN/WiMAX application is reported. In this work, circular

ring with T-shaped printed line produces dual hybrid radiating modes in cylindrical dielectric resonator antenna (CDRA). But advantages of CP in antennas

swerved the researchers toward new domain of circularly polarized MIMO DRA. Very few articles¹²⁻¹⁸ have been reported in this domain. In Reference 12 the authors have proposed dual polarized triple band (2.21-3.13, 3.40-3.92, and 5.30-6.10 GHz) MIMO DRA for WLAN/WiMAX applications. The discussed configuration has achieved significant CP bandwidth for the upper band only. Reported gain in the three bands are 1.5, 4.2, and 2.3 dBi, respectively. In Reference 13, a dual port DR based circularly polarized MIMO antenna has been proposed for WLAN applications, however only simulated results are discussed. In Reference 13, a corner truncated V-shaped DR has been utilized to obtain CP radiation and two symmetric orthogonal feed networks have been deployed to lessen mutual coupling between the ports. In Reference 14, two self-complementary L-shaped DR based MIMO antennas have been reported with 5.16 to 6.30 GHz impedance bandwidth and 5.20 to 6.08 GHz axial ratio band width (ARBW). In Reference 15, a dual port CDRA based MIMO antenna with dual sense polarization has been presented for WLAN applications. In Reference 16, a hybrid technique has been employed using a parasitic patch at an optimized distance beside the conformal metal strip of the two identical rectangular DRAs in order to generate CP wave. In Reference 17 two-element CP-DRA array has been implemented with electromagnetic band-gap (EBG) structure etched into the ground plane of the microstrip patch transmission line. In the best knowledge of authors, no work is reported related to dual-element, dual-band DRA based MIMO antenna with CP in both the operating bands. In

Reference 18 some of the authors of the present work has proposed the concept of CP agility in MIMO DRA for 5G applications.

In this article, a dual band compact MIMO DRA is proposed with CP operating in the 3.5 and 5.5 GHz bands. The structure consists of two ring DRAs excited by two arc-shaped line feeds and four conformal probes. The total substrate size is $50 \times 110 \text{ mm}^2$ which makes it compact for sub-6 GHz band applications (3.5 and 5.5 GHz) which includes WLAN, WiMAX, and 5G communications. Main advantages of the proposed antenna are: (a) Ease of fabrication of DRs, the microstrip line feed and the defect ground structure (DGS), (b) Compact in size with dual-elements on the substrate, (c) CP bandwidth is available in both the operating bands. The major contribution of this dissemination is to give concept of dual band with circular polarization in both the bands with the help of ring DRAs in realization of MIMO antennas. Isolation is achieved by using polarization diversity as well as utilization of simple DGS. Impedance matching is fulfilled by applying arc shaped microstrip line feed structure.

2 | ANTENNA STRUCTURE AND THEORY

The geometry of the proposed antenna is shown in Figure 1 and design parameters are shown in Table 1. The used substrate is RT Duroid with relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_{rsub} = 2.33$, thickness $W_{sub} = 0.8 \text{ mm}$ and

FIGURE 2 S-Parameters and ARBW comparison with RDRA, with CDRA and without DRA

FIGURE 3 Effect of DGS on isolation between ports

FIGURE 4 Photographs of the different parts of the fabricated prototype

$\tan\delta = 0.0012$. Moreover, Eccostock Hik bar with $\epsilon_{r\text{dra}} = 10$, $\tan\delta = 0.001$ has been used as DRA material. The antenna structure comprises (a) a $(110 \times 50\text{mm}^2)$ sized rectangular substrate, (b) two arc shaped microstrip lines feed, (c) two conformal probes per RDRA with heights 9 and 15 mm, (d) two ring shaped DRAs, (e) a DGS structure with a rectangle cut in the ground.

In this article, conformal probes have been chosen to excite the $HE_{11\delta}$ and $HE_{12\delta}$ modes having different resonant frequencies in the RDRA. Naturally comprehended “conformal probe” has been designed,

optimized by using HFSS software, and experimentally proved with a promise for dual-band operation of the RDRA. In $HE_{11\delta}$ mode in the RDRA is excited by using probe feed technique, which provides good impedance matching. To realize the dual mode excitation (for the structure supporting both the modes) with a single feed requires a proper feed network, which excites two orthogonal modes at each frequency. The conformal feed consists of two probes, which excite two orthogonal components of fields with same magnitude and in time-phase quadrature

FIGURE 5 Simulated and measured S-Parameters of the proposed antenna

FIGURE 6 Simulated and measured ARBW of the proposed antenna

in the RDRA. So, the conformal probe excitation is an easy and effective feed method where it is required to couple field energy between DRA and feed-line.¹⁹ It should be relevant to note that the conformal probe feed structure should also be helpful to realize CP. Principal of generation of CP states that, CP field can be attained in a DRA by exciting two orthogonal components of fields with same magnitude and in time-phase quadrature. Following this principal, in the proposed antenna, arc-shaped line feed provides orthogonality in field input and heights

of probes decides time-phase quadrature relationship. Both the probes, as shown in Figure 1, have been placed on arc-shaped feed line. These probes excite orthogonal modes inside DRA because each of them can generate both an x -polarized and y -polarized electric field lines. Time-phase quadrature relationship between both orthogonal field components is controlled by optimizing the heights of the two probes. Coupling of field components between the probe and RDRA, and impedance matching depends on the feed network configuration, which can be optimized by choosing different width of the arc-shaped line and feed line. Width of feed line and arc-shaped line corresponds to 50 and 70 Ω characteristic line impedance, respectively. By adjusting the height of probes the $HE_{11\delta}$ mode in the RDRA can be excited. Conformal probe-1 excites $HE_{11\delta}^x$ mode while probe-2 excites $HE_{11\delta}^y$ mode. As a proof, two dips at 3.3 and 3.6 GHz, respectively, in the S-parameter graph in Figure 2 can be observed.

The values of ϵ_{eff} and H_{eff} are calculated by using following equations Equations (1) and (2).¹⁴

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{H_{eff}}{(H/\epsilon_{rCDRA}) + (W_{sub}/\epsilon_{rsub})} \quad (1)$$

$$H_{eff} = H + W_{sub} \quad (2)$$

The design equation used to calculate the resonant frequency of the CDRA is shown in Equation (3).^{4,11}

FIGURE 7 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of proposed antenna at 3.5 GHz E-plane (Left) and H-Plane (Right)

FIGURE 8 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of proposed antenna at 5.5 GHz E-plane (Left) and H-Plane (Right)

$$f_{r(HE_{12\delta})} = \frac{18.963 \times 10^8}{\pi D r a \sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{reff}} + 2}} \times \left[0.27 + 0.36 \left(\frac{D d r a}{4H} \right) + 0.02 \left(\frac{D r a}{4H} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

The resonant frequency of the $HE_{12\delta}$ mode is approximated as 1.6 times of that of $HE_{11\delta}$ mode as shown in Equation (4). The scaling ratio of 1.6 depends upon the aspect ratio ($D d r a / 2H$) of CDRA as mentioned in References 11, 20

$$f_{r(HE_{12\delta})} = 1.6 \times f_{r(HE_{11\delta})} \quad (4)$$

The second resonance at 5.5 GHz is due to $HE_{12\delta}$ mode. Details about how to calculate the second resonance frequency band is also explained in Reference 20. Figure 2 shows simulated input scattering responses of the proposed antenna with RDRA, with CDRA and

without DRA: the RDRA provides lower frequency band while upper frequency band is the combined effect of RDRA and conformal probes. The antenna with RDRA has improved impedance bandwidth, isolation and ARBW in comparison to antenna with CDRA. An optimization aiming to find the diameter of the hole in the RDRA has been performed using HFSS software. A rectangular slot is cut in the ground to increase isolation between ports. Figure 3 shows a comparison of isolation between ports with DGS and without DGS. Minimum isolation measured between ports in lower and upper operating band is -16.2 and -16.5 dB, respectively.

3 | RESULTS AND VALIDATION

To validate the simulated results, a prototype of the proposed antenna has been fabricated, as shown in

FIGURE 9 Surface current distribution on ground at 3.5 GHz (above) and at 5.5 GHz (below)

FIGURE 10 Field distribution on surface of RDRA at 3.5 GHz (Left) and 5.5 GHz (Right)

TABLE 2 Comparison of resonant frequencies (GHz)

	Calculated f_r of CDRA	Simulated f_r of RDRA	Measured f_r of RDRA
Lower band	3	3.3 and 3.6	3.3 and 3.6
Upper band	4.8	5.5	5.5

Figure 4, and measured results have been compared with simulated counterparts. Simulated and measured input scattering parameters of proposed antenna are

shown in Figure 5, with measurement setup in anechoic chamber depicted in inset of the figure. The 3 dB ARBW for both bands are shown in Figure 6.

TABLE 3 Comparison of the proposed antenna with recently proposed CP MIMO DRA

Reference	Impedance bandwidth (GHz)	ARBW (GHz)	Gain (dBi)	Isolation (dB)
[12]	2.21-3.13, 3.4-3.92, 5.3-6.1	5.62-5.82	1.5, 4.1, 2.3	-20
[13]	4.89-5.42	5.16-5.38	5	-12
[14]	5.2-6.08	5.2-5.58	4	-19
[15]	5.25-6.25	not given	4.7	-25
[16]	3.5-4.95	3.58-4.4	6.2	-28
[17]	3.15-3.93	3.3-3.8 (simulated)	7.4 (simulated)	-24
[18]	3.12-3.9	3.26-3.45	7.3	-20
Proposed	3.1-3.75, 5.3-5.6	3.425-3.6, 5.45-5.55	6.8,4.6	-16.5,-16.2

FIGURE 11 Simulated and measured ECC and DG for lower band

Simulated and measured results are in good agreement with some reduced variations due to fabrication tolerance, soldering imperfections and due to usage of adhesive to stick on substrate. However, very minimal amount of adhesive is applied but effect of air layer in between DRA and substrate surface may result deviation in results which is depicted in Figure 5 and Figure 6. Measured 10 dB impedance bandwidths are 3.1 to 3.75 GHz (19%) and 5.3 to 5.6 GHz (9.4%); the 3 dB ARBW are 3.425 to 3.6 GHz (5%), and 5.45 to 5.55 GHz (2%), respectively, in broadside direction. Isolation between ports at 3.5 and 5.5 GHz have been measured to be equal to -16.2 and -16.5 dB, respectively.

Measured E- (left) and H-plane (right) radiation patterns at 3.5 and 5.5 GHz are reported in Figures 7 and 8, respectively: left hand CP wave dominates over right hand counterpart by acceptable margin. Figure 9 shows the surface current distribution on the ground plane to

quantify isolation between ports at both the resonant frequencies. HE_{mmp} mode is basically the hybrid mode, in which E_z component is more dominant as compared to H_z component. $HE_{11\delta}$ mode in CDRA indicates that there are the one full and one half wave variations in azimuthal and radial directions, respectively. Similarly, $HE_{12\delta}$ mode in CDRA indicates that there is the one full and two half wave variations in azimuthal as well as radial directions, respectively. δ indicates that the variation in axial direction (z) is in between the 0 and 1. Field distribution on the surface of the RDRA is shown in Figure 10 which is approximately same as that of CDRA and this difference can be attributed due to air gap at the center. Table 2 shows a comparison between calculated, simulated and measured resonant frequencies of the DRA. It is observed that resonant frequencies for lower and upper bands corresponding to $HE_{11\delta}$ and $HE_{12\delta}$ modes in RDRA have drifted in comparison to that of CDRA.

FIGURE 12 Simulated and measured ECC and DG for upper band

MIMO performance has been evaluated by calculating $DG = 10\sqrt{1 - ECC}^{22,23}$ and ECC using Equation (5).

$$ECC = \frac{\left| \int \int_{4\pi} \vec{F}_1(\theta, \phi) * \vec{F}_2(\theta, \phi) d\Omega \right|^2}{\int \int_{4\pi} |\vec{F}_1(\theta, \phi)|^2 d\Omega \int \int_{4\pi} |\vec{F}_2(\theta, \phi)|^2 d\Omega} \quad (5)$$

where $\vec{F}_i(\theta, \phi)$ is three dimensional field radiation pattern of the MIMO antenna when port- i is excited. Ω is solid angle and * represents the Hermitian product operator. ECC shows the amount of channel isolation in a wireless communication link. In Table 3 a comparison between the performances of the proposed antenna and data available in the literature is reported.

Simulated and measured ECC and DG for lower and upper bands are shown in Figures 11 and 12, respectively. ECC is well below 0.5 throughout the lower and upper operating bands and correlation coefficient (square root of ECC) is well below 0.3 as mentioned in Reference 22, 24. DG is above 9.8 dB for both the operating bands.

4 | CONCLUSION

In this article, a dual-band MIMO ring dielectric resonator antenna with appreciated CP performance has been proposed that operates at 3.5 and 5.5 GHz WiMAX bands. Measured ECC is below 0.5 and DG is above 9.8 dB for both bands. Measured impedance bandwidths are 19% and 9.4% and ARBWs are 175 and 100 MHz in broadside

direction at 3.5 and 5.5 GHz resonant frequencies, respectively. It demonstrates CP in both bands. The size of antenna is also compact ($110 \times 50\text{mm}^2$) which makes it good choice for sub-6 GHz dual band applications.

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ORCID

Binod K. Kanaujia <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7849-5299>

Jugul Kishor <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1108-998X>

Ladislau Matekovits <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0946-9561>

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Sumer Singh Singhwai did Bachelor of engineering in 2003 and Master in engineering in 2012 from Birla Institute of Technology Mesra Ranchi. He is currently pursuing PhD from Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun. He has interest in Dielectric resonator antennas, MIMO antenna, patch antennas, and so forth. He has published papers on these topics in refereed journals.

Binod Kumar Kanaujia is working as a Professor in the School of Computational and Integrative sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi since August 2016. Before joining Jawaharlal Nehru University, he had been in the Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering in Ambedkar Institute of Advanced Communication Technologies & Research (formerly Ambedkar Institute of Technology), Delhi as a Professor since February 2011 and Associate Professor (2008-2011). Dr. Kanaujia held the positions of Lecturer (1996-2005) and Reader (2005-2008) in the Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering, and also as the Head of the

Department in the M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, India. Prior to his career in academics, Dr. Kanaujia had worked as an Executive Engineer in the R&D division of M/s UPTRON India Ltd. Dr. Kanaujia had completed his BTech in Electronics Engineering from KNIT Sultanpur, India in 1994. He did his MTech and PhD in 1998 and 2004, respectively from Department of Electronics Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India. He has been awarded Junior Research Fellowship by UGC Delhi in the year 2001-2002 for his outstanding work in the electronics field. He has a keen research interest in design and modeling of microstrip antenna, dielectric resonator antenna, left-handed metamaterial microstrip antenna, shorted microstrip antenna, ultra wideband antennas, reconfigurable, and circular polarized antennas for wireless communication. He has been credited to publish more than 325 research papers with more than 2400 citations with h-index of 23 in several peer-reviewed journals and conferences. He had supervised 50 MTech and 24 PhD research scholars in the field of microwave engineering. He is a reviewer for several journals of international repute that is, IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation, IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters, Wireless Personal Communications, Journal of Electromagnetic Wave and Application, Indian Journal of Radio and Space Physics, IETE Technical Review, International Journal of Electronics, International Journal of Engineering Science, IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, AEU-International Journal of Electronics and Communication, International Journal of Microwave and Wireless Technologies, and so forth. Dr. Kanaujia had successfully executed 80 research projects sponsored by several agencies of Government of India that is, DRDO, DST, AICTE, and ISRO. He is also a member of several academic and professional bodies that is, IEEE, Institution of Engineers (India), Indian Society for Technical Education and The Institute of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineers of India. He is also Associate Editor in AEU-International Journal of Electronics and Communication of publisher Elsevier and IETE Technical Review of publisher Taylor and Francis.

Ajit Singh is working as Professor in B. T. Kumaon Institute of Technology, Dwarahat, Almora, Uttarakhand, India. He did his M. Tech in 2003 from Netaji Subhas Institute of Technology, New Delhi and Ph.D. in 2012

from Singhania University, Rajasthan. He has published several papers in refereed journals.

Jugul Kishor is working as Associate Professor, in the Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, JIMS Engineering Management Technical Campus Greater Noida. Before joining JIMS Engineering Management Technical Campus, he has been in the Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, National Institute of Technology, New Delhi as an Assistant Professor (Contract) in the session 2018-2019. Dr. Kishor also held the position of Assistant Professor (2009-2018) in the Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, I. T S Engineering College, Greater Noida. He received the degree in Electronics Engineering from Kamla Nehru Institute of Technology, Sultanpur, India, in 2002, MTech degree in Microwave Electronics from University of Delhi, India, in 2008, and the PhD degree from Indian Institute of Technology (Indian school of Mines), Dhanbad, Jharkhand, India, in 2017. His recent research interest activities have focused on the design and development of microwave passive components, dielectric resonator filters, MIMO antennas and metamaterial. He has been credited to publish more than 35 papers with various reputed International journals and conferences with citation and h-index.

Ladislau Matekovits, (M'94-SM'11) received the degree in electronic engineering from Institutul Politehnic din București, București, Romania, and the PhD degree (Dottorato di Ricerca) in electronic engineering from Politecnico di Torino, Torino, Italy, in 1992 and 1995, respectively. Since 1995, he has been with the Department of Electronics and Telecommunications, Politecnico di Torino, first with a post-doctoral fellowship, then as a Research Assistant. He joined the same Department as Assistant Professor in 2002 and was appointed as Senior Assistant Professor in 2005 and as Associate Professor in 2014, respectively. In February 2017 he obtained the Full Professor qualification (Italy). In late 2005, he was Visiting Scientist at the Antennas and Scattering Department, FGAN-FHR (now Fraunhofer Institute), Wachtberg, Germany. Beginning July 1, 2009, for 2 years he has been a Marie Curie Fellow at Macquarie University, Sydney, NSW, Australia, where in 2013 he also held a Visiting Academic position and in 2014 has been

appointed as Honorary Fellow. His main research activities concern numerical analysis of printed antennas and in particular development of new, numerically efficient full-wave techniques to analyze large arrays, optimization techniques and active and passive metamaterials for cloaking applications. Material parameter retrieval of these structures by inverse methods and different optimization techniques have also been considered. In the last years, bioelectromagnetic aspects have also been contemplated, as for example design of implantable antennas or development of nano-antennas for example for drug delivery applications. He has published 350+ papers, including 85 journal contributions, and delivered seminars on these topics all around the world: Europe, USA (AFRL/MIT-Boston), Australia, China, Russia, and so forth. Prof. Matekovits has been invited to serve as Research Grant Assessor for government funding calls (Romania, Italy, and Croatia) and as International Expert in PhD thesis evaluation by several Universities from Australia, India, Pakistan, Spain, and so forth. Prof. Matekovits has been a recipient of various awards in international conferences, including the 1998 URSI Young Scientist Award (Thessaloniki, Greece), the Barzilai Award 1998 (young Scientist Award, granted every 2-years by the Italian National Electromagnetic Group), and the Best AP2000 Oral Paper on Antennas, ESA-EUREL Millennium Conference on Antennas and Propagation (Davos, Switzerland), and more recently he has been

awarded with the 2019 American Romanian Academy of Arts and Sciences (ARA) Medal of Excellence in Science. He is recipient of the Motohisa Kanda Award 2019, for the most cited paper of the IEEE Transactions on EMC in the past 5 years. He has been Assistant Chairman and Publication Chairman of the European Microwave Week 2002 (Milan, Italy), and General Chair of the 11th International Conference on Body Area Networks (BodyNets) 2016. Since 2010 he is member of the organizing committee of the International Conference on Electromagnetics in Advanced Applications (ICEAA) and he is member of the technical program committees of several conferences. He has been recently appointed as Member of the National Council for the Attestation of University Degrees, Diplomas and Certificates (CNATDCU), Romania, for the term 2020-2024. He serves as Associated Editor of the IEEE ACCESS, IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters and IET MAP and reviewer for different journals.

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Dual-port MIMO dielectric resonator antenna for WLAN applications

Sumer Singh Singhwal^{1,2} | Binod Kumar Kanaujia³

¹Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun, India

²Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, HMR Institute of Technology and Management, Delhi, India

³School of Computational and Integrative Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India

⁴BTK Institute of Technology, Dwarahat, Uttarakhand, India

⁵Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, JIMS Engineering Management Technical Campus, Greater Noida, India

Correspondence

Jugul Kishor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, JIMS Engineering Management Technical Campus, Greater Noida, India.
Email: jugulkishor@gmail.com

Abstract

A dual-port multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) for 5 GHz IEEE (802.11a/h/j/n/ac/ax) is discussed in this article. Two prototypes of single feed DRA and dual feed MIMO DRA are fabricated and measured results are compared with the simulated data. The proposed single feed DRA and dual feed MIMO DRA exhibits wide impedance bandwidth (IBW). Antennas have been fabricated on Rogers RT Duroid substrate with Eccostock made DRA placed over the substrate. DRAs are excited by aperture coupled feed to achieve wide bandwidth and high efficiency. The measured IBW of uniport DRA and dual-port MIMO DRA are 26.6% (4.75–6.21 GHz) and 27.5% (4.7–6.2 GHz) respectively. Maximum gain of the antenna is 7.4 dBi. The results of the antennas are in good agreement with simulated data and they are suitable for WLAN applications. These antennas are also compact with area of substrate 32.8 cm².

KEYWORDS

dielectric resonator antenna (DRA), multiple input multiple output (MIMO), WLAN

1 | INTRODUCTION

Multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technology uses multiple transmitters and receivers to transfer more data at the same time. The advent of MIMO antennas is a boon for human kind, seeking high-speed wireless data transmission in various applications. Initially, patch antenna-based MIMO antennas were proposed in the literature until Ishimiya et al^{1,2} proposed dielectric resonator antenna (DRA)-based MIMO antenna which have more degree of freedom for designing and low loss due to the absence of metal in DRA. DRA-based MIMO antenna comprises advantages of both MIMO and DRA technology. In the literature, researchers proposed different DRA-based MIMO antenna for different applications. Thamae and Wu³ proposed dual-port cylindrical DRA

(CDRA) with two orthogonal feeds. Yan and Bernhard⁴ proposed dual-port frequency agile MIMO DRA for dynamic spectrum access applications in cognitive radios. Roslan et al⁵ investigated MIMO rectangular DRA (RDRA) for 4G applications. Sharawi et al⁶ proposed eight-element, dual-band, low profile MIMO antenna system using CDRA for wireless access points. Hussain et al⁷ proposed eight CDRA-based MIMO linear antenna array system for mm-wave. Roslan et al⁸ proposed two F-shaped DRAs-based MIMO antenna by exciting two orthogonal modes at two ports for 4G applications. Hussain et al⁹ proposed 16 CDRA-based four-port MIMO linear antenna array system for mm-wave applications at 30 GHz with bandwidth of 6.7%. Nasir et al¹⁰ presented single RDRA-based MIMO antenna fed by two microstrip lines for 4G applications. Sharma et al^{11,12}

proposed two-element mushroom-shaped DRA and A-shaped DRA excited by a microstrip feed line and conformal patch to achieve wideband operation. Sharma et al¹³ proposed two-element CDRA-based hybrid MIMO antenna for WLAN and WiMAX applications. Das et al¹⁴ presented a compact back-to back DRA-based four-port MIMO antenna system with bidirectional diversity. Kumari et al¹⁵ presented dual ring element MIMO DRA excited by U-shaped printed line feed to achieve wide bandwidth. In present catena of research, main focus is to design a compact MIMO DRA which can work for wide bandwidth and this article presents an MIMO DRA which is compact in size due to single element and dual feed, for WLAN applications.

In this article, an aperture coupled fed DRA is presented and fabricated which is extended to dual feed MIMO DRA. The proposed DRA is unique due to its kite shape structure which is a combination of CDRA and L-shaped DRA, along with conformal copper strips to increase gain up to 7.5 dBi. Prototypes of both the antennas have been fabricated to validate the simulated results. The measured impedance bandwidth (IBW) of single feed DRA is 26.6% (4.75-6.21 GHz) and of dual feed MIMO DRA, IBW is 27.5% (4.7-6.2 GHz). Maximum gain has been measured 7.5 dBi (DRA) and 7.4 dBi (MIMO DRA). Then, 10 dB port isolation bandwidth for MIMO DRA has been measured 5 to 6.2 GHz which is under IBW and covers 5 GHz IEEE (802.11a/h/j/n/ac/ax) band for WLAN. Envelope correction coefficient (ECC), total active reflection coefficient (TARC), diversity gain (DG),

and mean effective gain (MEG) are measured within accepted range for MIMO operation.

2 | ANTENNA DESIGN AND OPERATING PRINCIPLE

Antenna design layouts of single feed DRA and dual feed MIMO DRA are shown in Figure 1. In Figure 1A,B single feed DRA is shown and Figure 1C,D dual feed MIMO DRA is shown. Figure 1E-G shows trimetric and side views to demonstrate six metallic patches etched on the body of DRAs. Roger RT duroid substrate with ϵ_r 2.2 and height 1.6 mm is cut down in octagonal shape and an aperture coupled feed is etched on the substrate. Major steps involved to reach the proposed DRA are shown in Figure 2. Using design equations of^{24,25} for TE_{111} mode, a Rectangular DRA (RDRA) with dimensions $34 \times 34 \times 18$ mm³ resonating at 5 GHz has been designed with simulated IBW from 4.86-5.15 GHz, but very small simulated gain in this frequency range. Low substrate area becomes essential when aiming for a compact antenna design. So, open ground area has been increased by reducing dimensions of RDRA, such that it became a L-shaped DRA. By optimizing size of DRA, Antenna-1 as shown in Figure 2 has been obtained. A CDRA with optimized radius has been merged at the center of Antenna-1 and this antenna is represented as Antenna-2. Height of CDRA kept same as that of L-shaped DRA. In Antenna-3, four cylindrical air gaps with optimized radii and distance between each

FIGURE 1 Geometry of the antenna

FIGURE 2 Steps involved in design of the proposed dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) direction

FIGURE 3 Simulated S11 of Antenna-1, Antenna-2, Antenna-3, and Antenna-4

other, has been introduced in Antenna-2. In Antenna-4, six metallic patches with optimized width and height have been etched on the surface of DRA of Antenna-3. Simulated IBW and gain of Antenna-1, Antenna-2, Antenna-3, and Antenna- 4 are shown in Figure 2. While moving from Antenna-1 to Antenna-4, optimization of different parameters has been done using simulation software ANSYS HFSS.

Dielectric resonator is placed on a thin Roger's substrate and TE_{111} mode is excited using aperture coupled

FIGURE 4 Simulated gain of Antenna-1, Antenna-2, Antenna-3, and Antenna-4

TABLE 1 IBW and maximum gain comparison of Antennas 1 to 4

Antenna	IBW (GHz)	Maximum gain (dBi)
1	5.1-5.7	4.2
2	5-5.9	5
3	5.1-6.1	5.6
4	4.7-6.2	7.85

Abbreviation: IBW, impedance bandwidth.

FIGURE 5 Parametric analysis of S11 vs frequency for different number of strips on dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) surface

feed method. Symmetrical shape of DRA is considered so that it has been easily adopted in dual-port MIMO DRA, with port symmetry properties (where in S_{ij} , i and j are interchangeable). In Figure 3, it is observed that IBW of Antenna-4 is the largest among all four antennas. Figure 4 depicts that gain of Antenna-4 is highest among all four antennas and maximum simulated gain of Antenna-4 is 7.85 dBi. Table 1 summarizes the IBWs and maximum gains of Antenna-1, Antenna-2, Antenna-3,

and Antenna-4. It was noted with the merging of CDR in L-shaped Antenna-1, IBW and gain of the Antenna-2 has been increased. Introduction of air gap will again enhance operational frequency and lower the resonance impedance of the Antenna-3. The 3-dB bandwidth is not significantly affected by air gap.²⁶ Air gap is also used for better impedance matching.^{17,18,20} Effect of copper strips on simulated IBW and gain of DRA are shown in Figures 5 and 6, respectively. From Figures 5 and 6, it has been concluded that gain and IBW increase on addition

FIGURE 6 Parametric analysis of gain vs frequency for different number of strips on dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) surface

FIGURE 9 Simulated and measured S-parameters of the proposed dielectric resonator antenna (DRA)

FIGURE 7 Photographs of fabricated dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) (top view, bottom view, and side views)

FIGURE 8 Photographs of fabricated multiple-input multiple-output dielectric resonator antenna (MIMO DRA) (top view, bottom view, and side views)

FIGURE 10 Simulated and measured S -parameters of the proposed multiple-input multiple-output dielectric resonator antenna (MIMO DRA)

of conformal copper strips. By image theory, effective shape of DRA has been changed in discrete manner as per placement of vertical patches etched on the surface of DRA and connected to ground.²⁶ So, these vertically copper patches resulted gain enhancement and multiple resonances which yield broadening of IBW. However, optimization of length and spacing of copper patches are required, to maintain maximum radiation in desired direction.

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To validate simulated results of both the proposed antennas, two prototypes have been fabricated. Figures 7 and 8 show fabricated prototype of the proposed DRA and MIMO DRA, respectively. Adhesive has been used to stick dielectric resonators on substrate. Soldering deformity of connectors and adhesive on DRA may be

FIGURE 11 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of the proposed DRA at 5.1 and 5.7 GHz. A,B, E-plane and C,D, H-plane

FIGURE 12 Simulated and measured radiation pattern of the proposed multiple-input multiple-output dielectric resonator antenna (MIMO DRA) at 5.1 and 5.7 GHz. A,B, E-plane and C,D, H-plane

responsible for variation in measured results. Far field results have been measured in anechoic chamber with corrugated horn antenna as reference antenna while keeping other port matched with 50Ω . Standard measurement procedures²⁷⁻³⁰ adopted for parameters measurement and Equations (1)-(7) have been implemented by MATLAB.

In this section, different results of fabricated prototypes have been discussed and compared with their simulated counterparts. Simulated and measured IBW of DRA is shown in Figure 9. Measured IBW is 26.6% (4.75-6.21 GHz). Figure 10 displays simulated and measured S_{11} and S_{12} of MIMO DRA. Photographs of measurement setup are also shown in the inset of Figures 9 and 10. Due to symmetry of structure, S_{22} is same as that of S_{11} and not shown in Figure 10. It has been calculated that measured IBW of fabricated MIMO DRA is 27.5% (4.7-6.2 GHz) and 10 dB isolation bandwidth is 5 to 6.2 GHz. Far field co-pol and x-pol radiation patterns have been measured at different frequencies and found suitable gap between co-pol and x-pol values at broadside direction. Far field co-pol and x-pol radiation pattern measured at 5.1 and 5.7 GHz which covers complete band of 5 to 6.2 GHz, as shown in Figure 11. Co-pol

radiation is at least 10 dB better than x-pol radiation pattern in broadside direction at all frequencies. Figure 12 shows radiation pattern of MIMO DRA at 5.1 and 5.7 GHz. Simulated and measured gain variation of both the antennas with respect to frequency is shown in Figure 13. It is observed that maximum gain of single feed DRA is 7.5 dBi and of MIMO DRA is 7.4 dBi. Maximum simulated radiation efficiency of DRA is 0.93, as shown in Figure 14.

MIMO performance metrics have also been studied to justify the performance of the proposed dual feed MIMO DRA. ECC is one of the main performance metrics of MIMO system which describes isolation and correlation of communication channel with each other.³¹ ECC expressed in Equation (1) for two-port MIMO system.^{31,32}

$$ECC = \frac{\left| \int \int_{4\pi} \left[\vec{F}_1(\theta, \varphi) * \vec{F}_2(\theta, \varphi) \right] d\Omega \right|^2}{\int \int_{4\pi} \left| \vec{F}_1(\theta, \varphi) \right|^2 d\Omega \int \int_{4\pi} \left| \vec{F}_2(\theta, \varphi) \right|^2 d\Omega} \quad (1)$$

where $\vec{F}_i(\theta, \varphi)$ is three-dimensional field radiation pattern of MIMO antenna when port- i is excited. Ω is solid angle. The DG identifies the amount of improvement that

FIGURE 13 Simulated and measured gain of the proposed dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) and multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) DRA

FIGURE 14 Simulated radiation efficiency of the proposed dielectric resonator antenna (DRA)

can be seen in MIMO in comparison to single-input single-output system and this can be calculated using Equation (2) from References 32 and 33. Figure 15 depicts simulated and measured ECC and DG of the proposed MIMO DRA. Simulated and measured ECC is below 0.3 throughout the operating band and DG is more than 9.9 in the same band which signifies higher pattern diversity.

$$DG = 10\sqrt{(1 - ECC^2)} \quad (2)$$

FIGURE 15 Simulated and measured envelope correction coefficient (ECC) and diversity gain (DG) of the proposed multiple-input multiple-output dielectric resonator antenna (MIMO DRA)

FIGURE 16 Simulated and measured MEG1, MEG2, and total active reflection coefficient (TARC) of multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) antenna

MEG measures amount of the power received by the MIMO antenna in comparison to a standard antenna in the standard environment. MEG can be calculated using Equation (3).³¹⁻³⁴ Here, N is the number of MIMO elements or ports. MEG for both the ports can be calculated using Equations (4) and (5), whereas Equation (6) is the condition of good diverse performance of MIMO antenna.³⁴

$$MEG_i = 0.5 \left[1 - \sum_{j=1}^N |S_{ij}|^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

$$\text{MEG}_1 = 0.5[1 - |S_{11}|^2 - |S_{12}|^2] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{MEG}_2 = 0.5[1 - |S_{21}|^2 - |S_{22}|^2] \quad (5)$$

$$|\text{MEG}_1 - \text{MEG}_2| < 3 \text{ dB} \quad (6)$$

TARC is a new MIMO performance metric which defines bandwidth and radiation performances under diverse conditions. For dual-port MIMO system, it can be calculated using Equation (7) given in References 32 and 33.

FIGURE 17 Simulated input impedance of the proposed dielectric resonator antenna (DRA) and multiple-input multiple-output DRA (MIMO)

FIGURE 18 Current distribution when port-1 is excited

$$\text{TARC} = \sqrt{\frac{(S_{11} + S_{12}e^{j\theta})^2 + (S_{21} + S_{22}e^{j\theta})^2}{2}} \quad (7)$$

where θ is the input feeding phase. Desirable value of TARC for MIMO system is less than 0 dB. Figure 16 depicts simulated and measured values of MEG of both ports and TARC of the proposed MIMO DRA. It has been concluded from Figure 16 that MEG1 and MEG2 have almost same values in entire operating band and difference between MEGs is less than 3 dB whereas TARC value over entire operating band has been less than -10 dB which is good for MIMO operation. Figure 17 depicts simulated input impedance of both the antennas. Surface current distribution of MIMO DRA, when port-1 excited, is shown in Figure 18. Table 2 displays comparison between recent single element MIMO DRAs and proposed single element MIMO DRA. In comparison to recent MIMO DRAs with single DR element, the proposed MIMO DRA exhibits wider IBW and higher gain.

TABLE 2 Comparison with recent single element MIMO DRA

Ref.	IBW	Gain	Excitation	Isolation between ports	No. ports
16	(698-716 MHz, 728-746 MHz) LTE bands	3.96 and 3.19	Aperture coupled and probe coupled	-40	2
17	3.4-3.7 GHz and 5.15-5.35 GHz	5.7 and 6.61	Probe	$-13, -16$	2
18	1.43-1.50 GHz and 2.50-2.69 GHz	3 and 6.48	Microstrip feed and probe	-23	2
19	1.41-1.49 GHz and 2.2-2.85 GHz	4.83 and 4.92	Probe	-6	2
20	3.42-3.80 GHz and 4.97-5.50 GHz	5.2 and 6.38	Aperture coupled	-20	2
21	5.18-5.83 GHz	5.94	Microstrip feed	-30	2
22	3.78-4.07 GHz	5.1	Multiple feed line	-16	2
23	1.0-1.62 GHz	—	Slot coupled	—	8
This work	4.7-6.2 GHz	7.5	Aperture coupled	-15	2

Abbreviations: DRA, dielectric resonator antenna; IBW, impedance bandwidth; MIMO, multiple-input multiple-output.

4 | CONCLUSION

In this article, an aperture coupled fed DRA is proposed followed by dual feed MIMO DRA. Aperture coupled feed is used to achieve wide bandwidth. Both the antennas have been fabricated to validate simulated results. The proposed DRA exhibits 26.6% (4.75-6.21 GHz) IBW, whereas the proposed dual feed MIMO DRA exhibits 27.5% (4.7-6.2 GHz) IBW. Maximum gain of the proposed DRA is 7.5 dBi and the proposed MIMO DRA is 7.4 dBi. Both the antennas are suitable for 5 GHz IEEE (802.11a/h/j/n/ac/ax) WLAN applications. Advantages of the proposed antennas are wide bandwidth, high gain and compact substrate size of area 32.8 cm².

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ORCID

Binod Kumar Kanaujia <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7849-5299>

Jugul Kishor <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1108-998X>

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Sumer S. Singhwal did Bachelor of Engineering in 2003 and Master in Engineering in 2012 from Birla Institute of Technology Mesra Ranchi. He is currently pursuing PhD from Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun. He has research interest in dielectric resonator antennas, MIMO antenna, patch antennas, and so forth. He has published several articles in refereed journals.

Binod K. Kanaujia is working as a professor in the School of Computational and Integrative sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi since August 2016. Before joining Jawaharlal Nehru University, he had been in the Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering in Ambedkar Institute of Advanced Communication Technologies and Research (formerly Ambedkar Institute of Technology), Delhi as a professor since February 2011 and

associate professor (2008-2011). Dr Kanaujia held the positions of lecturer (1996-2005) and Reader (2005-2008) in the Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, and also as the Head of the Department in the M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, India. Prior to his career in academics, Dr Kanaujia had worked as an executive engineer in the R&D division of M/s UPTRON India Ltd. Dr Kanaujia had completed his BTech degree in Electronics Engineering from KNIT Sultanpur, India in 1994. He did his MTech and PhD in 1998 and 2004, respectively, from the Department of Electronics Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India. He has been awarded Junior Research Fellowship by UGC Delhi in the year 2001 to 2002 for his outstanding work in electronics field. He has keen research interest in design and modeling of microstrip antenna, dielectric resonator antenna, left-handed metamaterial microstrip antenna, shorted microstrip antenna, ultrawideband antennas, reconfigurable, and circular polarized antenna for wireless communication. He has been credited to publish more than 150 research papers with more than 430 citations with h-index of 12 in peer-reviewed journals and conferences. He had supervised 50 MTech and 08 PhD research scholars in the field of microwave engineering. He is a reviewer of several journals of international repute, that is, IET Microwaves, Antennas and Propagation, IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters, Wireless Personal Communications, Journal of Electromagnetic Wave and Application, Indian Journal of Radio and Space Physics, IETE Technical Review, International Journal of Electronics, International Journal of Engineering Science, IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, AEU-International Journal of Electronics and Communication, International Journal of Microwave and Wireless Technologies, and so forth. Dr Kanaujia had successfully executed four research projects sponsored by several agencies of Government of India, that is, DRDO, DST, AICTE, and ISRO. He is also a member of several academic and professional bodies, that is, IEEE, Institution of Engineers (India), Indian Society for Technical Education, and The Institute of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineers of India.

Ajit Singh is working as professor in B. T. Kumaon Institute of Technology, Dwarahat, Almora, Uttarakhand, India. He did his M. Tech in 2003 from Netaji Subhas Institute of Technology, New Delhi and PhD in 2012 from Singhania

University, Rajasthan. He has published several papers in refereed journals.

Jugul Kishor is working as an associate professor, in Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, JIMS Engineering Management Technical Campus Greater Noida, India. Before joining JIMTEC, he worked as an assistant professor in the in the Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, National Institute of Technology, New Delhi and I. T S Engineering College, Greater Noida, India. Dr Kishor had completed his BTech degree in Electronics Engineering from KNIT Sultanpur, India in 2002. He did his MTech in 2008 from University of Delhi and PhD in 2017 from

Indian Institute of Technology (Indian school of Mines), Dhanbad. His recent research interest activities have focused on the design and development of microwave passive components, dielectric resonator filters, antennas, and metamaterial. He has been credited to publish more than 35 papers with various reputed International journals and conferences with citation and h-index.

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Summer Singh
Singhwal

Dual Band Circularly Polarized Antenna for Ka Band Applications

Sumer Singh Singhal

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering
Uttarakhand Technical University, Dehradun, India
Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering
H.M.R. Institute of Technology and Management, Delhi, India

Ajit Singh

B.T.K. Institute of Technology, Dwarahat
Uttarakhand, India

Binod Kumar Kanaujia

School of Computational and Integrative Science
Jawaharlal Nehru University
Delhi, India

Jugul Kishor

Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering
JIMS Engineering Management Technical Campus
Greater Noida, India

Abstract- In present scenario dual band high gain microstrip patch antennas are very much desirable in view of 5G mobile communication implementation in near future, So, this paper presents a new dual band Circularly Polarized (CP) patch antenna operating in 5G band. A rectangular slot at angle 45° is used for the design of this compact dual band CP patch antenna. The proposed antenna can operate at 28 GHz and 38 GHz having bandwidth 900 MHz and 1.3 GHz, respectively, which are useful in mobile 5G communication and multimedia wireless systems. Axial Ratio Band Width (ARBW) is 210 MHz at 28 GHz and 300 MHz at 38GHz. The gain of the proposed antenna is 7.5 dBi and 7.7 dBi at 28 GHz and 38 GHz, respectively. The proposed dual band microstrip patch antenna has been simulated, optimized and miniaturized by using EM simulator software HFSS.

Index Terms— Dual band antenna, Circular Polarization, Ka band, 5G.

I. INTRODUCTION

In present time wireless technologies are growing very speedily and technology is moving upward in frequency spectrum. Ka band and millimeter wave band are under research for wireless access technologies and multimedia wireless systems. Patch antenna at Ka band and millimeter wave band are in great demand due to their low profile, conformability, robustness and compact design. In past researchers designed majority of the dual band antennas suitable for lower frequencies but antenna for Ka band is relatively new topic of research. In [2-8], authors have design different dual band antenna operating in the 28/38 GHz bands using different techniques. For Ka band high gain is very essential requirement because of various link losses. As in comparison to linearly polarized antennas, circularly polarized antennas are preferred due to their advantages over linearly polarized as they can effectively lessen delay spread and have shorter read range.

In this paper, single element microstrip patch antenna element with desirable axial ratio (AR) with only microstrip line feed, over two center frequencies in Ka band is proposed. The proposed antenna consists of an angular slot etched in the ground plane. A slotted section on the patch is imbedded for

circular polarization. The proposed patch antenna can be designed by using RT/Duroid substrate with dielectric constant 2.2, height 10 mils and loss tangent 0.0009. The proposed antenna is designed and simulated in HFSS simulator software. Dimensions of square patch is calculated using analytical design equations given in [1].

Figure 1. Design layout of proposed antenna

Next, a rectangular slot is etched in the ground plane to achieve dual band circular polarization in the antenna. In HFSS a parameter-based optimization has been done to achieve better impedance matching and desirable AR. The final design has been tuned by changing slot dimensions accordingly at the two 5G frequencies viz 28 GHz and 38 GHz. Tuning can also be done using slot sections between two nested patches. On comparing from some recent designs to

proposed design, it is found that proposed design has very good gain along with impedance matching, circular polarization and axial ratio bandwidth.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN

Design layout of single patch antenna element for dual band is shown in Fig.1. Geometry of patch antenna is simple monolayer structure with a slot in ground plane at the center of patch. For dual band operation two patches are made which are separated by slot sections. These slots pass current to inner nested patch from outer patch. These slots change capacitive and inductive properties of nested patches which results in dualband resonance.

The size of square patch for both the frequency of operation is calculated by general design equations for $\frac{W}{h} > 1$

$$\epsilon_{r \text{ eff}} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left[1 + 12 \frac{h}{W} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (1)$$

$$W = \frac{c}{2f_r} \sqrt{\frac{2}{\epsilon_r + 1}} \quad (2)$$

given in [1]. By equation (2) size of square patch at 28 GHz is calculated as 3.5mm but due to slots in patch size of patch is reduces to approximately 3mm. Size of second internal patch is 2.5mm approximately as calculated by equation at frequency 38GHz. There are multiple design parameters such as L1, t2, t3, t4, t5, ground slot length, ground slot angle, ground slot width. After rigorous study of parameters, it was concluded that ground slot length parameter is good regulator for selecting desired frequency for both the 5G mobile communication bands. Optimized design variables are shown in Table-1

Table-1 Design parameters

S.No	Parameters	Unit -mm	S.No	Parameters	Unit -mm
1	Wf	0.2	9	t5	0.4
2	Df	0.9	10	Lf	1.5
3	L1	3	11	h	0.254
4	L2	2.5	12	ws	6
5	t1	0.1	13	Ls	6
6	t2	0.5	14	ss	0.6
7	t3	0.5	15	sst	0.2
8	t4	0.7	16	angss	-45

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To study antenna results, simulated responses of antenna have been plotted. Fig. 2 shows the S_{11} parameter graph of antenna which confirms that our proposed design exhibit dual-band operation. At 28GHz impedance bandwidth is 900MHz (3.2%) and at 38GHz it is 1300 MHz (3.4%) for general limits of ($S_{11} \leq -10\text{dB}$). Fig.3 and Fig. 4 shows the AR versus frequency graph for 28 GHz and 38GHz which shows acceptable AR for better CP operation. Axial ratio at 28.1GHz

is 1.8 dB and at 38 GHz it is 0.33dB which is acceptable value. Axial ratio bandwidth is 210 MHz at 28 GHz and 300 MHz at 38GHz. Fig. 5 shows gain variation of proposed antenna at 28 GHz and 38 GHz. Gain in broadside direction at 28 GHz is found to be 7.5 dBi and at 38 GHz is found to be 7.7dBi. It was observed that we can increase polarization bandwidth at 38 GHz at the cost of polarization bandwidth at 28 GHz by increasing slot section sizes. Surface current distribution at both the frequencies are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7.

Figure 2. S-parameter graph of proposed antenna

Figure 3. Axial ratio graph for lower band (28 GHz)

For better comparison with some of the recent designs on 5G dual band antenna at same frequencies, these designs have been compared with our proposed design. In Table-2 a comparison is shown between recent designs and proposed design. It can be seen that H. Aliakbari et al [2] has made a very good design but its gain on same substrate is less and impedance bandwidth at 38 GHz is 750MHz which is also very less in comparison to proposed design's impedance bandwidth on same frequency i.e. 1.3 GHz bandwidth. Ashraf et al [3] made a good design for dual band 5G antenna but it was not circularly polarized. Gain in [3] is also less in comparison to proposed design. Zhou et al [5] has made a very

good circularly polarized 5G antenna but only at one frequency i.e. 28 GHz. In comparison to all recent 5G dual band antenna design, proposed antenna is better in all aspects of design and performance.

Figure 4. Axial ratio graph for upper band (38 GHz)

Figure 5. Gain of proposed antenna for 28GHz and 38GHz

Figure 6. Surface current magnitude of the proposed antenna at 28 GHz

Figure 7. Surface current magnitude of the proposed antenna at 38 GHz

Table-2 Comparison with some recent designs in Ka Band

Reference	Gain at 28 GHz	Gain at 38GHz	10dB BW at 28GHz	10dB BW at 38 GHz	Axial ratio BW at 28 GHz	Axial ratio BW at 38 GHz
[2]	4dBi	4.5dBi	850MHz	750MHz	200MHz	400MHz
[3]	5.2dBi	5.9dBi	450MHz	2.2GHz	-	-
[5]	Not given	-	1.3GHz at 27.8GHz	-	370MHz at 27.8 GHz	-
Proposed	7.5dBi	7.7dBi	900 MHz at 28 GHz	1.3 GHz	210 MHz	300 MHz

IV. CONCLUSION

For 5G communication a dual band antenna for 28/38 GHz (frequency ratio ~1.35) with high gain and circularly polarization is needed and proposed design is a simple single feed design with defected ground structure working in these dual frequencies with good axial ratio bandwidth and gain. Hence it is concluded that in comparison to some recent work this design is very competitive and can be used for commercial purpose for 28/38 GHz 5G applications.

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